

REVISED VERSION

Consortium Proposal
National Research Data Infrastructure
(NFDI)

KonsortSWD – *nfdi4society*

Second Funding Phase

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This version reflects a 30.5% cut made with the funding decision

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	artificial intelligence
AAI	authentication and authorization infrastructure
AB	Advisory Board
AGD	Archive for Spoken German
AIP	Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam
ALLBUS	German General Social Survey
API	application programming interface
AS	Academy of Sociology
ASI	Association of Social Science Institutes
ASSURED	Accrediting Safe Use of Research Environments
BStatG	Federal Statistics Law
BA	Federal Employment Agency
BAMF	Federal Office for Migration and Refugees
BAMF-FDZ	Research Data Centre of the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees
Base4NFDI	NFDI-wide basic services initiative
BAuA	Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health
BBK	Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance
BERD@NFDI	NFDI consortium: business, economic, and related Data
BestFDM	project: Better results through interoperability and standardised research data management
BIBB	Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training
BIBB-FDZ	Research Data Centre of the Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training
BIPS	Leibniz Institute for Prevention Research and Epidemiology
BMBF	Federal Ministry of Education and Research
bwFDM	Federal State Initiative for Research Management Baden-Württemberg
BZgA	Federal Centre for Health Education
CCT	Cross-cutting topic (i.e. cross-disciplinary / cross-domain topic)
CDIF	cross-domain interoperability framework
CESSDA (ERIC)	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
cf.	confer (= compare / see)
CLARIN (ERIC)	Common Language Resource and Technology Infrastructure
CMS	Content management system
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoO	KonsortSWD Coordination Office
CODI	Automated Coding of Open Responses
CoRDI	NFDI Conference on Research Data Infrastructure
CORS	Comparative Research Center Sweden
CRAN	The Comprehensive R Archive Network
CTS	CoreTrustSeal
DAGStat	German Consortium in Statistics
DALIA	Data Literacy Alliance
da ra	Registration agency for social science and economic data
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DataPlant	NFDI consortium: plant sciences
DataWiz	Data management system to prepare research data
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DDI-CDI	Data Documentation Initiative Cross Domain Integration
Destatis	Federal Statistical Office of Germany
DeZIM	German Centre for Integration and Migration Research

DeZIM.fdz	Research Data Centre of the German Centre for Integration and Migration Research
DFG	German Research Foundation
DGEKW	German Society for Cultural Analysis European Ethnology
DGfE	German Educational Research Association
DGfP	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Politikwissenschaft (en: "German Society for Political Science")
DGfW	German Society for Electoral Studies (en: "German Society for Electoral Studies ")
dggö	German Association for Health Economics
DGI	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Information und Wissen e.V. (en: "German Society for Information and Knowledge")
DGMS	German Society of Medical Sociology
DGPH	German Association for Public Health
DGPs	German Psychological Society
DGPuK	German Communication Association
DGS	German Sociological Association
DGSKA	German Association for Social and Cultural Anthropology
DIE	German Institute for Adult Education Leibniz Centre for Lifelong Learning
DINI	Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformationen e.V. (en: "German Initiative for Network Information")
DIPF	Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education
DiTraRe	Digital Transformation of Research
DIW	German Institute for Economic Research
DJI	German Youth Institute
DKFZ	German Cancer Research Center
DKKV	German Committee for Disaster Risk Reduction
DMP	data management plan
DMP4NFDI	NFDI Basic Service: Data Management Plans for the German National Research Data Infrastructure
DOI	digital object identifier
DRV	German Pension Insurance
DStatG	German Statistical Society
DZHW	German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies
e.g.	for example
EBDC/EBDC@IFO	LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center
EBDC RDC	LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center Research Data Centre
EDDI	European Data Documentation Initiative
EduTrain	NFDI Section for Training and Education
ECPR	European Consortium for Political Research
ELSA	NFDI Section for Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects
ELSST	The European Language Social Science Thesaurus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Entrust	European Network of Trusted Research Environment
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESS (ERIC)	European Social Survey
FaBiO	FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology
FAIR	findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
FAIRagro	NFDI consortium: agrosystems research
FAIR-GPT	AI assistant focused on guiding researchers and data stewards in making their datasets compliant with the FAIR principles.
FDI Committee	Ständiger Ausschuss Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (Committee for Research Data Infrastructure)
FD-LEX	Forschungsdatenbank Lernertexte (en: "research data base learner's texts")
FDLink	Project to promote the anchoring of research data management in the organisational structures and workflows of research institutions
FDM	research data management
FDM-SH	Schleswig-Holstein State Initiative for Research Data Management
FDZ	German for RDC - research data centre
FDZ-AGD	Research Data Centre Archive for Spoken German at Leibniz Institute for the German Language
FDZ at KBA	Research Data Centre at the Federal Motor Transport Authority

FDZ-BAuA	Research Data Centre of the Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health
FDZ-BO	Research Data Center for Business and Organizational Data
FDZ-Bund	Research Data Centre of the Federal Statistical Office
FDZ BZgA	Research Data Centre of the Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training
FDZ-DJI	Research Data Center of the German Youth Institute
FDZ-DZA	Research Data Centre of the German Centre of Gerontology
FDZ-DZHW	Research Data Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies
FDZ eLabour	Centre for Qualitative Data in the Field of Sociology of Labour and Industry
FDZ GePaRD	German Pharmacoepidemiological Research Database
FDZ-Länder	Research Data Centre of the Statistical Offices of the Länder
FDZ-pairfam	Research Data Center of the German Family Panel
FDZ RKI	Research Data Centre of the Robert Koch Institute
FDZ-RV	Research Data Centre of the German Pension Insurance
FDZ-SAFE	Research Data Center of the Leibniz Institute for Financial Research SAFE
FDZ-SOEP	Research Data Centre of the Socio-Economic Panel Study at DIW Berlin - German Institute for Economic Research
FEaA	BMBF Research Initiative for the Conservation of Biodiversity
FID	specialised information service
Forum4MICA	Forum for Making Information Commonly Available
FRBR	Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records
FTE	full-time equivalent
F-UJI	Tool for automated assessment of FAIRness at the dataset level
FU Berlin	Freie Universität Berlin
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union
GEBF	Society for Empirical Educational Research
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
GesundFDM	project: "Angewandtes Forschungsdatenmanagement für die gesundheits- und pflegebezogenen Wissenschaften" (en: "Applied research data management for the health and care sciences")
GFD	Association of Fachdidaktik
GfhF	Society for Research into Higher Education
GHGA	NFDI consortium: German Human Genome-Phenome Archive
GI	German Informatics Society
GND	Integrated Authority File
GO FAIR	GO FAIR is a bottom-up, stakeholder-driven and self-governed initiative that aims to implement the FAIR data principles
GRW	guest researcher workstation
GWGD	Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (en: "Society for Scientific Data Processing")
GWK	Joint Science Conference
HeFDI	Federal State Initiative Hessian Research Data Infrastructures
IAB	Institute for Employment Research
IAM	identity and access management
IAM4NFDI	NFDI Basic Service: Identity and Access Management for the German National Research Data Infrastructure
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Service & Technology
ICPSR	Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research
ID	Identifier
IDAN	International Data Access Network
IDS	Leibniz-Institute for the German Language
IDSC	International Data Service Centre
IDSC IZA	International Data Service Centre (IDSC) at the Institute for the Study of Labour
Ifo (Institute)	Leibniz Institute for Economic Research at the University of Munich
IfSS	Institute of Sports and Sports Science at KIT
infra	NFDI Section Common Infrastructures
IÖR	Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
IOER RDC	RDC of the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
IQB	Institute for Educational Quality Improvement
ISDFPN	International Secure Data Facility Professionals Network
IWH	Halle Institute for Economic Research

IZA	Institute for the Study of Labour
Jupyter4NFDI	NFDI Basic Service: Jupyter-Notebooks application used for various tasks in dealing with research data, e.g. for data analysis and visualisation, statistical modelling, machine learning and deep learning
KGI4NFDI	NFDI Basic Service: Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for the German National Research Data Infrastructure
KBA	Federal Motor Transport Authority
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
KODAQs	Competence Center Data Quality in the Social Sciences
KonsortSWD	Consortium for the Social, Behavioural, Educational, and Economic Sciences
KPI	key performance indicator
KrimG	Kriminologische Gesellschaft (en: "Criminological Society")
KSWD	Conference on Social and Economic Data
LifBi	Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories
LIS	Scientific Library Services and Information Systems
LMU	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (LMU Munich)
LOD	linked open data
MDUC	multidisciplinary use cases
MOJRE Data	eResearch infrastructure for sports science motor activity research data
MVP	minimum viable product
NEPS	National Educational Panel Study
NEPS-ADIAB	Combined dataset of the National Educational Panel Study administrative data of the IAB
NEPS-SC6	Cohort 6 "Adult Education and Lifelong Learning" of the NEPS
NFDI	National Research Data Infrastructure
NFDI4BioDiversity	NFDI consortium: biodiversity, ecology, and environmental data
NFDI4Chem	NFDI consortium: chemistry
NFDI4Bioimage	NFDI consortium: microscopy and bioimage analysis
NFDI4Microbiota	NFDI consortium: microbiota research
NFDI4Culture	NFDI consortium: material and immaterial cultural heritage
NFDI4DataScience	NFDI consortium: data science and Artificial Intelligence
NFDI4Earth	NFDI consortium: earth system sciences
NFDI4Energy	NFDI consortium: interdisciplinary energy system research
NFDI4Health	NFDI consortium: personal health data
NFDI4Memory	NFDI consortium: historically oriented humanities
NFDI4Objects	NFDI consortium: material remains of human history
NFDI-Matwerk	NFDI consortium: materials science and materials engineering
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
ODF	Open Data Format
ODISSEI	Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations
OneNFDI	Describes a desired convergence of multiple infrastructures for RDM across domains. It is a concept that emerged in the preparation of the 2019 paper on Cross-Cutting-Topics.
OpenAPI	open application programming interface
OPERAS	open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities
pairfam	Panel Analysis of Intimate Relationships and Family Dynamics
PID	persistent identifier
PID4NFDI	NFDI Basic Service: Persistent Identifier Services
PolMine	Research group in computational social science at University of Duisburg-Essen
polmineR	R-package for text mining with the Corpus Workbench (CWB) as backend
PostDoc	postdoctoral researcher
PR	public relations
PREMIS	Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies
PreReg in Psychology	Preregistration platform by the Leibniz Institute for Psychology, offering a domain-specific repository. By using preregistration, researchers can verify that their studies have been conducted, analysed, and reported as initially specified.

PROGEDO	As part of the 'L'Infrastructure de Recherche étoile (IR*)', PROGEDO aims to develop a culture of data, and to drive and structure a survey data policy for social science research
Pro LTA	Long term availability/Long term archiving
PROV	a specification that provides a vocabulary to interchange provenance information. Users can do so by marking up their web page using the terms provided or by making available provenance information expressed as linked data.
PUNCH4NFDI	NFDI consortium: particle, astro-, astroparticle, hadron, and nuclear physics
QualiTerm	A controlled vocabulary for the description of central and specific elements of qualitative research, developed by the QualidataNet.
RatSWD	German Data Forum (Rat für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsdaten)
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDC	research data centre
RDC ALLBUS	Research Data Centre ALLBUS at GESIS
RDC GML	Research Data Centre German Microdata Lab at GESIS
RDC-IQB	Research Data Center at the Institute for Educational Quality Improvement
RDC-IWH	Research Data Centre of the Halle Institute for Economic Research
RDC-LifBi	Research Data Center of the Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories
RDC MoL	Forschungsdatenzentrum Motorische Leistungsfähigkeit (en: "Research Data Centre Motoric Performance")
RDC PIAAC	Research Data Centre 'Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies'
RDC-RISC	Research Data Center of the Research Institute Social Cohesion
RDC Ruhr at the RWI	Research Data Centre Ruhr at the RWI - Leibniz Institute for Economic Research
RDC SHARE	Research Data Center of the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
RDI	research data infrastructure
RDM	research data management
RDMCompas	Research Data Management Competence Base
RDMO	research data management organiser
RDSC Bundesbank	Deutsche Bundesbank Research Data and Service Centre
Re3data	Registry of Research Data Repositories
Rfill	German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures
RiC	Records in Context
rOpenSci	Initiative for technical infrastructure in the form of staff and community-contributed R software tools
RWI	Leibniz Institute for Economic Research
SAFE FDZ	Data Center of the Leibniz Institute for Financial Research SAFE – Sustainable Architecture for Finance in Europe
SAMF	Deutsche Vereinigung für Sozialwissenschaftliche Arbeitsmarktforschung (en: "German Association for Social Science Labour Market Research")
SaxFDM	Saxonian Federal State Initiative for Research Data Management
Scorpion KPI Dashboard	Scorpion is a Dashboard that collects and visualizes Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for services.
BASiD	Biographical Data of Selected Insurance Agencies in Germany
SEO	search engine optimisation
SFB	collaborative research centres
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe
ShaReD	Sharing and Reusing Data
SIS	specialised information service
SIS SCA	specialised information service for social and cultural anthropology
SocioHub	specialised information service for sociology
SOEP	Socio-Economic Panel
SOEP-CMI-ADIAB,	Combined Dataset of the Survey data of SOEP Core, IAB-SOEP Migration Sample, IAB-BAMF-SOEP Survey of Refugees and SOEP Innovation Sample linked to administrative data of the IAB.
SOEP-RV	Combined dataset for life course research of the Socio-Economic Panel and administrative pension data.
SOFI	Sociological Research Institute Göttingen
SSH	social sciences and humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

SSHOC-DE	SSHOC in Germany
Stamp	standardised data management plan for educational research
StanDem	Standardising (Socio-)Demographic data
StC	KonsortSWD Steering Committee
TA	Task Area
Text+	NFDI consortium: language and text-based research data
TF	Task force
TFER	NFDI Task Force Evaluation and Reporting
TH	University of Applied Sciences
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
VDS	Verband Deutscher Stadttestatistik (en: "Association of German City Statistics ")
VerbundFDB	Network of Educational Research Data
VfS	German Economic Association
VHB	German Association for Business Research
WG	working group
WZB	WZB Berlin Social Science Center
XML	Extensible Markup Language
ZB MED	Information Centre for Life Sciences
ZBW	Information Centre for Economics
ZEW-FDZ	Research Data Center of the Leibniz Centre for European Economic Research
ZIS	Open Access Repository for Measurement Instruments
ZPID	Leibniz Institute for Psychology

1 General Information

KonsortSWD – nfdi4society

Consortium for the Social, Behavioural, Educational, and Economic Sciences

KonsortSWD – nfdi4society

Konsortium für die Sozial-, Verhaltens, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften

KonsortSWD, the nfdi4society, supplies research data management (RDM) solutions for the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. Building on the successes integrating the RDM landscape more closely through services during the first phase, KonsortSWD's mission is to further *strengthen, widen, and deepen* the research data infrastructure for the study of human society. It aims to be *the* RDM platform for its communities.

KonsortSWD builds on the established and very successful network of currently 41 Research Data Centres and leverages RatSWD (German Data Forum) to universally involve its communities. Central to its mission are its three overarching, strategic aims: A) Make RDM part of the research routine in KonsortSWD's disciplines; B) consolidate reputable services, improve user-friendliness, and address new needs; and C) anchor RDM structures and advance "OneNFDI". These aims will be realised through ten central objectives, ranging from refining data quality criteria to strategically extending national and international networks. KonsortSWD's work program is structured into five Task Areas: 1) Involving Communities; 2) Advancing FAIRness; 3) Enhancing Competences; 4) Integrating Data; and 5) Governance and Sustainability. Each Task Area comprises several measures designed to achieve the consortium's objectives. Crucial components include the German Data Forum (RatSWD), the Committee for Research Data Infrastructure (FDI Committee), training activities, and services to improve data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR). The consortium will continue to prioritise close collaboration with its diverse stakeholders, including individual researchers, academic associations, and Research Data Centres (RDCs). Internationally, KonsortSWD will strengthen ties with other national RDM initiatives and continue to participate in the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) and build links to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Within NFDI, it will continue to actively contribute to cross-cutting topics, foster multidisciplinary use cases, and support the development of basic services. Sustainability is a key focus for the second funding phase: KonsortSWD will develop business models for its services to ensure the long-term viability of its offerings. The consortium's governance structure, centred around the Steering Committee and the five Task Areas, will be optimised to support these efforts.

KonsortSWD actively consolidates its service portfolio, ensuring that established services consistently meet the community's evolving needs while developing new services to address emerging demands. By leveraging its strengths, expanding its reach, and proactively adapting to the dynamic landscape of RDM, KonsortSWD is poised to make significant contributions to its disciplines and the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in the coming years.

Summary of the proposal in German

KonsortSWD, nfdi4society, liefert Lösungen für das Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) in den Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften. Aufbauend auf den Erfolgen der ersten Phase bei der Integration der FDM-Landschaft durch Dienste, sieht KonsortSWD seine Mission darin, die Forschungsdateninfrastruktur zur Erforschung der Gesellschaft zu stärken, zu erweitern und zu vertiefen.

KonsortSWD will *die* FDM-Plattform für seine Communities sein, baut auf dem etablierten und sehr erfolgreichen Netzwerk von derzeit 41 Forschungsdatenzentren auf und kann dank des RatSWD seine communities umfassend einbinden. KonsortSWD hat drei Oberziele: A) Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) als Teil der Forschungsroutine in den Disziplinen von KonsortSWD etablieren; B) Ansehen von Dienstleistungen festigen, Benutzerfreundlichkeit verbessern und neue Bedürfnisse adressieren; C) FDM-Strukturen verankern und "OneNFDI" voranbringen. Hierfür stehen zehn Unterziele, die von der Verfeinerung der Kriterien für die Datenqualität bis zum strategischen Ausbau nationaler und internationaler Netzwerke reichen. Das Arbeitsprogramm ist in fünf Task Areas gegliedert: 1) Communities einbinden; 2) FAIRness vorantreiben; 3) Kompetenzen fördern; 4) Daten zusammenführen; und 5) Governance und Nachhaltigkeit. Jede Task Area umfasst mehrere Arbeitspakete. Wesentliche Bestandteile sind der RatSWD, der FDI-Ausschuss, Trainingsaktivitäten und Angebote zur Verbesserung von Auffindbarkeit, Zugang, Interoperabilität und Nachnutzbarkeit von Daten (FAIR).

Weiterhin arbeitet KonsortSWD eng mit Forschenden, Fachgesellschaften und Forschungsdatenzentren (FDZ) zusammen. Auf internationaler Ebene wird KonsortSWD die Zusammenarbeit mit anderen nationalen FDM-Initiativen stärken und zur Research Data Alliance (RDA) der Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) und der European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) beitragen. Innerhalb der NFDI wird KonsortSWD weiterhin aktiv zu Querschnittsthemen beitragen, multidisziplinäre Use Cases fördern und die Entwicklung von Basisdiensten unterstützen. In der zweiten Förderphase steht die Nachhaltigkeit im Vordergrund: KonsortSWD wird Geschäftsmodelle für seine Dienste entwickeln, um die langfristige Tragfähigkeit seiner Angebote zu gewährleisten. Die Organisationsstruktur des Konsortiums, die auf den Lenkungsausschuss und den fünf Aufgabenbereiche aufbaut, wird optimiert, um diese Aufgaben zu unterstützen.

KonsortSWD konsolidiert sein Dienstleistungsportfolio aktiv und stellt sicher, dass die bestehenden Angebote den sich wandelnden Bedürfnissen der Community gerecht werden. Gleichzeitig entwickelt KonsortSWD neue Angebote, um neue Anforderungen bedienen zu können. Durch die Nutzung seiner Stärken, die Ausweitung seiner Reichweite und die vorausschauende Anpassung an eine dynamische FDM-Landschaft ist KonsortSWD in der Lage, in den kommenden Jahren einen wesentlichen Beitrag für seine Disziplinen und die Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) zu leisten.

1.1 Applicant institution

Applicant institution	Location
GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research Data Centre ALLBUS at GESIS ▪ Research Data Center Elections at GESIS ▪ Research Data Centre German Microdata Lab (GML) at GESIS ▪ Research Data Center International Survey Programmes at GESIS ▪ Research Data Center PIAAC at GESIS 	Mannheim and Cologne

1.2 Spokesperson

Spokesperson	Institution, location
Christof Wolf	GESIS, Mannheim

1.3 Co-Applicant Institutions

Co-applicant institution ¹	Institution, location
DIPF – Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research Data Centre for Education at the DIPF 	Frankfurt (Main)
DIW Berlin – German Institute for Economic Research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research Data Center for Business and Organizational Data (RDC-BO) ▪ Research Data Centre of the Socio-Economic Panel Study (RDC-SOEP) 	Berlin
DZHW – German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research Data Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (RDC-DZHW) 	Hannover
Freie Universität Berlin	Berlin
ifo Institute – Leibniz Institute for Economic Research at the University of Munich <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center (EBDC) 	Munich
KIT – Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Karlsruhe
LIfBi – Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research Data Center of the Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories (RDC-LIfBi) 	Bamberg
RWI - Leibniz Institute for Economic Research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research Data Centre Ruhr at the RWI (RDC-Ruhr) 	Essen
University of Bremen <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research Data Centre Qualiservice ▪ Research Data Centre of the Research Institute Social Cohesion (RDC-RISC) 	Bremen
University of Duisburg-Essen	Duisburg
WZB – Berlin Social Science Center	Berlin

¹ As Research Data Centres (RDC) play a central role for the research data infrastructure proposed to be further developed in this proposal, we also list the RDC situated at the (co-) applicant institutions. Others see Participants.

ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics	Kiel / Hamburg
ZPID – Leibniz Institute for Psychology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Center of the Leibniz Institute for Psychology (RDC at ZPID) 	Trier

1.4 Co-Spokespersons

Co-spokesperson ²	Institution, location	Task area(s)
Christian Aßmann	LIfBi, Bamberg	3 (lead)
Katarina Blask	ZPID, Trier	3 (lead)
Andreas Blätte	University of Duisburg-Essen, Duisburg	2
Philipp Breidenbach	RWI, Essen	4
Jan Goebel	SOEP at DIW Berlin, Berlin	4 (lead)
Jan Paul Heisig	WZB, Berlin	1 (lead)
Betina Hollstein	University of Bremen, Bremen	2, 3, 4
David Broneske Monika Jungbauer-Gans	DZHW, Hannover	1
Bernd Kleimann	DZHW, Hannover	5
Katja Keller (née Klemm)	KIT, Karlsruhe	4
Stefan Liebig	Freie Universität Berlin, Berlin	4
Brigitte Mathiak	GESIS, Cologne	2 (lead)
Claudia Niessner	KIT, Karlsruhe	4 (lead)
Marc Rittberger	DIPF, Frankfurt on the Main	2, 3
<u>Kerstin Schneider</u>	<u>University Wuppertal</u>	<u>1 (lead)</u>
Klaus Tochtermann	ZBW, Kiel / Hamburg	2 (lead)
Sebastian Wichert	ifo, Munich; LMU Munich	4
Christof Wolf	GESIS, Mannheim	5 (lead)

1.5 Participants³

Participating institutions ⁴	Location
Bundesarchiv – Federal Archives	Coblenz
German Institute for Adult Education Leibniz Centre for Lifelong Learning (DIE)	Bonn
Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam (AIP)	Potsdam
LMU Munich	Munich
Institute for Employment Research (IAB) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre (FDZ) of the German Federal Employment Agency (BA) 	Nuremberg
Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF)	Nuremberg

² New co-spokespersons institutions are highlighted in bold.

³ Please note that not all 41 Research Data Centers are listed as participants. Some are situated at co-applicant institutions (such as RDC-SOEP and RDC-BO at DIW).

⁴ New participating institutions are highlighted in bold.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre of the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF-FDZ) 	
<p>Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre of the Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (FDZ-BAuA) 	Berlin
<p>Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre at the Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (BIBB-FDZ) 	Bonn
<p>Leibniz Institute for Prevention Research and Epidemiology (BIPS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre German Pharmacoepidemiological Research Database (FDZ GePaRD) 	Bremen
<p>Federal Centre for Health Education (BZgA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre at the Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training (FDZ BZgA) 	Cologne
<p>German Youth Institute (DJI)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre (FDZ-DJI) 	Munich
<p>German Centre of Gerontology (DZA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre (FDZ-DZA) 	Berlin
<p>German Centre for Integration and Migration Research (DeZIM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre (DeZIM.fdz) 	Berlin
<p>eLabour e.V.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> eLabour Centre for Qualitative Data (FDZ eLabour) 	Göttingen
<p>Institute for the Study of Labour (IZA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Data Service Centre (IDSC IZA) 	Bonn
<p>Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG)</p>	Göttingen
<p>Institute for Educational Quality Improvement (IQB)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Center (FDZ IQB) 	Berlin
<p>Leibniz Institute for the German Language (IDS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre Archive for Spoken German (FDZ AGD) 	Mannheim
<p>Leibniz Institute for Financial Research SAFE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Center of the Leibniz Institute for Financial Research SAFE (FDZ-SAFE) 	Frankfurt (Main)
<p>Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre (IOER RDC) 	Dresden
<p>Halle Institute of Economic Research (IWH)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre (RDC-IWH) 	Halle (Saale)
<p>Federal Motor Transport Authority (KBA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Data Centre (FDZ at KBA) 	Flensburg
<p>Leibniz Centre for European Economic Research (ZEW)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEW Research Data Centre (ZEW-FDZ) 	Mannheim
<p>LMU Munich</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center (EBDC) 	Munich

SHARE BERLIN Institute <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Data Center of the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (RDC SHARE) 	Berlin
German Pension Insurance (DRV) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Data Centre (FDZ-RV) 	Berlin
Robert Koch Institute (RKI) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Data Centre at the (FDZ RKI) 	Berlin
Statistical Offices of the Länder <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Data Centre (FDZ-Länder) 	Düsseldorf
Federal Statistical Office <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Data Centre (FDZ-Bund) 	Wiesbaden
Stifterverband <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Data Centre Wissenschaftsstatistik (FDZ Wissenschaftsstatistik) 	Essen
University of Cologne <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Data Center of the German Family Panel (FDZ-pairfam) • Forschungsdatenbank Lernertexte at Mercator Institute (FD-LEX) 	Cologne
<i>Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ)</i>	Leipzig

1.5.1 Contributions by Participants

KonsortSWD delivers services to consolidate a network researchers and data providers all of whom contribute significantly and become more than the sum total of their parts thanks to activities by KonsortSWD, funded by DFG. Crucially important contributions come from volunteers from many institutions in this network: the 20 members of **RatSWD** (German Data Forum) contribute their time on a voluntary basis, ranging from two hours per week (regular member) to ten hours per week (chairs), fielding extensive support for the data infrastructure in Germany. Additionally, six external members of RatSWD working groups contribute 0.5 hours per week. The 41 representatives from the research data centres (RDC) who form the **FDI Committee** (Committee for Research Data Infrastructure) volunteer their time, offering significant support to Germany's data infrastructure. Regular members spend about one hour a week, while the chairs spend up to five hours a week.

All participants with a Research Data Center ("FDZ" in the table above) contribute to maintaining the RDC network at the heart of the infrastructure KonsortSWD builds on. They finance staff for data curation, consultations, and providing access to sensitive data; 335 full time equivalents (FTE) in total across all RDCs in 2023.⁵ The ensuing list describes contributions of participants which receive funding in this proposal regardless of whether they operate an RDC or not:

- ✓ Bundesarchiv - Federal Archives contributes expertise on long-term preservation.
- ✓ Destatis, the Federal Statistical Office contributes 24.7 person months through its RDC.

⁵ This total includes RDC at co-applicant institutions but also covers one RDC, that of the German Federal Reserve (Bundesbank) (RDSC) which is not a participant in KonsortSWD. For contributions of co-applicants cf. [Description and Summary of Contributions by \(Co-\) Applicants, see 8, Table 8.4](#).

- ✓ DIE contributes expertise on data curation for educational data and data provision.
- ✓ DRV - German Pension Insurance contributes 39.3 person months through its RDC.
- ✓ GWDG hosts the ticket system for KonsortSWD Helpdesk and collaborates on PIDService.
- ✓ IAB - Institute for Employment Research contributes 43.9 person months through its RDC.
- ✓ IDS - Leibniz Institute for the German Language contributes 39.0 person months through its RDC.
- ✓ Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam (AIP) contributes expertise on their software, the Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO).
- ✓ Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (LMU Munich) co-hosts EDBC with ifo Institute and, as partner in BERD@NFDI, collaborates on development of the ASSURED service.
- ✓ UFZ contributes to the creation of workflows for data from environmental sciences.

1.6 Participating Individuals

Participating individual	Institution, location
Kerstin Schneider	University of Wuppertal, Wuppertal

1.6.1 Contributions by Participating Individuals

Kerstin Schneider is the deputy-chair of RatSWD, a position requiring substantial amounts of time.

1.7 DFG Review Boards

1.16-01 - Social and Cultural Anthropology and Ethnology	1.24 - Economics
1.21 - Educational Research	1.25-05 - Criminology
1.22 - Psychology	2.22-01 - Epidemiology and Medical Biometry/Statistics
1.23 - Social Sciences	2.22-02 - Public Health, Healthcare Research, Social and Occupational Medicine

2 Scope and Objectives

KonsortSWD's mission is to *strengthen, widen, and deepen* the research data infrastructure for the study of human society. We aim to be *the* platform research data management (RDM) for our communities. Building upon an extensive network of currently 41 RDCs accredited by RatSWD (cf. 3.4.1), the consortium ensures that sensitive data and services for managing such data are at the core of its operations. As a platform, KonsortSWD facilitates secure and user-oriented data access, adhering to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to strengthen the management and reuse of both sensitive and non-sensitive data. Through widening, the consortium adapts to the dynamic research landscape by making relevant new data types available

to researchers. Leveraging RatSWD's reputation as a trusted and researcher-elected governing body, KonsortSWD's activities are based on the needs and priorities of the research community, ensuring that the data infrastructure remains robust, high-quality, and responsive to the evolving demands of researchers' communities. Deepening ties within the NFDI will enhance data accessibility, collaboration, and sharing across research communities, elevating the quality and efficiency of RDM solutions.

This chapter introduces the scope and objectives of KonsortSWD within NFDI. KonsortSWD is inherently interdisciplinary, encompassing the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences.

2.1 Research Domains or Research Methods

RDM has become an increasingly critical aspect of modern scientific inquiry. KonsortSWD, the *nfdi4society*, is a discipline-based consortium, supplying RDM solutions in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. These disciplines deal with complex human values and behaviours, societal structures, and economic systems and thus require robust and tailored approaches to managing the vast amounts of data generated through research, public administration, and digitalisation, including "Big Data". The intricate nature of these fields necessitates RDM strategies that are closely aligned with the specific subjects of analysis, which can be broadly categorised into three societal levels: macro, meso, and micro.

At the macro level, researchers focus on countries or large-scale economic systems. Economists may analyse national or state-level economic indicators or cross-country comparisons. Educational researchers might examine educational policies. Political scientists frequently study national party systems and international relations (Valentim & Dinas, 2024). These macro-level studies often involve aggregated data that are readily available through public sources.

The meso level encompasses research on social groups, regions, networks or organisations. This might include studies on specific demographic groups, social networks, educational institutions, labour market dynamics (Heisig et al., 2019; Löwe & Unger, 2023), or regional economic trends. While less common than macro-level research, meso-level studies provide valuable insights into the dynamics of smaller, more defined units within larger systems.

Micro-level research focuses on individuals or individual legal entities and is perhaps the most prevalent and challenging in terms of RDM. In the social and behavioural sciences, studies often involve detailed personal data from participants (Power et al., 2023). Educational researchers frequently work with student-level data, while economists may analyse individual consumer behaviour or firm-level financial information (Richter & Schneider, 2021). Political scientists examine voter behaviour; sociologists study personal histories and social interactions (Hollstein, 2021; Mikucka et al., 2021; Vacchiano et al., 2024). The prevalence of micro-level research in these fields is significant, as it allows for nuanced understanding of human behaviour, learning processes, and economic decision-making at the individual level (Bruckmeier et al., 2021). Research topics also

include ageing and health (Carstensen & Jungbauer-Gans, 2016; Grube et al., 2019; Holzwarth & Wolf, 2023), migration (Kalter & Foroutan, 2024) and behaviour on the internet (Kirkizh et al., 2024). Yet, it is precisely this micro-level data that presents the most significant challenges for RDM. The sensitive nature of individual-level information raises critical concerns about privacy, confidentiality, and ethical (e.g. Roth & Von Unger, 2018; Von Unger, 2021) data handling. Thus, effective RDM must address these concerns.

KonsortSWD defines research data as **sensitive** when it contains information relating to identified or identifiable living individuals, confidential details, or ethically sensitive information. Sensitive data typically pertains to persons, households, or businesses. All data types can contain sensitive information: data from personal interviews, from surveys, in videos but also data from wearables and from social media. Such data requires stringent protection due to the risk of re-identifying individuals through the aggregation of various data points. Re-identification, unauthorized access, or disclosure of sensitive data can potentially cause harm or have adverse consequences to the subjects involved.

Research in KonsortSWD fields relies on a diverse array of data sources, many of which were not originally collected for scientific analysis. For instance, social scientists may study human interaction through messages exchanged on social media platforms, while economists frequently utilise data collected by social insurance systems or central banks. Each source may have its own format, structure, and associated metadata.

Some of the data types referred to above, are often called „Big Data“. KonsortSWD does not primarily focus on these data. In NFDI it is BERD@NFDI who provide RDM solutions for these data types. We stress, however, that there is a substantial overlap in partner institutions between our two consortia (GESIS, LMU, ZEW, ZBW) and that we cooperate intensively so that interdependencies resulting from connections between data types are addressed.

In terms of research methods, researchers routinely work with survey data, text data from social media posts or parliamentary protocols, network information, experimental and quasi-experimental data, administrative data, observational data from field and lab studies, interview transcripts, and audio/video. Each data type requires specific handling, storage, and analysis techniques. Effective RDM must therefore provide robust protocols for data harmonisation, documentation, and ensuring compliance with varying data usage agreements and regulations.

Figure 1: Inherently interdisciplinary: RDC data for interdisciplinary research fields

RDCs acting as data trustees are key to effective RDM in our domain (Buck et al., 2022; Fuß & Laible, 2023; Hoffstätter & Linne, 2022). In this role they provide sensitive data offering unique – because not otherwise accessible at the same level of detail – insights into many topics. To underscore the relevance and the breadth of the spectrum of data in RDCs, we use the [Interdisciplinary research field classification](#) (KDSF, 2022) and map its categories to RDC data: Figure 1 shows to which of these interdisciplinary fields KonsortSWD provides data through RDCs⁶. These data evidently address many areas of interdisciplinary research, much beyond KonsortSWD’s disciplines. KonsortSWD is therefore in an excellent position to help NFDI attain one of its central goals: “NFDI will contribute significantly to answering new interdisciplinary research questions with high social relevance.” (GWK, 2018).

2.1.2 Impact of KonsortSWD

The Research Data Centre (RDC) network has consistently shown a significant impact on research, as evidenced by the increasing number of downloads and publications. In 2023 alone, the 41 RDCs provided **6,852** data products, with **586** new additions that year (see Figure 2). These data products were downloaded **72,289** times in 2023, indicating a high level of engagement from the research community. Moreover, the data provided by RDCs was used in **3,008** publications in 2023, up from 2,359 publications in 2019. This increase in impact on research output is not merely due to the growing number of RDCs but also reflects an increase in the average number of publications per RDC, which rose from 69 in 2019 to 73 in 2023. Ideally this number reflects the dividend of documentation and FAIRification efforts (cf. 4.3) which results in a more productive use of data

⁶ Data based on self-descriptions on RDC’s websites, Figure 1 does not weight by the number of datasets provided.

provided. Together, these figures underscore the essential role that RDCs play in facilitating research and highlight the importance of the resources provided by KonsortSWD to maintain and enhance this network.

Since its inception in 2020, KonsortSWD has added value to the existing infrastructure, primarily through enhancing processes rather than directly impacting research outputs. The establishment of services like Forum4MICA has enabled researchers to share expertise on RDC data, fostering a collaborative environment. KonsortSWD's efforts have led to the creation of 12 operational services, which have generated significant synergies within the research community (for an overview see 4.4 and Appendix A5). The number of registered users of RDC data and services reached **51,747** in 2023 (figure includes ca. 150 registered users at Forum4MICA). In addition, KonsortSWD invested in community work which is bound to show in usage numbers with services becoming more and more available: KonsortSWD involved its communities, at **37** events in 2023, like conferences or through a “Roadshow” (cf. 3.1.3) (Miller et al., 2024). For further indicators that can inform impact, please see the Data Sheet (A5).

Figure 2: 2023 Key Performance Indicators for KonsortSWD's Impact

KonsortSWD's first proposal in 2019 (Adena et al., 2020) emphasized the integration of a diverse data landscape. This goal has been achieved through various services that tie the elements of this landscape together. For example:

- **Forum4MICA** has emerged as a significant platform for connecting researchers and RDCs. The online forum, developed by KonsortSWD, has rapidly become a valuable resource for **accessing and sharing expertise** on research data management. In 2023, Forum4MICA with 16 participating RDCs, generated over 1,100 unique visits and approximately 175,000 pageviews across nearly 500 new posts. In terms of impact, Forum4MICA has significantly reduced the time researchers need to access expert knowledge from RDCs.
- Support and Consulting Activities include **harmonized contracts** for data ingest and access in RDCs and recommendations on increasing findability of data on the web. Our contract templates (Schallaböck, Hoffstätter, et al., 2023; Schallaböck, Kreuzer, et al., 2023b, 2023a) have seen extensive interest, as evidenced by over 2,500 downloads on Zenodo in 2023. While we cannot track adoption, it is safe to assume that some of these downloads lead to improvements for data users. Thanks to our recommendations on findability, RDC research data on the web attracted **significant increases in web traffic** (Limani et al., 2023). Guidelines on findability have

garnered international attention and will be part of outputs by RDA (working group (WG) on [Data Granularity](#) and IG [Data Discovery Paradigms](#) (Wu et al., 2024).

These services have been instrumental in creating a cohesive and integrated research data infrastructure. KonsortSWD had also set the goal in 2019 of diversifying support for different data types. Impactful initiatives include:

- [QualidataNet](#): The first portal for finding and archiving **qualitative research data**, which attracted 700 visitors in December 2023, its first month of operation, alone.
- [Linking Textual Data](#): A collection of R-libraries facilitating **liking survey and text data**, which saw 20,783 downloads, indicating active usage within the community.
- [Harmonisation \(now StanDem\)](#): Recommendations on how to uniformly measure sociodemographic attributes in survey – a precondition for **combining data** from different such surveys – were partially developed with NFDI4Health and have been adopted by two major surveys: ALLBUS and NEPS. Publications (Ortmanns, 2020; Palm et al., 2023; Schneider et al., 2022, 2023) were viewed over 1,200 times and downloaded nearly 1,000 times. Documentation for each sociodemographic characteristic has been published at the [ZIS Open Access Repository](#) since December 2023, with entries viewed almost 1,250 times and downloaded 60 times.
- KonsortSWD's impact is also visible in **data availability** (Aßmann & Schlücker, 2023): newly curated datasets comprise data on life stories (combining longitudinal qualitative and quantitative data) (Habermas, 2022b, 2022a), video observed patient-doctor interactions in four countries (Sommer et al., 2021; Weiß et al., 2021, 2022), a repository for bilateral science and technology agreements (Rüffin, 2021), data on 10,000 students that allow identification and analysis of causes of accidents and injuries in the school context (Klocke et al., 2022) and comparative panel data from Germany and the US on media exposure and opinion formation that include web-tracking data (Guess et al., 2022; Munzert et al., 2022a, 2022b). Four further projects to curate datasets will be funded via so-called RDM Grants until 2025⁷.

KonsortSWD also made impact towards its goal of fostering skills development as set forth in the first proposal:

- The **Standardised Data Management Plan** (Stamp) generates impact through structured guidance for writing - often mandatory - DMPs (DDP-Bildung & Verbund Forschungsdaten Bildung, 2023). In April 2024, an initial version of Stamp was integrated into [RDMO](#), a much used software tool supporting researchers in RDM throughout the project lifecycle by facilitating the creation and sharing of DMPs in machine-actionable format (Anders et al., 2024) enhancing its usability. [Stamp](#), saw **1,692** visitors in 2023.

⁷ RDM Grants are not part of the second proposal as sufficient funding now exists from DFG and other funders to assure solid RDM from the beginning of a research project.

- KonsortSWD has furthermore developed a **social science module** for the [RDM Certificate Course at TH Köln](#), a comprehensive program aimed at equipping participants with the skills and knowledge necessary for effective RDM. The course will provide reliable impact through the know-how of its graduates. This course is part of [RDMCompas](#), our training platform which will roll out most of its content in the coming months.
- Additionally, RDCs offered **80 RDM-related trainings** in 2023.

A substantial impact KonsortSWD has had, is on **policies**: Thanks to KonsortSWD's funding, RatSWD has not only provided valuable community input, but was able to successfully continue to inform public data policy: since 2020, RatSWD answered 12 requests for comments on legal drafts by federal ministries and issued 14 opinion papers on legislative initiatives relating to research data.

Some projects initiated by KonsortSWD have shown potential in their prototype stages but have yet to be fully released to demonstrate their full impact. For instance, the Persistent Identifier (PID) service, is designed to enhance data management and accessibility by ensuring that datasets can be reliably located and cited over time (Saldanha Bach, Klas, & Mutschke, 2023b). Once fully operational, the PID service is expected to significantly improve the efficiency and reliability of research data management.

KonsortSWD will conclude the illustration of its impact with two qualitative **case studies**, mirroring real-world use cases:

In 2023, Lukas, a researcher working with wage tax data from the RDCs of the Statistical offices, found himself navigating complex datasets. Utilizing [Forum4MICA](#), an online platform designed for data- and RDM-related discussions, Lukas could easily post his questions and receive expert guidance. For instance, when Lukas sought to identify wage tax cases post-2012, he posted his query on the forum and received a detailed response within hours, significantly accelerating his research process. This collaborative environment not only provided immediate solutions but also allowed Lukas to benefit from a growing repository of shared knowledge. In contrast, in 2020, without Forum4MICA, researchers like Lukas had to rely on traditional methods such as emailing RDCs, often waiting days for a response. The introduction of Forum4MICA thus represents a substantial improvement, streamlining data access and fostering a collaborative research community.

Gabriela, a PhD researcher in political science studying the motivations behind civic engagement through biographical narratives, faces the challenge of ensuring her sensitive data can be reused while maintaining interviewee anonymity. Turning to [QualidataNet](#), she finds a wealth of resources on data sharing, archiving, and reuse that adhere to strict data protection, research ethics, and data security standards. The platform provides comprehensive guidelines on how to manage and share qualitative data, ensuring that her work can be securely archived and made accessible for future research projects. This centralized repository not only simplifies the process of data management but also connects her with a network of research data centres, archives, and repositories, facilitating

the secondary use of her data. Before 2023, Gabriela would have had to rely on emails and fragmented information, making the process more cumbersome and less efficient.

RDCs and KonsortSWD have significantly enhanced RDM, as evidenced by the substantial increase in data products, downloads, and publications. Their collaborative efforts and innovative services have already streamlined data access, helped foster a vibrant research community, and informed public data policy.

2.1.3 Aims for the Second Funding Period

After achieving our goal to start integrating the landscape around RDCs in the first funding period, and in line with the German Research Foundation's (DFG) funding criteria, strongly emphasising the consolidation of NFDI (NFDI Expert Committee, 2023), we aim to be *the* RDM platform for our communities and have three overarching aims for the second funding period, detailed objectives follow in 2.2.1:

A Make RDM part of the research routine in KonsortSWD's disciplines.

We support research on society, in particular through sensitive data⁸, and expand RDM competences.

B Consolidate reputable services, improve user-friendliness, and address new needs.

We continue to support RDM for sensitive data by consolidating a portfolio of user-friendly services. At the same time, KonsortSWD will keep addressing new needs based on community demands. Additionally, our focus will be to develop business models⁹.

C Anchor RDM structures and advance "OneNFDI".¹⁰

FDI Committee and RatSWD, key components of KonsortSWD's RDM framework, will interact even more strongly with NFDI. KonsortSWD will provide RDM resources from the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences to support OneNFDI and its services.

2.1.4 Goals for NFDI

Advancing "OneNFDI" has been at the core of the drive to promote professional RDM since the Berlin-Declaration, which we have co-authored (Glöckner et al., 2019a). In addition to aim C and objectives O8 – O10 (see below), we continue to contribute to NFDI

1. through staff and expertise to all sections and their working groups that directly relate to one or more of our services (cf. 5).

⁸ See footnote 5.

⁹ In the context of this proposal, a business model refers to a detailed concept outlining the financial, operational, and organizational specifics for delivering a RDM service. The term aligns with DFG's funding criteria, which emphasise sustainability and does not necessarily imply user-based pricing models.

¹⁰ OneNFDI describes a desired convergence of multiple infrastructures for RDM across domains. It is a concept that emerged in the preparation of the 2019 paper on Cross-Cutting-Topics (Glöckner et al., 2019a).

2. by supporting the introduction of and adaptation of Basic Services (cf. Basic Services).
3. by further building on the cooperations we have already developed with selected consortia (Amelung, Bodenschatz, et al., 2023; Eberl et al., 2024) to advance RDM in areas of mutual interest. This crucially involves multidisciplinary use cases.

2.2 Objectives and Measuring Success

2.2.1 Central Objectives

KonsortSWD sets out to realise the three aims outlined in 2.1.3 through the following objectives. All of which are central to further entrenching RDM for our disciplines in NFDI. All will, therefore, require long-term funding beyond 2030. In italics, we briefly explain how we intend to measure success; a more thorough presentation on criteria for success and its measurement can be found in 4.1.1 and 4.4.3, respectively.

Objectives relating to aim A: Make RDM part of the research routine in KonsortSWD's disciplines.

- O1. To support research on social processes KonsortSWD will advance RDM, systematically expand data access, and refine quality criteria for data. *Success will manifest itself in increasing numbers of users. Success stories in addition will portray the scientific gain achieved through the eased access to sensitive data.*
- O2. To expand RDM competences, particularly for sensitive data, among researchers and RDM professionals, KonsortSWD will interlock RDM Compas, KonsortSWD's platform for training material, with all competence-related activities. *Success will manifest itself in the number of users of RDM training materials.*
- O3. To enhance usability of our infrastructure KonsortSWD will strengthen efforts to automate and standardise RDM in our disciplines thereby increasing scalability of services. *Success will manifest itself in new (semi-)automated and / or standardised RDM processes.*
- O4. To establish RDM we will target early career researchers by highlighting services offered by KonsortSWD. Our aim is for KonsortSWD to be recognized as the platform fostering RDM for research on society. *Success will be measured by attendance at events for early career researchers, and success stories illustrating impact on research projects.*

Objectives relating to aim B: Consolidate reputable services, improve user-friendliness, and address new needs

- O5. KonsortSWD will ramp up efforts to establish itself as the go-to platform for RDM services within our target communities. In particular, we will work to embed our services into externally funded projects through partnerships and collaborations. *Success will manifest itself in the number of cooperations with such projects and in RDM outputs from such projects supported by KonsortSWD.*

O6. To assure the degree of reliability necessary to build research strategies on our services, we will establish sustainable business and operating models for them. *Success will manifest itself in the business and operating models defined as deliverables for all services (cf. 3.5.1).*

O7. To benefit from international developments in RDM, we will strategically use and, if necessary, extend our national and international networks, to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in particular. *Success will manifest itself in bilateral meetings and success stories from international cooperations.*

Objectives relating to aim C: Anchor RDM structures and advance “OneNFDI”

O8. We aim to expand collaborations within NFDI that improve the quality of RDM across disciplines in the spirit of “OneNFDI”. These will serve as cornerstones for the definition of standards and of a viable long-term organisational model. To this end, we build on experiences from integrating the data infrastructure in our disciplines through the FDI-committee. *Success will manifest itself in jointly collected collaboration data (Amelung, Bodenschatz, et al., 2023; Eberl et al., 2024).*

O9. To benefit researchers with multimodal data and those linking data across disciplines, we will support and fund joint multidisciplinary use cases (Ebert et al., 2023). Strategic partnerships with other consortia and strong support for basic services in NFDI’s sections will complement this. *Success will be measured by the number of supported multidisciplinary use cases, resulting prototypes, and related success stories.*

O10. RDM of sensitive data, not only in KonsortSWD’s disciplines, depends on legal and regulatory settings. RatSWD will continue to be uniquely placed to advise policy makers and administrators shaping these rules and regulations. *Success will manifest itself through continued visibility of RatSWD’s influence on research data policies.*

We will reference these objectives throughout the proposal.

2.2.2 DFG Key Objectives

This proposal also references the following key objectives by DFG (NFDI Expert Committee, 2023) in chapters 3 to 5 and relating to each measure.

- a) (Further) develop research data management for the target group(s) addressed and, leading on from this, identify the core tasks for which long-term funding is required beyond the period of project funding.
- b) Expand inclusion of target community/communities, intensify feedback, increase the use of services beyond the consortium partners themselves, integrate new (sub-) communities where appropriate.

- c) Consolidate and expand the relevant structures in order to be able to continuously meet both the evolving requirements of the target groups and the NFDI as a networked infrastructure with a common architecture.
- d) Stabilise, advance and promote a quality-assured service portfolio with regard to the communities addressed to date and also new communities yet to be addressed where relevant.
- e) Expand relevant information and further training programmes in a targeted manner.
- f) Implement an organisational model that is sustainable in the long term and ensures a consortium's capacity to engage in participatory processes as well as its sustainable use of human resources.
- g) Develop a sustainable model that ensures the continued operation and ongoing funding of services relevant to the target groups as well as NFDI-wide activities in the long term, while at the same time incorporating strategies and measures for innovation.
- h) Expand and deepen local, regional, national and international collaborations so as to increase networking within and outside the NFDI, achieve synergies and increase cross-consortia (re)use of data and services.

3 Consortium

Chapter 3 describes KonsortSWD's structure which supports making valuable contributions to RDM in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences, as well as to the broader NFDI. The consortium's composition and organisational setup are designed to leverage existing expertise while remaining flexible enough to address emerging needs. At the core of this approach is KonsortSWD's dedication to systematically expanding data access and thereby supporting RDM as realised through the RDCs (O1). As this chapter elaborates, training and education play a core role in the consortium (O2). By fostering close connections between established bodies like RatSWD and FDI Committee with the broader NFDI network, KonsortSWD aims to promote mutual learning and synergies across disciplines and infrastructures (O8). KonsortSWD will assure the reliability of its services by establishing sustainable business and operating models (O6). As Chapter 3.2 describes, we contribute actively to NFDI and are taking active steps to deepen cooperations that help researchers in our domains, through supporting relevant multidisciplinary use cases (O9). Crucially, through RatSWD, we will continue to influence the legal frameworks impacting RDM in Germany (O10).

The content of this chapter also directly addresses several key criteria outlined by the DFG Expert Committee. It demonstrates KonsortSWD's efforts to (a) further develop RDM for its target user groups (see sections 3.1 and 3.2), (b) increase utilisation beyond consortium boundaries (sections 3.2 and 3.3), (c) consolidate and expand existing structures (sections 3.1 and 3.4), (e) build RDM competences (section 3.1), and (h) expand international collaborations to increase networking inside (section 3.2) and outside (section 3.3) NFDI. By detailing the consortium's composition, community embedding, and organisational structure, this chapter illustrates KonsortSWD's readiness and relevance to drive RDM development as part of NFDI. KonsortSWD furthermore describes (g) its contribution to help NFDI services achieve sustainability through establishing business and operating models (section 3.5). The basis for this is (f) our organisational model which already has time-proven elements that will also support the NFDI process (section 3.4).

3.1 Composition of Consortium and Embedding in Community of Interest

3.1.1 Composition of Consortium

KonsortSWD was established in 2020. It builds on and continues many years of successful and influential work of RatSWD and its data infrastructure. As a consortium of ten co-applicant institutions with long-standing experience and complementary expertise in building and operating research data infrastructures, it represents the broad spectrum of disciplines studying society, the behaviour of individuals as members of society and reflecting the whole range of empirical research methods (cf. 2.1) (Blätte et al., 2022; Hollstein et al., 2021). Table 1 below lists the RDM-experience and RDM-qualifications of co-applicant institutions. From the start, participants, many of which operate RDCs, extend this expertise. Together, these partners continue to demonstrate that a treasure-trove of

unique - and mostly sensitive data - serving more than 51,000 registered users in 2023 (cf. [A5](#)) - is at the core of the RDM concerns in KonsortSWD. All RDCs involved in the Consortium are funded by research institutes (e.g. DZA or GESIS) or public institutions (e.g. Federal Statistical Office, Federal Employment Agency). 40 RDCs have decided to become part of the NFDI and support KonsortSWD's second proposal (see [A3](#)). KonsortSWD expects to add further RDCs, offering new data types and sources to researchers. Past trends might even accelerate given the endorsement of RDCs in the Federal Government's data strategy (Bundesregierung, 2023). As the services supporting RDCs scale easily and data provision and curation is funded through the RDC host institution we see no reason not to welcome such developments.

3.1.2 Changes to the Consortium and Reactions to Changing Needs

Compared to the beginning of the first funding phase KonsortSWD has successfully increased its reach beyond its established network by **adding 11 new partners**. Four new co-applicant institutions have been selected strategically to join KonsortSWD in the first funding period following a competitive open call for funding (FU Berlin, ifo, KIT, RWI). GWDG joined to bring technical know-how to operating our helpdesk (cf. [M3-5](#)) and will collaborate with KonsortSWD also relating to persistent identifiers (PID) (cf. [M2-3](#)). We were also very pleased to add the newly accredited RDC-RISC. In the second funding phase the following partners will be added to address evolving needs: host institutions of newly accredited RDCs or RDCs which had been unable to participate in the first proposal: Federal Motor Transport Authority, German Pension Insurance. Further new partners are: Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam (AIP) which is involved in developing our DMP solution, Stamp (cf. [M3-8](#)), German Institute for Adult Education - Leibniz Centre for Lifelong Learning (DIE), which will complement RDM expertise for educational data and has long been part of VerbundFDB (cf. [M3-9](#)), the Federal Archives, which will explore additional avenues (Hoffstätter & Weber, 2024) to ensure long-term access to research data (Naumann et al., 2023), UFZ - Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, with which processes will be tested to manage the plethora of social science data created alongside environmental data (such as acceptance surveys). In total, this proposal has six new participating institutions actively contributing their unique expertise to the infrastructure.

NFDI has also affected the **structures** KonsortSWD is built on: RatSWD has increased the number of elected members from eight to ten, with more academic associations participating in the elections. Being a part of the NFDI also intensified the cooperation with other disciplines as reflected, e.g., in the collaboration with the German Informatics Society (Gesellschaft für Informatik, GI), which has a substantial exposure to social science topics and has started to participate in RatSWD's working groups. FDI Committee, where the RDC infrastructure is self-governed, will openly invite data stakeholders like data protection agencies, repositories, and RDM experts to participate in the exchanges between the RDCs.

These dynamics show that KonsortSWD can both grow and explore new avenues, valuable to our communities and the RDM landscape. This is also thanks to the experience of our partners in the area of RDM, detailed in Table 1, which, for reasons of space, is limited to co-applicants.

Table 1: RDM experience and qualifications of current partners

Institution (alphabetical order)	RDM experience and qualifications
DIPF - Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education	DIPF hosts the German Network for Educational Research Data (VerbundFDB) together with GESIS and IQB and the RDC Education; research infrastructure provider (e.g., ShaReD – Sharing and Reusing Data)
DIW Berlin - German Institute for Economic Research	German Socio-economic Panel Study (SOEP at DIW Berlin) provides rich data to an international research community since 1984; innovative data and infrastructure development, hosts RDC SOEP; founding partner of the SHARE Berlin Institute (ERIC)
DZHW – German Center for Higher Education Research and Science Studies	RDC (fdz.DZHW) provides access to quantitative and qualitative research data; research on infrastructure development and research evaluation; active also in Base4NFDI.
Freie Universität Berlin	FU's Research Group 'Social Stratification and Survey Methodology' and the Disaster Research Unit aim to establish data infrastructures for crisis situations; strengthens links with NFDI4Earth for record linkage with social science data.
GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	GESIS is involved in over 10 national and international survey and RDM infrastructures; hosts a Core Trust Seal - certified long-term repository and data archive; a platform for data and code sharing; is partner in the specialised information services (FID) for political science (Pollux) and sociology (SocioHub); active also in BERD@NFDI, NFDI4DataScience, and Base4NFDI.
ifo – Center for Economic Studies	Ifo hosts the EDBC RDC and provides firm and company data for researchers
KIT – Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	KIT's Institute of Sports and Sports Science (IfSS), hosts the first MO RE Data repository for sports science data, is initiator of an ad hoc committee for RDM in German sports science and of a Leibniz Campus for Digital Transformation in Research (DiTraRe), strong links with NFDI4Health.
RWI – Leibniz Institute for Economic Research	RWI hosts RDC Ruhr with datasets from commercial providers. The RDC has extensive expertise in processing and referencing geo data.
LifBi - Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories	LifBi has extensive expertise in editing and disseminating complex data, RemoteNEPS offers remote access for sensitive data, hosts RDC NEPS.
University of Bremen - RDC Qualiservice	Qualiservice the RDC for sensitive qualitative data covers the entire range of qualitative data (e.g., textual, audio, video data; interview and observational data); Qualiservice is partner in the specialised information services (FID) for social and cultural anthropology (SIS SCA), sociology (SocioHub), political science (Pollux), and criminology.
University of Duisburg-Essen	UDE'S research group in computational social science (PoMine) brings experience with text-as-data methods, software architectures for empirical analysis of corpora and data linkage.
WZB - Berlin Social Science Center	WZB is a research hub; founding partner of the SHARE Berlin Institute (ERIC); administers RatSWD.

ZBW - Leibniz Information Centre for Economics	ZBW hosts the GO FAIR office for Germany; contributes to the development of EOSC software to connect research data repositories and to provide access to services, active also in BERD@NFDI, and NFDI4DataScience.
ZPID - Leibniz Institute for Psychology	ZPID operates an RDC curating and publishing data in the different fields of psychology. Operates a repository for psychological science (PsychArchives) with 20 different publication types, including research data, tests, pre-registrations, multimedia, and code. Active also in Base4NFDI.

3.1.3 Active Participation of Communities of Interest

KonsortSWD's communities of interest come from a wide range of disciplines and work with data relating to an impressive number of interdisciplinary research fields (cf. 2.1).

At the core of KonsortSWD's tight links with its communities is RatSWD. The basis of RatSWD's legitimacy and effectiveness are the **15 academic associations** in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences which contribute to the election of RatSWD members. All of them have explicitly expressed their support for KonsortSWD's activities in letters attached to this proposal. Support for KonsortSWD in the communities is furthermore evident in the Letters of Support for the second funding phase from an impressive additional **13 academic associations and relevant projects**. Ten members of RatSWD are elected for a three-year term in a general, anonymous election. In the 2023 elections, **2,661 researchers** cast their vote. While half of RatSWD's 20 members are elected, the other half represent data-producing institutions (like the Bundesbank and the Statistical Offices of the German Länder). In addition, the members' work is supported by a large network of volunteer experts working at foundations, interest groups or universities, e.g., with legal expertise or expertise in research ethics. As parts of the communities, these experts perform critical functions in ensuring KonsortSWD's responsiveness to changing community needs, quality assurance (e.g., the accreditation of RDCs), and continuous scanning of relevant trends in the environment of KonsortSWD. All members of RatSWD are appointed by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research.

Beyond these close links to the communities, we will ensure in that our work continues to align with the constantly changing demands of users. We employ a variety of institutionalised and ad-hoc formats targeting researchers, RDCs, and professional associations:

- KonsortSWD regularly organises various **events and conferences** that foster the dialogue between infrastructure and researchers (cf. M1-4). In addition to our core disciplines, recent events were also attended by researchers from neighbouring fields such as empirical cultural studies/European ethnology, contemporary history, and social ecology. Further avenues for community work go, e.g., through specialised information services (SISs, Fachinformationsdienste) (cf. M1-3). Our **Meet-the-Data** sessions in collaboration with VerbundFDB have repeatedly drawn highly motivated audiences.

- The **community involvement** also includes engaging with relevant academic associations, e.g. through attending conferences and hosting or attending dedicated panels (Fuß et al., 2022). We have also entered regular exchanges with the boards of professional associations in our domains. By presenting the consortium at different federal state RDM initiatives and other multipliers, we reach large parts of our community.
- The **consortium within the NFDI association** (Konsortium gemäß Satzung (NFDI e.V., 2020)) has proven to be a new path for community participation. It extends the reach of our existing channels as 14 universities with strong research profiles have joined the Consortium. To intensify ties at the level of institutions, we are currently working with the [Association of Social Science Institutes](#) (ASI e.V.) linking it more closely to RatSWD in particular.
- **Research Data Centres (RDCs)** actively engage researchers and students through feedback loops via user surveys and participation in conferences with dedicated panels. Networking initiatives, including QualidataNet and VerbundFDB, facilitate coordination among researchers and RDCs.

3.1.4 Training and Education

KonsortSWD focuses on complementing the landscape of RDM training and facilitating access to know-how that helps to build RDM competences. Users interested in Social Science RDM Training can draw on offers by [GESIS](#), but also through the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives ([CESSDA](#)). In total, RDCs offered 80 qualification measures like workshops, training, or seminars in 2023. We therefore focus on building skills for data stewards or curators through a **train the trainer** approach thereby strengthening existing offers for end-user training. This is captured in **RDM Compas** (cf. [M3-7](#)) which will provide curated RDM training materials for RDM professionals.

KonsortSWD actively contributed to the **RDM Competence Matrix** together with BERD@NFDI and in the context of section EduTrain (Behrens & Kvetnaya, 2023) where we are also active in working groups on a certificate course and on error cultures. We developed the social science module of the **RDM certificate course** at TH Cologne. There, core elements of KonsortSWD's training programme are integrated in a - highly relevant - curriculum for RDM professionals. Also, the module in the course constitutes a sustainable channel (financed through fees) to prepare future RDM professionals. With a particular focus on qualitative data, **QualidataNet** (cf. [M3-6](#)) offers customised RDM training materials, also to be linked with RDM Compas. With a focus on data dtewards we have pioneered a workshop format - [Agents of Change](#) - with accompanying materials that help this crucial group establish their role in their organisations. ASSURED (cf. [M3-1](#)) will - in collaboration with the NFDI consortia GHGA and BERD@NFDI - facilitate safe research by providing an e-learning programme covering topics such as data protection and statistical disclosure for researchers working with sensitive data and for data stewards.

3.1.5 Benefits Generated

The question of the benefits KonsortSWD has generated is closely linked to the impact we have described above both in quantitative, and in qualitative terms (cf. 2.1.2). We will therefore describe concrete benefits for researchers that a selection of our services bring:

Thanks to **Forum4MICA**, researchers can now access a comprehensive knowledge base on RDM topics and RDC-data questions. This platform is constantly updated with expert insights and user contributions, facilitating the exchange of information and solutions among researchers and data providers. The forum's low-threshold access and systematic search capabilities make it an invaluable resource for navigating complex datasets in the social sciences. **RDMCompas** serves as an informational and training platform that equips researchers and data curators with the discipline-specific competencies needed for RDM. It offers a data-type-specific information tailored to the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences and will add training materials by the end of 2024. **QualidataNet** significantly improves the visibility and accessibility of qualitative research data. As a network of RDCs, archives, and repositories, researchers now have a single point of entry for qualitative RDM, addressing the unique challenges posed in this still-emerging field. **OpenDataFormat** addresses the critical need for sustainable and interoperable data formats. Using it, researchers can now store their data in repositories that facilitates long-term accessibility and, therefore, re-use. With **RDCNet**, researchers can securely access sensitive, weakly anonymized microdata from a network of guest researcher workstations located at participating RDCs. This service enhances data accessibility, reducing travel costs to secure access points, while maintaining high security standards. Using **Stamp** (Standardized Data Management Plan for Educational Research), researchers are being guided through the many aspects RDM potentially involves when sensitive data are in play. This service provides structured templates, checklists, and guidelines that align with the FAIR principles. Researchers can thus ensure their data is well-organized, shareable, and reusable, enhancing the overall impact of their research. **Question Link** enhances researchers' ability to conduct comparative analyses across different surveys and link their data. With this service, researchers can for example, compare question wordings across different surveys, enabling the identification of similarities and differences, or access detailed metadata for each question. By providing these capabilities, Question Link ultimately helps save time and enhances the quality of research outcomes. With **Linking Textual Data**, researchers have access to R-tools which help link textual research data with other data types. This service promotes interdisciplinary research and enhancing the feasibility of novel research approaches using textual data.

A unique benefit is that RatSWD, funded through this project, continues to help **shape RDM policies**, such as the Research Data Act or other RDM-related policies (RatSWD, 2021, 2022b, 2022a, 2023a, 2023b, 2023b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024b, 2024d, 2024c).

Not the least, thanks to KonsortSWD's **coordination and maintained quality assurance** of the RDC network, researchers can continue to access the ever-growing data treasures RDCs provide. This infrastructure proves useful **far beyond the disciplinary limits of KonsortSWD**. While we

estimate KonsortSWD's target groups based on the number of employed researchers in our fields to be roughly 15,000, we count over 51,000 registered data users in 2023 (see [A5 - Data sheet](#) and [A4](#) for documentation of the Data Sheet).

3.2 Consortium Within NFDI and the National Academic Research System

3.2.1 Contribution to the NFDI as a Whole and Collaborations

KonsortSWD contributes to NFDI by sharing its unique expertise on sensitive data and beyond. Our communities likewise benefit from KonsortSWD's contributions to NFDI through linkable data from novel sources (e.g., satellites), capable technical services (e.g., PID provisioning) and expertise. KonsortSWD has actively participated in building "OneNFDI" (cf. [2.1.3](#)) from the start (Glöckner et al., 2019b). KonsortSWD contributes expertise and resources to the following cross-cutting topics:

- **legal and ethical aspects** in operating a research data **infrastructure** for **sensitive data**, based on more than 20 years of experience, and considered 'best practice' (Bundesregierung, 2021, 2023; RfII, 2016; Wissenschaftsrat, 2011) and tied to technical and management models for the sharing of sensitive or restricted research data.
- **metadata** with our engaged community metadata specialists, contributing internationally to RDA and DDI (cf. [4.2](#)).
- **tools and services** through experience from our diverse landscape, ranging from R libraries to institutional repositories at DIPF, GESIS, KIT (MO|RE data), ZPID, and ZBW.
- **cultural change**¹¹ and **Open Science** based on RatSWD's long standing commitment to these topics.
- **interoperability** thanks to the expertise in linking and harmonising data in a legally and ethically challenging environment, demonstrated by datasets such as [NEPS-ADIAB](#), [SOEP-CMI-ADIAB](#), [SOEP-RV](#). We also bring long-established expertise in **data standardisation** to the table.
- **training and competence building** through programmes in RDM and data-driven research methodology at most RDCs, which, thanks to [Stamp](#), is closely linked to systematic expertise in Data Management Planning (**DMP**).
- **data legislation**: KonsortSWD remains the only consortium with institutional support for sharing RDM expertise with **political and administrative actors**.
- **quality management and assurance** through KonsortSWD's extensive experience, in particular through the accreditation and monitoring processes for RDCs.
- **FAIR Assessment** thanks to best practices in evaluating the FAIRness maturity of research data infrastructures (together with BERD@NFDI and NFDI4DataScience).

¹¹ Cultural change in general refers to the transformation of collective behaviours, norms, values, and practices within a community or organization over time. In the context of data sharing in science we refer with this term to the dissemination of practices in research data management that align broadly with maxims in open science or, more formally, FAIR data principles.

- **sustainability and governance** through the experiences from establishing a network of currently 41 RDCs with the strong basis of 335 mostly institutionally funded FTE supporting RDM and active involvement in the NFDI task force on this topic.

Figure 3: Selected Contributions of Expertise and Resources to Cross Cutting Topics

As Figure 3 shows, and selected examples below illustrate, KonsortSWD strongly contributes its expertise and resources on the above-mentioned cross-cutting topics to collaborate with other consortia, share expertise in sections and task forces, and to help develop Basic Services in NFDI. It also shows that we cooperate very broadly and on many topics, providing a strong contribution to NFDI. To extract some examples: on Cultural Change we cooperate with many other consortia, amongst them NFDI-MatWerk; we contribute know-how on legal and ethical questions to a section, namely sec-ELSA; thanks to expertise in training, we are PI in RDMTraining4NFDI, a basic service. KonsortSWD sees no principled need to adjust collaboration on cross cutting topics as the activities described below have already started to return results. As we also describe below, we will strategically step up support for sections and basic services.

3.2.2 Collaboration with other Consortia and Multidisciplinary Use Cases

KonsortSWD has demonstrated significant achievements and strong commitment within the NFDI. As one of 26 consortia, KonsortSWD has taken a leadership role in cross-consortial collaborations, **co-leading 12 out of 144** initiatives like joint workshops, joint proposals or events (8%) and actively

participating in 31 (21%). Within the NFDI association, KonsortSWD has **co-led 13 out of 86** joint activities (like sections or task forces; equalling 15%), showcasing its prominent role. The consortium's dedication is further evident in the frequency of its collaborations, with almost 10% meeting at least quarterly, compared to the overall average of 7%. Moreover, KonsortSWD's collaborations tend to involve a median of 6 consortia, surpassing the overall median of 4, indicating its commitment to broader, multi-consortial efforts. These statistics underscore KonsortSWD's active involvement and leadership in fostering cooperation and advancing research data infrastructure across multiple disciplines within NFDI.¹²

We supported the conference on [social media archiving](#) with NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4Culture, Text+, BERD@NFDI, and NFDI4Memory. For a [FEa \(BMBF- Research Initiative for the Conservation of Biodiversity\)](#) use case (cf. [3.2.2](#)), we collaborated with NFDI4Biodiversity. The collaboration yielded integrated RDM support processes and a joint presentation on RDM services to the DFG plant sciences review board (with DataPlant, FAIRAgro, NFDI4Bioimage, NFDI4Microbiota). A joint project with NFDI4Health yielded suggestions for harmonised sociodemographic variables in epidemiology (Palm et al., 2023). On crises-related data (cf. [M3-4](#)), KonsortSWD works with NFDI4Earth. Looking ahead, we will host a workshop on LLMs in scientific publishing in spring 2025 (with NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Earth, NFDI-MatWerk), develop ASSURED (cf. [M3-1](#)) with BERD@NFDI and GHGA, and collaborate with NFDI4Energy. We have teamed up with NFDI4Culture to jointly develop business models (cf. [M5-1](#)). With NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Earth, NFDI-MatWerk, and PUNCH we took responsibility for a series to advance cultural change, entitled CC-BY-US (Rakers et al., 2023), which has attracted NFDI-wide attendance. In the area of policy papers, we share RatSWD's experience extensively with others in NFDI. Furthermore, together with BERD@NFDI, NFDI4Culture, and Text+ we organize and are regular contributors to another workshop series on Social Media data ([Social Media Show and Tell](#))

KonsortSWD aims to dedicate its resources efficiently to promoting RDM. A part of this is a systematic approach through multidisciplinary use cases (MDUC). As these use-cases are relevant across disciplines, they are likely to benefit a larger number of researchers. An MDUC is a real-world problem that necessitates the combined expertise, knowledge, and methodologies from two or more disciplines or methodological approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding, analysis, and solution (Ebert et al., 2023). KonsortSWD has already been engaged in MDUCs in the context of the FEa (Ebert et al., 2023), relating to crises-data with NFDI4Earth, and is part of an initiative by FairAgro on conflicts of interest in agricultural production. In the FEa example, ecology researchers needed to archive interviews with beekeepers, requiring the integration of RDM processes from NFDI4Biodiversity and KonsortSWD. To further pursue MDUC, we commit to 1) collaboratively

¹² Numbers based on a dataset, jointly collected, curated, published and regularly updated by all NFDI consortia (Eberl et al., 2024).

issuing open calls for multidisciplinary use cases with other consortia¹³, incorporating a joint selection process, if applicable, 2) assist researchers in finding other consortia that complement our expertise, and 3) use resources from our flex funds (cf. 3.4.5, M5-4). Decisions on flex funds for multidisciplinary use cases will be fast tracked.

3.2.3 Work in Sections

As shown in Figure 3, KonsortSWD is contributing to NFDI's Sections. We are **active in all five** and **very active in three** NFDI Sections. Until March 2024, KonsortSWD co-chaired the section (Meta)Data, Terminologies, Provenance (Metadata), continues to co-chair its working group Search & Harvesting and is active on the PID as well as the task force Metadata groups. We co-chair (with BERD@NFDI) the task force Data Protection in section Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA) (cf. M3-3) and strongly contribute to section Training & Education's (EduTrain) activities on certification (Blask et al., 2022) and error cultures (Herres-Pawlis et al., 2022). On the provision of data by firms (cf. M4-6) we contribute actively to the section Industry Engagement. Our helpdesk (cf. M3-5) contributes to the RDM Helpdesks working group, which is transitioning from a task force to a section working group within the section Commons Infrastructures (Infrastructure). In the second funding phase, we will strengthen the links between our services and the corresponding sections. In the profile boxes of the measures (cf. 5), relevant sections are identified. Decisions on section support will be made in the Executive Board (cf. 3.4). KonsortSWD thereby helps address the challenges faced by un(der)funded sections.

3.2.4 Basic Services

KonsortSWD values universal access to common services as essential for effective data sharing in science. We have played an active and early role in shaping the Base4NFDI initiative as part of the leading group on the position paper published in early 2022 (Konsortialversammlung, 2022) and as part of the core writing team for the joint proposal (Bernard et al., 2022). KonsortSWD partners are engaged on different levels in the Base4NFDI initiative: as Task Area leads and co-leads (GESIS), as hosts for Base4NFDI's service stewards (ZPID), and as partners in Base4NFDI development projects.

Technologically, KonsortSWD and its partners provide specific expertise to the following Basic Service developments: as principal investigators in Jupyter Notebooks (Jupyter4NFDI), and Knowledge Graphs (KGI4NFDI), and as use case partners concerning Persistent Identifiers (PID4NFDI). We regard basic services as a way to assure interoperability both with other consortia in NFDI as well as with EOSC.

It is during the Base4NFDI service Integration Phase that KonsortSWD will focus specific efforts to align with and integrate the service into our workflows. We are actively engaging with IAM4NFDI

¹³ We are aware that at least of 7 out of 9 consortia applying for a second funding phase commit to supporting MDUC in their proposals (DataPLANT, GHGA, KonsortSWD, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Health, NFDI4ING). Several second- and third-round consortia have also announced to participate.

during its Integration Phase through an [incubator pilot](#) for Forum4MICA (cf. [M3-4](#)) that could showcase the advantages of a simple login to RDM services. KonsortSWD is **committed to supporting service integration** process through its newly established Service Advocate (cf. below and [M5-2](#)). Furthermore, KonsortSWD will reserve flex funds to actively integrate basic services.

3.2.5 Governance Structure of NFDI

Members of KonsortSWD contribute to NFDI's governance structure through the NFDI Senate (Klaus Tochtermann and Christof Wolf are both members). Together with NFDI4Culture and Text+, we have successfully nominated a candidate for the Board of Trustees. Monika Jungbauer-Gans and Christof Wolf are spokespersons of the KonsortSWD chapter in the NFDI association.

3.2.6 Contribution to Knowledge Transfer Beyond NFDI

As shown in Figure 1 and Figure 3 as well as the above paragraphs, KonsortSWD contributes expertise to NFDI. Beyond NFDI, KonsortSWD has established cooperations with several federal state RDM initiatives (SaxFDM, FDM-SH, HeFDI, and bwFDM) (Chicherina et al., 2024), and Specialised Information Services (SIS), e.g. in social and cultural anthropology (SIS SCA), sociology (SocioHub), political science (Pollux), and criminology. KonsortSWD partners are actively engaged in setting up a SIS for Gender Studies, with work packages that connect to NFDI. We have also established connections with the Data Competence Centres (cf. [3.1.4](#)). Additionally, KonsortSWD partners are key drivers behind Leibniz Data, the RDM Forum of the Leibniz Association, and played a significant role in preparing a position paper on NFDI (Leibniz-Gemeinschaft, 2024). Furthermore, we contribute knowledge to and from our international networks, as detailed below.

3.3 International Networking

KonsortSWD aims to develop and strengthen research data infrastructure in social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. While research is globally oriented, sensitive data face challenges due to national legislation. Internationalisation supplements this focus, helping to find better solutions, particularly in areas like metadata standards (cf. [4.2](#)). KonsortSWD contributes to international RDM developments and **participates in key global research and infrastructure networks** through its partner institutions.

3.3.1 Forms of International Cooperation

KonsortSWD has established ties to **national infrastructure consortia** in the Netherlands (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations, [ODISSEI](#)), France ([PRODEGO](#)), Sweden (Comparative Research Center Sweden, [CORS](#)), and the [Luxemburg Data Service](#) (currently being set up). Beyond occasional exchanges, our aim is to establish formats for regular exchange with these initiatives. KonsortSWD's partners are well established in European Infrastructures: GESIS represents Germany in the [Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives](#) (CESSDA ERIC) and the [European Social Survey](#) (ESS ERIC). [RDC SHARE](#) – a participant

of KonsortSWD – is responsible for data documentation and dissemination for the whole SHARE ERIC (including all international users). The Leibniz Institute for the German Language (IDS) is one of 20 certified Service Providing Centres of the Common Language Resource and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN) ERIC.

In order to make headway in the fast-evolving field of AI, we will build on existing and strong contacts with the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) at the University of Michigan, to determine which and how their services (like the TurboCurator), currently built with substantial funding, can be re-used.

KonsortSWD will continue to be deeply involved in RDM development within DDI and RDA contexts. QualidataNet coordinates the DDI-CDI (Cross-Domain Integration) Qualitative Data Subgroup and collaborates internationally on developing a cross-disciplinary metadata specification for qualitative and non-numerical research data (Mozygamba & Betancort Cabrera, 2024). Additionally, the controlled vocabulary “QualiTerm” will be available via CESSDA. Brigitte Mathiak co-chairs RDA’s WG Data Granularity and IG Data Discovery Paradigms to enhance findability. Klaus Tochtermann keeps us closely aligned with developments in the EOSC Federation.

3.3.2 Implementation of Embedding in International Context and Services Established

Given its strong international embeddedness from the start, KonsortSWD has not formalised an explicit internationalisation strategy but has identified key areas for beneficial international cooperation. RDCs attract significant international users; in 2018, 64% of GESIS and 45% of Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) data users were from outside Germany. To cater to this, 75% of RDCs offer English contracts, data files, and documentation, an increase of 2 percentage points over the past five years (RatSWD, 2019, 2023e). Some RDCs, like IAB, provide safe rooms for data access abroad (e.g., in France, UK, USA, Canada). Additionally, 65% of RDCs use metadata compliant DDI (cf. 4.2). KonsortSWD has promoted the **CoreTrustSeal** (CTS) standard, crucial for repositories with confidential data (Hoffstätter & Beck, 2023). The FDI Committee has established cooperation with the International Secure Data Facility Professionals Network (ISDFPN) to learn from international best practices. Through RatSWD, the consortium has engaged in European Data legislation, an increasingly relevant activity (e.g., the European Commission's 2022 Open Data Initiative). Moreover, partners from KonsortSWD and other NFDI consortia have submitted a joint questionnaire to establish an **EOSC Node for social sciences and humanities** (SSH) - SSHOC-DE, maintained by German nodes of SSH ERICs (international infrastructure consortia): CLARIN, the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH), the open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities (OPERAS), and GESIS as CESSDA's national service provider, directly linking to NFDI consortia, including KonsortSWD.

3.4 Organisational Structure and Viability

3.4.1 Description of Structure and Governance

KonsortSWD's organisational structure has been implemented as intended in the first funding phase. It has six central elements:

Figure 4: KonsortSWD's organisational structure

Steering Committee (StC) is composed of the spokespersons from all the consortium's partner institutions and is responsible for all strategic and financial decisions.

Executive Board (EB) is composed of the spokesperson, the heads of the Task Areas, the chair of RatSWD, the Chair of FDI Committee, the Chair and Co-Chair of the "Consortium within the NFDI Association" (Konsortium gemäß Satzung)¹⁴. KonsortSWD's executive director and the director of the RatSWD office have guest status. The EB is responsible for all operative decisions and the preparation of strategic and financial decisions by the StC. It implements the work programme and continually adjusts it to developments in our communities and within the NFDI.

Task Areas (TAs) are thematic and organisational units that contribute to the consortium's mission. The consortium's work packages (Measures) are thematically clustered in five Task Areas. The PIs of all measures meet regularly in their TAs to exchange results, discuss potential synergies, plan next steps and assess emerging risks.

RatSWD (German Data Forum) membership consists of ten elected representatives from KonsortSWD's disciplines and ten appointed representatives of Germany's most important data producers. As such it represents KonsortSWD's communities. Among other things, it is responsible

¹⁴ The NFDI is designed to provide a comprehensive, cross-disciplinary platform for RDM Services. To facilitate the development of agreed-upon roadmaps, identify and define standards, and ultimately operate services, NFDI is structured as a legal entity under German law, an association. Within the association, each consortium is represented (Consortium as part of the NFDI association) and interested institutions can join as members. While the consortia's participation in the association currently has limited practical effects, KonsortSWD leverages this structure to expand its network. In a sustainably funded NFDI, decision-making will likely transition, at least partially, to the association level.

for quality control of the RDCs through its Monitoring Commission. RatSWD convenes three times a year and has a number of highly active working groups.

FDI Committee (Committee for Research Data Infrastructure) is the exchange forum for the RDC network. The RDC network currently consists of 41 entities accredited by RatSWD (German Data Forum). These RDCs provide access to quality-assured data from administrative, commercial, and scientific sources. Each RDC offers at least one path for scientists to access their data. Access must be indiscriminate, long-term, and provided under conditions that ensure data protection and research ethics. Quality assurance for accredited RDCs entails an annual monitoring, and an independent complaints process. Most RDCs are institutionally funded by their host institutions and are part of a broader network coordinated by the FDI Committee. The committee convenes biannually, bringing together representatives from all accredited RDCs to facilitate coordination, foster the exchange of experiences and knowledge, and drive strategic development.

Advisory Board (AB) advises the consortium on strategic matters, reviews and approves the work programme, and recommends future developments. The AB also participates in selecting future Measures, particularly regarding flex funds. It convenes at least once a year, sets its own agenda, and incorporates users' perspectives into KonsortSWD's developments. It comprises all impartial RatSWD members who are not part of the StC and do not receive funding. A majority of AB members belongs to those RatSWD members who are elected by researchers.

3.4.2 Adjustments of the Governance Structure for the Next Funding Phase

KonsortSWD's governance has proven effective and will continue, closely resembling the structures established in 2020. However, Task Areas will be adjusted to meet evolving needs (cf. Figure 5). We are now emphasising service governance and sustainability. These changes reflect DFG's emphasis on consolidation (NFDI Expert Committee, 2023), our commitment to optimising internal collaboration, and our analysis of existing weaknesses.

Figure 5: Illustration of Interconnected Task Areas

TA5 now emphasises sustainability (cf. 3.4.4). In the first proposal, TA2 and TA3 focused on Data Access and Data Production. However, within NFDI, a service-centric approach is more effective. Thus, we have grouped services enhancing FAIRness in TA2, training and competence formation in TA3, and data-integration activities in TA4. This shift clarifies our focus areas, with each TA having a clear mission and reflecting our investment areas for the second funding period. A structural weakness was the limited interaction between the old TAs Technical Solutions, Data Access, and Data Production. The new structure groups services by commonalities, regardless of their technical nature. To improve communication between technical and content-centric activities, we will introduce a Service Advocate (cf. 3.2.4) in the Coordination Office (CoO), part of TA5. This role, inspired by Base4NFDI, will integrate Basic Services and enhance internal communication on service-related issues. Coordination will also adapt in the next funding phase. Drawing on successful examples from NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Objects, and Base4NFDI, the CoO (cf. M5-2) will bundle TA coordinators to provide flexible support, foster external stakeholder relations, and coordinate within NFDI.

3.4.3 Demand

KonsortSWD is rooted in a network of partners which have been running successful data services for a long time. Therefore, we adopted a strict demand-driven approach. Determining community demand (cf. 3.1.3) and its measurement (cf. 4.4.3) have been successfully practised in our first funding period as the uptake of our services illustrates.

We ensure **demand-oriented development** through several steps. One, by engaging with our communities at conferences and through RatSWD, KonsortSWD identifies the needs of data users and providers. We have conducted numerous workshops, a large open call for [Network Development](#) in 2023, and a call for ideas for this proposal. Increasingly, we also involve member institutions of the “Consortium within the NFDI Association”¹⁵ to directly reach research-active universities. Two, our [Advisory Board](#) helps prioritise community needs and desires (cf. 3.4). Three, once a service is part of KonsortSWD’s portfolio, it is rigorously evaluated against project plans and community demands. This includes qualitative and quantitative success tracking through monthly status reports (cf. 4.4.3). This step will be crucial in the second funding phase as development concludes and usage becomes measurable. Four, further prioritisation will help consolidate towards an NFDI-ready service portfolio. The Advisory Board and the wider community, including the consortium in the association, will play key roles in this process.

¹⁵ The NFDI is designed to provide a comprehensive, cross-disciplinary platform for RDM Services. To facilitate the development of agreed-upon roadmaps, identify and define standards, and ultimately operate services, NFDI is structured as a legal entity under German law, an association. Within the association, each consortium is represented (Consortium as part of the NFDI association) and interested institutions can join as members. While the consortia’s participation in the association currently has limited practical effects, KonsortSWD leverages this structure to expand its network. In a sustainably funded NFDI, decision-making will likely transition, at least partially, to the association level.

Figure 6: Assuring demand-oriented development

As NFDI develops, our method for translating demand into services will need adjustments. This will impact two areas: first, cross-consortial demand, meaning services relevant beyond our disciplines, must be prioritized. We will incorporate multidisciplinary use cases (cf. 3.2.2), an approach pioneered with NFDI4Biodiversity and NFDI4Earth at the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI) 2023 (Ebert et al., 2023). Second, as demand for RDM services is likely to grow faster than KonsortSWD can address, more selection will be necessary. This is particularly important as many of our services are Support/Consulting services, which have limited scalability (cf. 4.4.2). We anticipate such adjustments in particular when the permanent shape of NFDI becomes clear after its evaluation in 2026 (cf. 3.4.6).

3.4.4 Consolidation of Portfolio

KonsortSWD's strategy is process-based and aligns with central objectives to ensure services are usable and integrated into standard research processes. The process involves identifying suitable services through Advisory Board evaluations and performance KPIs (cf. 3.4.3). Based on these evaluations, the Executive Board makes recommendations, considering interrelations with other consortia or basic services. Business models (cf. M5-1) factor prominently in Steering Committee decisions. This results in a demand-driven portfolio best suited to serve KonsortSWD's communities.

Sustainability has been a key focus from the start. All services are designed to support research or improve the work of RDCs. The established and sustainably funded infrastructure of existing RDCs provides a solid foundation for continuing KonsortSWD's services and software once their technical readiness and usefulness are proven. Partners are committed to maintaining the technical operation of selected services. Beyond that, all services will have developed business and operating models by October 2027. The proposed timeline aligns with the anticipated Joint Science Conference (GWK) decision on permanent NFDI funding in fall 2026, allowing for strategic adjustments based on the outcome.

Basic services (cf. 3.2.4) can help the sustainability and consolidation of KonsortSWD's portfolio. These services focus on core functionalities relevant to many RDM users, thereby providing a broader base for support in terms of funding and development capacities. KonsortSWD will increase efforts to incorporate basic services into its portfolio, dedicating some flex funds for this purpose. Integrating basic services into the infrastructure landscape remains challenging, especially for

smaller RDCs with limited IT influence. Larger scientific institutes in KonsortSWD will be approached to identify ways basic services can consolidate the portfolio (cf. 3.2.4).

3.4.5 Allocation and Spending of Funds and Flex Funds

Spending of funds deviated from the first proposal particularly due to substantial budget cuts which reduced the extent of KonsortSWD’s deliverables. With regard to activities contained in our revised proposal, spending was according to plan (Adena et al., 2020). For unspent funds, primarily due to delays in hiring, filling vacancies, and the pandemic, we have initiated short-term projects to respond flexibly to community needs. These projects support activities such as service implementation at partner institutions, training programs, and collaborations with other consortia. This approach has redirected more funding to participants not funded in the proposal (see 2023 progress report to DFG).

In the second funding phase, KonsortSWD will implement an annual flexible funding process for innovative projects and multidisciplinary use cases. This allows thorough evaluation and preparation time for partners, including those outside the consortium. Funds are distributed across annual rounds (cf. M5-4), can be supplemented with funds rolled over from the previous year and will have a small reserve for ad-hoc projects. This structure supports multiple smaller projects rather than a few large ones. Multidisciplinary use cases (cf. 3.2.2) will be a key component in each call. Projects are typically funded for one year, with an extension possible in the first two calls to fund larger initiatives.

The process is planned as follows (see Figure 7): *September/October*: The Executive Board determines the thematic focus for the upcoming call, consulting with the Advisory Board. For multidisciplinary use cases and basic NFDI services, coordination with other consortia takes place. *December/January*: public announcement of the call for proposals. *April/May*: proposal review by the Advisory Board. For multidisciplinary use cases, other consortia may also be involved in the evaluation process. *June/July*: funding decisions are made, contractual foundations are established, and recipients are notified. *January (following year)*: commencement of the funding period. This structured approach ensures a transparent and efficient allocation of flexible funds, promoting innovation and collaboration within KonsortSWD and the broader community.

Figure 7: Timeline for yearly allocation of Flex funds

3.4.6 Financial Setup 2029-30

The current financial framework for NFDI ends in 2028. Given that NFDI aims to establish a reliable infrastructure for RDM, KonsortSWD very much appreciates the opportunity to apply for additional support in 2029 and 2030. Our financial and substantial plans for this time are shaped by the expectation that, by the end of 2028, the context for NFDI will differ substantially from today: the Federal Government will, on the one hand, have committed itself to how NFDI is to become a national node in EOSC (EGI Federation, 2024). The German Council of Science and Humanities' [recommendation](#) on the future of NFDI on the other hand, will have been translated into funding decisions by the Länder and Federal governments. At this point, the focus of a permanent NFDI (technical services for domains, user support, overarching basic services, community work) is unknown

KonsortSWD wants to be in the best possible position to provide RDM services to our communities under these unknown conditions after 2028. We have therefore not drawn up a detailed work program beyond 2028. Instead, we will transition all services that have been developed by the end of 2028 into operating mode. That is, given they satisfy user demand (cf. [3.4.3](#)), we request further funding for providing a service. Financially, we calculate the operation of services to cost about 30% of development effort. For our operational model (Coordination structures, RatSWD, FDI Committee) to be able to continue to work, we request funding at the current level. KonsortSWD will use freed up funds to increase its flex funds. They will be used to transition structures and services into the "new" NFDI that will by then have been defined. Beyond that, we will further include new communities and integrate or develop services based on the RDM demands of researchers in our fields.

3.5 Operating model

3.5.1 Experience with Financial and Operating model

KonsortSWD's business and operating model builds on a solid foundation of institutionally funded RDCs, which provide essential data services far beyond what NFDI funding alone could support. With **335 full-time equivalent** staff in 2023 (RatSWD, 2024f), this RDC network forms a robust basis for sustainable operations. We have complemented these own contributions by KonsortSWD's partners (for details see [ch. 8](#)) with project funds to finance overarching community participation (RatSWD, TA1), coordination, standard-development across RDCs and maintenance of the network (mainly, FDI Committee) and services. This structure of the finance model has worked well. With the current level of NFDI funding, this support is adequate.

Given that some RDCs, e.g., at the statistical offices but also at GESIS date back more than 20 years and their user base keeps increasing (cf. [2.1.2](#)) there is strong evidence that this operating model works for both, researchers and data providers. With their community focus and sustainable finances, we think that RDCs can serve as a blueprint for other domains, particularly those with sensitive, restricted data. By a similar reasoning, the expansion of the RDC system is also highlighted in the Federal Government's Data Strategy (Bundesregierung, 2023). This is a very strong backing

of the operational model behind KonsortSWD's infrastructure. However, heading towards a permanent NFDI integrating and establishing federated services and ecosystems, a convincing long-term operating model requires the transition of current KonsortSWD funding into more stable contexts.

Regarding new services, currently being developed or rolled out by KonsortSWD to support researchers and RDCs, it is premature to present a fully defined operating model in this proposal. These services are demand-driven, and their usage patterns are yet to be determined, while others are still in development. Recognizing this, KonsortSWD commits to preparing business and operating models for its services by 2028. We outline this approach in detail in chapter [4.4.4](#).

KonsortSWD partners have traditionally adhered to the Open Science ideal, thus charging fees only to cover extensive efforts associated with data preparation, documentation, curation, and distribution. Fees are occasionally levied on data users or providers, particularly when non-standard data products are needed. The underlying cost structures for these services vary significantly depending on the type of effort necessary for curation, leading to a diverse application of user fees within the consortium. This approach ensures that the primary focus remains on facilitating access to data for scientific research while maintaining a balance between cost recovery and affordability for researchers.

In the next funding phase, we will explore the feasibility of incorporating costing models more systematically. This investigation would include potential contributions from universities and research organisations, other grants, and paid use by other research infrastructures and industry. Such an approach would diversify funding sources and enhance the sustainability of KonsortSWD's services. At the same time, money raised through such models would still mainly come from public funding (through projects or data users' institutions) and will most likely not be able to fully replace current funding of KonsortSWD activities.

To address these challenges, KonsortSWD will individually analyse each of its services to assess the potential for incorporating fees into a sustainable business model. In the context of this proposal, a business model refers to a detailed concept outlining the financial, operational, and organizational specifics for delivering a RDM service. The term aligns with DFG's funding criteria, which emphasise sustainability and does not necessarily imply user-based pricing models. These models will be developed by 2027 and supported by TA5 in collaboration with NFDI4Culture, whose community is very similar in structure to KonsortSWD's. This structured approach, which will also draw on international experience (OECD and Science Europe, 2020), will ensure that the implementation of user fees is both feasible and aligned with the consortium's overarching goals of supporting scientific research and data accessibility. Along those lines, the FDI Committee has established a working group in 2023 to methodically compile prevailing costing models and explore related challenges and potential recommendations.

It is important to point out that fees for individual researchers, in particular, should be balanced and appropriate. The advisory board for the RDC of the statistical offices at the federal and state levels (Wissenschaftlicher Beraterkreis, 2024) has recently highlighted the risk of substantial fee increases in those RDCs. This has drawn heavy criticism from our communities. To draw public attention to the problem, RatSWD issued a critical statement (RatSWD, 2024e) which was broadly linked and also echoed in the mainstream media (e.g. Table.Media, 2024). Fees for data access are widely seen as an inhibitor of research as they would, at the very least, introduce a level of discrimination (who can pay and who can't). While this debate is not directly transferrable to RDM services, it shows that, in order to maintain legitimacy of NFDI as a user-driven and research-friendly effort, user fees are unlikely to be a probate means to cover service costs in all but very few cases. Therefore, KonsortSWD has begun to discuss different elements of sustainable finance models (cf. 4.4.4).

4 Research Data Management Strategy

While KonsortSWD and NFDI have made progress and shown substantial impact, RDM has yet to become an integral part of most researchers' routines. Thus, a strategic approach is necessary to embed RDM practices more deeply within the research workflows in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. Chapter 4 outlines this strategy, focusing on key elements such as the implementation of metadata standards, adherence to FAIR principles, the provision of comprehensive services, and the anticipation of external changes and constraints. These elements are designed to make RDM more common and seamlessly integrated into researchers' daily activities.

The initiatives described in Chapter 4 support several central objectives of KonsortSWD. For example, standardising RDM processes (O3) is crucial for enhancing the usability of the infrastructure, and this is closely tied to KonsortSWD's efforts to work with metadata and improve FAIR principles. The expansion of RDM competences through training and support services (O2) is essential for helping researchers understand the value of using metadata, thus fostering a robust RDM culture. Additionally, the chapter highlights the importance of international networking (O7), which benefits developing useful approaches to metadata and FAIR. Finally, the entrenchment of services (O5) in addition to training will help solidify the effects of the RDM strategy, particularly for early career researchers as a key target group for RDM (O4), ensuring long-term adoption and sustainability. We also address the need to influence RDM-related legislation to help shape conditions for a research-friendly environment (O10).

Chapter 4 additionally takes up several key objectives outlined by the DFG Expert Committees. Key objective (d) is met through the stabilisation and promotion of a quality-assured service portfolio. KonsortSWD's strategy for this involves categorising services based on their development stage, establishing service-specific business models by 2027, and developing consortium-wide consolidated business models by early 2028. This approach allows flexibility to adapt to the future

NFDI landscape while working towards long-term sustainability. Key objective (e) is at the core of the efforts described to improve professionalism while key objective (g) is addressed through this staged development of sustainable operating and funding models for RDM services, ensuring their viability and adaptability.

4.1 Scientific Relevance and Quality of the Measures

4.1.1 Success of Implementation of Measures and Task Areas and Reorganisation

Overall, the implementation of the work program set forth in our initial proposal has been successful. KonsortSWD has **initiated new dynamics** in an infrastructure that is among the most established in the NFDI. Across all measures, 93% have met or are set to meet their targets. Key successes include the establishment of Forum4MICA, QualidataNet, RDCNet, and the integration of the Standardized Data Management Plan (Stamp) into RDMO. Overall, the first funding phase has helped to tie important elements of our infrastructure closer together, integrating the diverse landscape and strengthening its RDM capacities (cf. 2.1.2).

In the first funding phase, we set out five Task Areas: Community Participation, Data Access, Data Production, Technical Solutions, and the Secretariat. TAs Data Access and Data Production were modelled along the research data life cycle, whereas TA Technical Solutions and Community Participation have a functional focus and are cross-cutting by design¹⁶. For this proposal we have substantially altered the structure of our Task Areas and coordination structure between them and NFDI (cf. 3.4). This reflects the shift in focus to consolidation as emphasised strongly by DFG (NFDI Expert Committee, 2023) and our own determination to optimise collaboration within KonsortSWD. These organisational changes do reflect adaptations to NFDI as do – with equal importance – our commitments to contribute to NFDI sections in all measures where suitable activities exist, and fund MDUC and Basic Services (cf. 3.2.2, 3.2.4). A further refinement that will affect our work across services is the combination of community input and KPI-oriented development (cf. Figure 6). This will lead to a more service-centric approach. We combine this with the establishment of a Coordination Office which, among other things, will strengthen the interaction between technical and more content-oriented services. These organisational changes reflect KonsortSWD's focus on consolidating its service portfolio while remaining responsive to emerging needs in the research community, in line with aim B.

4.1.2 Improving RDM Professionalism in the Target Communities

Many implemented and future planned measures of KonsortSWD address the professionalism of RDM in our research communities directly. They foster the provision of data (e.g. RDCnet, M2-4) and the standardisation of access procedures (cf. M4-2) to sensitive research data. The Stamp will help turn Data Management Plans from necessary paperwork into a useful tool for structuring a data-

¹⁶ We substantially adjusted our work plan given the 27% cut in funding. Most notably we did not proceed with TA4, a research data ethics forum. Yet, RatSWD continued work on the topic and KonsortSWD's partners have applied for additional funds.

driven research process and speed up related processes once data are processed (cf. [M3-8](#)). Early career researchers in particular, benefit from an easy-to-use information and exchange platform, Forum4MICA (cf. [M3-4](#)), offering tips and tricks which help establish professional best practice. More broadly, our training activities (cf. [3.1.4](#)) are designed to support RDM professionals. Expansion of RDM competences through training and support services, with a particular focus on sensitive data, will help make RDM a routine part of the research process in KonsortSWD's communities.

4.1.3 Further Advancing Research Data Management

The RDC-system supported by KonsortSWD is the ideal platform to ensure correspondence of RDM with community needs. A central challenge for the second funding phase will be **scaling our effects** (cf. [4.4.2](#)): Forum4MICA will expand its offerings and link to the basic service [IAM4NFDI](#), to allow simplified logins across institutions. Furthermore, we are launching a joint, cross-consortial effort to train the specific competences needed to work with highly sensitive data (cf. [M3-1](#)), thereby further scaling capacities. We also intensify our cooperation with [forschungsdaten.info](#), the most reputable source for RDM information in Germany, to better disseminate our content. A different type of scaling would come from a broader uptake of RDM in large project contexts (e.g., collaborative research centres (SFB)). In collaboration with [NFDI4Culture](#), KonsortSWD will attempt to emulate the successes of consortia in the natural sciences where many newly established projects co-organize their RDM efforts with the NFDI. Integrating RDM support for sensitive data into major project contexts and placing references to KonsortSWD in funding organization calls ([M1-3](#)) will be a major step towards making it a standard operating procedure in the social sciences (aim A).

4.1.4 Criteria for the Relevance of KonsortSWD's Contribution

To measure the relevance and quality of our RDM strategy, we will primarily rely on **key performance indicators (KPIs)** that track the usage of the services and data we provide. All services (cf. [5](#)) propose KPIs that most meaningfully capture their intended contribution to RDM. While KPIs give us valuable insights into how researchers use our services, we are acutely aware of their limits: any KPI will only capture part of the effect KonsortSWD has on advancing research. Operating time of a service and even newly registered users will only very indirectly help spark an idea that truly advances science. Therefore, in line with recommendations by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, 2022), we will **not make strategic decisions based on KPIs alone**. Rather, we will combine them with qualitative evaluations by our Advisory Board and by feedback from our community more generally. Wherever possible, we aim at assessing the impact of our RDM strategy based on data and service citations. Citations provide a clear indication that our data and services are being actively used and referenced in research, demonstrating their value and relevance to the scientific community (RatSWD, 2024f). We will also track the name recognition of KonsortSWD and our key services as a proxy for the relevance of our research data strategy. Finally, we will measure the success of our

RDM strategy through our interactions with researchers at events like conferences and especially through the volume and nature of inquiries received by our helpdesk (cf. [M3-5](#)).

4.2 Metadata Standards

4.2.1 National and International Standards

KonsortSWD's participating RDCs have **embraced international metadata standards** since the early 2000s, primarily utilising the [Data Documentation Initiative](#) (DDI) standard. DDI covers all research data lifecycle stages in our fields, aiming to comprehensively describe datasets from surveys and observational methods. By providing detailed metadata at various levels, including datasets and variables, DDI enhances metadata consistency and reliability, promoting data sharing, findability, and reuse. KonsortSWD's commitment to DDI is evident from our six presentations at international European Data Documentation Initiative (EDDI) conferences in recent years (Xiaoyao & Saalbach, 2022; Bach et al., 2022; Klas & Hopt, 2022; Betancort & Mozygamba, 2022; Bach & Klas, 2023; Betancort & Mozygamba, 2023).

In addition to DDI, generic metadata standards like DataCite and schema.org are used for cross-disciplinary interoperability. Most KonsortSWD RDCs are registered with DataCite, making our dataset-level metadata available as DataCite metadata. By integrating schema.org into dataset landing pages, KonsortSWD provides structured metadata that help search engines and harvesters identify KonsortSWD datasets, enhancing their findability (Limani, Younes, et al., 2022b). These standards are crucial for improving metadata findability and interoperability, aiding integration with other NFDI consortia or EOSC. This aligns with recommendations of NFDI section Metadata's task force, to use standards like schema.org and DataCite in addition to domain-specific standards such as DDI.

Among KonsortSWD's services, DDI is used for the Open Data Format (cf. [M2-6](#)), the PID Service (cf. [M2-3](#)) and the core metadata set of QualidataNet (cf. [M2-8](#)). DataCite's metadata schema is used by the PID Service and QualidataNet's harvesting tool. Additionally, KonsortSWD metadata will be mapped to the [EOSC EU Node](#) metadata schema to include it in the EOSC EU Node search index (cf. [M2-1](#)).

4.2.2 Contributions to Metadata Standards and other Standards Relevant to RDM

Internationally, KonsortSWD actively contributes to the DDI standard. GESIS, SOEP@DIW, IZA, Qualiservice, and IAB are full or associate members of the DDI alliance, with GESIS and Qualiservice closely involved in its development. For qualitative data, we are creating the QualidataNet metadata core set, compliant with DDI and DataCite, to improve the findability and reuse of metadata from diverse data providers. QualidataNet also develops the controlled vocabulary "QualiTerm" in collaboration with researchers and infrastructures to better describe qualitative research data. The vocabulary will be integrated into the QualidataNet search portal and published (planned via CESSDA) to be reused by the partners.

Beyond metadata standards, KonsortSWD promotes non-proprietary data formats like .csv and .txt, by formulating recommendations in the Open Data Format (Han et al., 2022) (cf. M2-6). The 'harmonised variables' measure established standards for sociodemographic variables (Schneider et al., 2023), based on the "Demographic Standards" (Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik et al., 2024) (cf. M4-9).

4.2.3 Strategy for Increasing the Interoperability and (Re)Use of Data and Metadata

Enabling and promoting linking and reuse of our (meta)data across disciplines is a key concern. Metadata and other standards foster interoperability and reusability of our (meta)data and code, crucial for KonsortSWD's follow-up. Focusing on cross-domain data integration, DDI-CDI (Data Documentation Initiative Cross Domain Integration) will be addressed by Open Data Format and QualidataNet measures (cf. M2-6, M2-8, M3-6). Efforts to standardise sociodemographic and crisis-related survey instruments continue in StanDem (cf. M4-9) and on crises data (cf. M4-3). PIDs for elements within datasets have been introduced to enhance data linking on a more fine-grained level (cf. M2-3). Linking heterogeneous datasets is addressed by StanDem. Furthermore, linking services are proposed by highly reputable RDCs with invaluable experience in handling administrative data (cf. M4-1; M4-7) as well as Linking Textual Data (cf. M2-7). This enables researchers to combine and analyse data from multiple sources and types, facilitating new research questions.

KonsortSWD is very actively involved in the NFDI section Metadata (cf. 3.2.3). The following measures will participate in the section: QualidataNet (M2-8; M3-6; M4-8) will enhance qualitative data visibility and FAIRness through a common platform and "QualiTerm" vocabulary, helping researchers find suitable data for their studies. Findability of Services and Data (cf. M2-2) supports the use of interdisciplinary metadata standards for KonsortSWD data, to promote re-use through findability (cf. 4.3).

4.2.4 Contribution to Building a Common Architecture for NFDI

KonsortSWD is actively participating in the current NFDI task forces on governance and architecture and in all NFDI sections (cf. 3.2.3) as well as in several basic services, including [Jupyter4NFDI](#) and [KGI4NFDI](#) as investigators and in [PID4NFDI](#) as a use case partner. Likewise, KonsortSWD is very active in Base4NFDI, providing two of the twelve co-spokespersons. Via these and other activities (cf. 3.2) KonsortSWD is an active partner in discussing, designing and implementing NFDI's organisational as well as technical architecture.

4.3 Implementation of the FAIR Principles and Data Quality Assurance

4.3.1 Assessment of FAIR Implementation given the Needs of the Relevant Community

All four FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) are crucial for our communities (Betancort Cabrera et al., 2020):

Findability. The main challenge for data findability in Germany's social sciences is decentralisation and heterogeneity (Limani et al., 2023). KonsortSWD offers central services and consulting to

improve data findability and visibility. In the first funding phase, KonsortSWD focused on search engine optimization (SEO) and using standardised web vocabularies, with recommendations which have already been adopted at central repositories, such as at DIPF, DZHW, and GESIS (Limani, Younes, et al., 2022a). KonsortSWD also tackled FAIR assessment, finding that automatic metadata improvement can overcome many findability obstacles (Saldanha Bach, Klas, Mathiak, et al., 2023; Saldanha Bach, Limani, et al., 2023). To further enhance findability, KonsortSWD applied [FAIR Signposting](#) to create machine-actionable links for downloadable resources (Wilkinson, 2023). In the next funding phase, KonsortSWD will apply the findability methodology from the first phase to KonsortSWD services (cf. [M2-2](#)) and map metadata schemas to the EOSC EU node (cf. [M2-1](#)). This integration into EOSC will increase KonsortSWD's data visibility in Europe, complementing the near-complete listing of RDCs in [Re3data](#), a global registry of research data repositories. Assigning PIDs to data elements below the study level (cf. [M2-3](#)) supports findability by directing users to landing pages with citable information. Optimising qualitative data findability is a goal of QualidataNet (cf. [M4-8](#)), which supports researchers by harvesting data holdings for a search portal.

Accessibility. Due to the sensitive nature of our microdata and the need to protect personal rights as well as confidentiality, Open Data is not feasible for all KonsortSWD data. Research often involves sensitive information and vulnerable groups, necessitating managed data access in compliance with legal requirements like EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). KonsortSWD also aligns with the Five Safes framework, which addresses safe projects, people, data, settings, and outputs (Green & Ritchie, 2023). Operationally, KonsortSWD focuses on improving contractual frameworks for data access and establishing RDCnet, a multilateral network of secure data access points, to enhance accessibility (cf. [M2-4](#)). KonsortSWD has published and will maintain contract templates for data use and transfer agreements (Schallaböck, Kreutzer, et al., 2023a). RDCnet has started and will continue to connect workstations at partner RDCs, allowing access from any participating RDC and reducing travel requirements, thereby improving data access. KonsortSWD also offered RDM grants to smaller projects to make their data FAIR (Aßmann & Schlücker, 2023). In the next phase, RDCnet will expand to include non-RDC institutions, like universities, as additional data access points (initial collaborations are built on partnerships that SOEP@DIW already has, while further are planned with Bielefeld University and the University of Konstanz). Other data access measures include CrisesData (cf. [M4-3](#)), FirmData (cf. [M4-6](#)) and Sports Science data (cf. [M4-5](#)). The systematic efforts to enhance the accessibility of sensitive data are crucial for consolidating KonsortSWD's unique service profile centred around sensitive data, as called for by aim B.

Interoperability. In the first funding phase, KonsortSWD addressed interoperability with the Open Data Format, ensuring compatibility with software broadly used in our domain, such as Stata, SPSS and R. For quantitative data, controlled vocabularies like the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) are common, while QualidataNet developed the "QualiTerm" vocabulary, and will work on an extension of the DDI-CDI model for qualitative data (Betancort Cabrera & Mozygamba, 2023) (cf. [M2-8](#)). The [QuestionLink Service](#) allows users to harmonise variables for

latent constructs from different survey programs. In the next funding phase, KonsortSWD aims at enabling the linkage of (confidential) datasets between RDCs and other data owners (cf. [M4-1](#); [M4-7](#)), implementing the DDI-CDI standard to the Open Data Format (cf. [M2-6](#)), and expanding the implementation of sociodemographic standard items and variables (Schneider et al., 2023) to a larger number of surveys and RDCs (cf. [M4-5](#)).

Reusability. The first funding phase has been addressing reusability through the measures Stamp, Forum4MICA, and QualidataNet, which will all be continued in the second phase. Stamp (cf. [M3-8](#)) is an easy solution to systematically guide users on how to document and archive data in a data repository by which reusability is ensured. Forum4MICA (cf. [M3-4](#)) fosters reusability by generating a steadily growing knowledge base for data users together with a discussion platform for sharing expertise on data resources and data handling. QualidataNet - RDM and re-use of qualitative data (cf. [M3-6](#)) provides a portal for finding and sharing qualitative research data. Furthermore, in the first funding phase, the measure [RDM grants](#) supported smaller projects in making their data FAIR and thus also reusable. In the next funding phase, QualidataNet will systematise best practices for qualitative data reuse and develop tools for anonymisation and pseudonymisation of textual data. Stamp will be generalised to better meet the needs of different social science disciplines and further integrated in online applications (e.g., DataWiz 2).

KonsortSWD is also associated with major initiatives related to FAIR, such as the [FDO Forum](#), [GO FAIR 2.0](#), the [EOSC Task Force FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects](#), which ensures that the latest developments in the field and community needs are always taken into account. KonsortSWD uses RDA's FAIR Data Maturity Model (RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, 2020), to continuously (re-)assess the "FAIRness" of its metadata.

4.3.2 Quality Criteria in KonsortSWD and Assessment of Data Quality

RatSWD has **established criteria** for accrediting Research Data Centres (RDCs) to ensure high standards (Buck et al., 2022). These criteria include providing transparent and standardised access to data, offering comprehensive user support, ensuring proper data preparation and anonymization, maintaining detailed documentation, and complying with legal and ethical standards for data protection. Additionally, RDCs are encouraged to engage in their own research activities to stay up to date with methodological advancements. These **accreditation criteria directly impact the quality of data** within RDCs. By mandating transparent access procedures and comprehensive user support, RatSWD ensures that data are readily available and usable for researchers, promoting extensive use and validation. Detailed documentation and proper data preparation guarantee that the data are reliable and can be effectively used for scientific analysis, helping researchers understand the context, methodology, and limitations of the data, which is crucial for producing valid and reproducible results. Furthermore, compliance with data protection regulations ensures that data are handled ethically, protecting the privacy and rights of individuals and maintaining public trust (Strobel et al., 2022). Encouraging RDCs to participate in research activities helps them stay at the

forefront of methodological advancements and data management practices, continuously improving the services and quality of data they provide. In summary, RatSWD's criteria balance accessibility, quality, and legal compliance, supporting the scientific community in conducting rigorous and impactful research.

RatSWD regularly monitors RDCs to ensure compliance with these accreditation criteria, including legal checks and data handling (RatSWD, 2017). Moreover, KonsortSWD has fostered quality assurance, in terms of promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures, by assisting KonsortSWD partners in acquiring the [CoreTrustSeal](#) (CTS), a certification that ensures data repositories meet essential standards for data preservation and accessibility. QualidataNet enhances qualitative data management and re-use potential, promoting cultural change towards qualitative data sharing.

Finally, KonsortSWD supports and collaborates with the Competence Center Data Quality in the Social Sciences ([KODAQS](#)) funded by the Federal Ministry for Education and Research, which fosters quality-assured use of social science data through learning, research, and networking. KonsortSWD will incorporate KODAQS results into its quality assurance practices, such as in RDM Compas (cf. [M3-7](#)).

4.3.3 Procedures and Regulations for Access to and Use of Data

The RDC system is a nationally and internationally recognized and well-established framework for accessing sensitive research data. KonsortSWD's measures further enhance its user-friendliness (cf. [M2-2](#), [M3-4](#)). Given its robustness and efficiency, it is unlikely that viable alternatives will emerge, even with repeated promises to simplify data access through legal reforms such as the planned Research Data Act.

Due to the sensitive nature of data in our research disciplines, the protection of personal data has been at the core of the RDC system since its establishment. The model is widely considered to be a best practice. KonsortSWD's RDCs have substantial expertise with regard to data protection. RatSWD has issued statements on several GDPR-related regulatory endeavors since 2020 (RatSWD, 2021). In addition, RDCs have established a fruitful exchange with the Office of the Federal Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information. Within NFDI, KonsortSWD has co-initiated and co-chairs section ELSA's task force Data Protection. Additionally, KonsortSWD supports a current application for the establishment of a research ethics research group by the LMU Munich, WZB and RatSWD in the DFG's Scientific Library Services and Information Systems (LIS) programme.

Regarding access to and use of data, we expect new demands to emerge. KonsortSWD will address these with its flex funds (cf. [3.4.5](#))

4.4 Services Provided by the Consortium

Table 2 lists the services developed in the first funding period of KonsortSWD, grouped by service category (Amelung, Anthofer, et al., 2023). It adds services funded from the institutional budgets of the consortium partners, where the latter include - but are not limited to - the RDCs maintained by the partner institutions. Please note that this list and services listed in the Data Sheet (cf. A5) differ from each other in five aspects: 1) The Data Sheet does not allow listing of “Support/Consulting” services as acknowledged and defined in NFDI (Amelung, Anthofer, et al., 2023) and beyond. A substantial number of eight services is thus suppressed from appendix 5. 2) We do not include institutionally funded services in the DataSheet. They are already fully developed and run with one or more of our partners and are open for use for the community; 3) this list allows for multiple classifications, whereas the Data Sheet does not. QualidataNet, for example, has a website reported in the Data Sheet but also does extensive consulting we wish to reflect here; 4) this table includes services to be developed through this proposal (in *italics*). 5) We include RatSWD’s activity here; while a community activity, it also has a support component to it.

Table 2: Services provided and proposed by KonsortSWD by category and funding

Categories	Project Funded Services ¹⁷	Institutionally Funded Services
Databases	QualidataNet	Databases at RDCs, VerbundFDB search portal forschungsdaten-bildung.de , GESIS’ Archiving BASIC , MOJRE data , ZPID’s PsychArchives
DataCuration	QualidataNet, RDC Mol , BASiD , Linking Data , QualidataNet - DDI , ProLTA	Data curation services by all 41 RDCs and KonsortSWD partner institutions, VerbundFDB
Libraries/Application Programming Interfaces (API)	Harmonization - Question Link , Linking Textual Data (R packages: LinkTools , polmineR , cwbtools , and RcppCWB), OpenAPI	
Support and Consulting	Access to Firm Data , Data Findability , FDI Coordination , Guides Systematic Reviews , Harmonization - Question Link , Harmonization - StanDem , Helpdesk , QualidataNet , RatSWD Best Practice Collection Research Ethics , RatSWD Standardised Questionnaire Catalogue , RDC Support (CTS, contracts) , RDM Support - qualitative , early career researcher support	Ethics committees at partner institutions, GESIS’ Data Services , support and consulting services at all RDCs and KonsortSWD partner institutions, VerbundFDB -consulting services
Tools/Applications	Open Data Format , PIDService , QualidataNet	da ra , Harmonization - Question Link
Training	RatSWD Best Practice Collection Research Ethics , RatSWD Teaching	Contributions to Leibniz workshop series on the introduction to RDM,

¹⁷ Links are provided to web sources / services online.

	Slide set for RDM, RDM Compas, ASSURED	Training activities by RDCs and VerbundFDB
Web Applications	CODI, Data on Crises, Forum4MICA, QualidataNet, Stamp (RDMO)	paneldata.org, ZPID PreReg in Psychology
Workflows and Pipelines	QualidataNet, RDCNet, Stamp, Disclosure Control, Federation with EOSC Node	RDM processes at RDCs and in VerbundFDB, user management systems at RDCs, workflows at most partner institutes and RDCs

4.4.1 Ensuring and Increasing Service Usage

During the initial funding phase, KonsortSWD's services have been met with great interest and generated substantial impact in its communities (cf. 3.2, A5). The latter include our primary target groups of research data managers and data users in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences, but also extend to other stakeholders such as public administrators and policymakers who have benefited from the expertise provided by RatSWD - e.g., from consultations and expert opinions on a new Research Data Act.

To ensure and increase the service usage in the second phase we will

a) Broaden the user base: Since 2020, RatSWD has accredited further RDCs, expanding the network to 41 centres. These add new data types to KonsortSWD, such as object and spatial data (IOER RDC – RDC of the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development) visual data (RDC DeZIM of the German Centre for Integration and Migration Research), or historic company data (RDC SAFE of the Leibniz Institute for Financial Research), as well as established data types such as survey or administrative register data (RDC-BAuA of the Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health or BAMF-RDC of the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees). While the disciplines of economics, education, political science, psychology, and sociology are well represented among both the consortium members and its user base, we have begun to integrate further disciplines from the broader field of the social, educational, behavioural, and economic sciences. Specifically, flexible Network Development Grants have been successfully used to add cooperation partners, e.g., from sports science in 2023. They aim to establish an RDC for sports science data (cf. M4-5). We will continue and expand such efforts in the second funding phase, which includes the strategic use of flex funds (cf. 3.4.5) to establish new collaborations and deepen existing partnerships. Specifically, we have actively supported the proposal for a Specialised Information Service (Fachinformationsdienst) Gender Studies to support this rich and diverse research community and integrate data from this community into our infrastructure. The Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ) has joined our consortium following the successful implementation of two use cases. KonsortSWD will furthermore leverage cooperations with other consortia in related areas (BERD@NFDI, NFDI4DataScience) to expand the user base (cf. 3.2).

b) Deepen and expand engagement with existing user bases: From the first funding phase, we learned that KonsortSWD has been more successful in bringing its services to institutional actors (e.g., academic associations) and professional data managers than to individual researchers, particularly those in their early careers. To address this, a new measure (cf. [M3-2](#)) was specifically designed to familiarise early career researchers with the consortium's services. This group is relevant as it will shape RDM usage and is increasingly aligned with Open Science and reproducibility (Gewin, 2016). Another critical goal is to strengthen university-based research involvement. Most RDCs are hosted by non-university institutes, however, integrating universities and their researchers is essential to maximising the consortium's impact. We have already integrated over ten research-active universities into the NFDI association and have established productive regular exchanges. We will extend this approach through collaboration with the [Association of Social Science Institutes](#) (ASI e.V.), with 45 member institutes from social sciences departments in Germany (cf. [M1-3](#)).

c) Internationalise: Efforts to improve and enhance the use of our services by connecting and cooperating with relevant European and non-European international partners have been initiated and will be further pursued in the second funding period. The international links are described above (cf. [3.3](#)). Moreover, a priority for the next funding round will be to achieve optimal representation of data, tools and services in the EOSC by ensuring the compatibility of our metadata standards with those of the EOSC (cf. [M2-1](#)). We will explore with ICPSR whether cooperation on service use is possible.

d) Cooperate with other NFDI consortia and the NFDI association: KonsortSWD will also continue to foster cooperation within the NFDI, ranging from (leading) roles in Task Forces and sections across multidisciplinary use cases, jointly designed services and basic services (for details cf. [3.2](#)).

4.4.2 Enabling Expansion and Scaling

To enable the expansion and scaling of our services, we follow several approaches. Maintaining and expanding **digital training and consulting infrastructures** is one key strategy. It includes RDM Compas (cf. [M3-7](#)), an online platform offering information and best practice recommendations for data managers and curators, and Forum4MICA (cf. [M3-4](#)), a searchable online forum facilitating exchange between RDC staff and data users. The newly established KonsortSWD Helpdesk (cf. [M3-5](#)) will serve as a one-stop point for users, assisting them in navigating our services and collecting feedback to update our portfolio.

We will also continue to contribute to mutual learning and the dissemination of best practices within NFDI. This exchange will add knowledge about potential new avenues for scaling services. Additionally, we are learning from other consortia about effective helpdesk support and systematic approaches to larger infrastructure projects in need of RDM support.

Finally, we will pursue **technical approaches**: We will extend RDCnet, a network providing secure access to data from multiple RDCs, by adding more secure-access sites at universities. This expansion will reduce the need for time-consuming and costly travel for users (cf. [M2-4](#)). We are also focusing on automation and tools, refining an open-source anonymisation tool for qualitative data (cf. [M4-2](#)), developing partial automation of disclosure control checks in RDCs (cf. [M3-1](#)), semi-automating ingest of sensitive firm data (cf. [M4-6](#)), and exploring the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Forum4MICA (cf. [M3-4](#)). These efforts aim to handle labour-intensive data management tasks more efficiently.

KonsortSWD recognizes the significant opportunities presented by the automation of RDM through AI. AI can streamline automating metadata production, disclosure control, and anonymisation tasks, among others, making RDM processes more efficient and scalable. However, there are no ready-made answers across the NFDI on how to best invest sparse resources. To prepare a sustainable strategy for integrating AI into RDM, KonsortSWD has initiated several collaborations. For instance, we are organizing a workshop on Large Language Models (LLMs) in scientific publishing, in collaboration with NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Earth, and NFDI-MatWerk, to explore the potential applications (cf. [3.2.2](#)). Additionally, we have established a partnership with ICPSR at the University of Michigan to leverage their AI-driven tools like TurboCurator (cf. [3.3.1](#)). Once viable AI solutions materialise, KonsortSWD is committed to using flex funds to implement use cases for these innovations.

4.4.3 Tracking of Success

KonsortSWD has **tracked all its funded activities** since the start of its first funding period, with evaluation support from our Advisory Board. We use lean internal monthly updates to monitor progress and promptly detect challenges, tracking interactions with target communities, activity outputs, and event reception. We collect both quantitative indicators and qualitative descriptions. For instance, the success of the data-sharing contract template (Schallaböck, Hoffstätter, et al., 2023) is evident from its over 1,300 downloads on Zenodo since its publication. Indicators for other services, such as Forum4MICA, QualidataNet, and RDM Compas, have emerged since their release in late 2023 and continue into 2024.

The RDC network with currently 41 accredited RDCs, is integral to KonsortSWD, participating in a yearly monitoring (RatSWD, 2023e, 2024f). These reports include staff, research output, data offerings, usage, access pathways, service offerings, and internationalisation efforts. Before the release of DFG's Data Sheet, our internal monitoring used a multi-indicator approach. We will now define one KPI per service to capture the most important impact, although we remain sceptical of any single indicator's reliability and will continue to use multiple indicators. In the second funding phase, KonsortSWD will refine its monitoring, improving the granularity and comparability of milestones and deliverables, and facilitate transparent KPI presentation, possibly through a dashboard like NFDI4Biodiversity's [Scorpion KPI Dashboard](#).

Our **Advisory Board** (cf. 3.1.3), will **continue to evaluate** our work, focusing on the relevance of services to our communities and additional criteria for long-term sustainability, such as the development of business models. To improve measuring success, KonsortSWD partners are preparing a proposal with all consortia through Task Force Evaluation and Reporting to coordinate KPIs and reporting development in NFDI, based on scientifically sound and internationally established indicators, expected to be submitted by the end of 2024.

4.4.4 Ensuring Sustainable Operation of the Services

To ensure the sustainable operation of services, the consortium's strategy (cf. 2.1.3) involves two main elements. First, it categorises services based on their **developmental stages**: "in operation," "extensions," and "in development." This categorisation helps the targeted allocation of resources and in the development of comprehensive work programs. Second, a business and operating model is developed for each service that is suitable for a continuous operation in NFDI.

KonsortSWD implements a cost estimation approach to determine the expenses for maintaining each service, based on functionalities expected at the end of the first funding period. For example, in the case of contract templates for data usage, we learned how much effort (in time and consulting fees) is involved, which dependencies exist with partners to pre-test solutions, and at which intervals updates will likely be necessary. This approach acknowledges the need to understand long-term service costs, additional resources needed to develop, and "extension" services, while recognising the inherent uncertainty in service evolution.

All services have a deliverable for a business model due in October 2027¹⁸, facilitated by a dedicated Task Area Governance and Sustainability (cf. 5.5). This process involves workshops and expertise from both internal and external sources, focusing on business and organisational aspects of service operation. KonsortSWD will collaborate with NFDI4Culture to leverage mutual expertise and consolidate approaches within NFDI. This discussion will take place in a broad context, where an ideal path to proceed is still lacking (RfII, 2023, p. 10).

As part of a business models will be to specify financial aspects for delivering a service, we will draw on a combination models we have started to develop. We anticipate that these models will serve as a kind of modular toolbox for the business models. The extent to which these models are suitable will differ between developments, services in day-to-day operation and functional extensions to a service. Furthermore, services have widely different user structures and provider models that will also impact which model - or mix of models - can be considered for sustainable operation. The table below introduces the models KonsortSWD has so far started discussing. At the same time, RDCNet will start introducing a fee-based model (cf. M2-4).

¹⁸ See footnote 9 for a definition.

Table 3: Modular toolbox for business models

Funding Model	Details
community-based	Operation is community based, no direct costs accrue (e.g., open source code)
Consortium	Costs of operation shared by a consortium of institutions from their existing institutional resources
fees, individual	Costs billed to individual users, based on full-cost or partial cost of service operation
fees, institutional	Costs billed to institutions to allow usage for their members, based on full-cost or partial cost of service operation
fees, members	Costs distributed across a number of members (individual and / or institutional) of an operator (e.g., association), based on full-cost or partial cost of service operation
institutional funds, existing	Funding from existing institutional funding of an operator
institutional funds, top-up	Additional funding provided for the operation of an NFDI-service by public funders
Third party funds	Temporarily acquired funds from research funder

While selecting suitable business models, KonsortSWD will carefully weigh the pros and cons each model is likely to have and make sure that suitable combinations of models are chosen where this is deemed beneficial dependent on the specific character of a service.

4.4.5 Strategies for Terminating or Transferring a Service to another Operator

The data services forming the basis of KonsortSWD are for the most part institutionally and sustainably funded through their host institutions. This solid funding net with partners in the RDC network sharing similar interests has already helped to mitigate risks of termination, e.g., serving as a fall back for other data that could not be sustainably funded. However, this is not true for services currently under development. Therefore, we anticipate two scenarios leading to service termination: 1) project underperformance including obsolescence and 2) externally triggered events causing financial strain, precluding continued operation of a service.

For the first scenario, KonsortSWD has quality assurance mechanisms, including evaluation by our Advisory Board and stringent financial controlling with project monitoring. KPIs for each service are developed as part of our quality assurance efforts (cf. 4.4.3). In the first funding phase, this process led to the conclusion that two development efforts, Automated Coding of Open Responses (CODI) and OpenAPI, were unlikely to deliver sufficient added value and will not be continued.

To prevent the second scenario, developing solid business models is a central task for this funding period, including the development of service-specific exit strategies. KonsortSWD's general exit strategy comprises four main elements: 1) avoid termination by generating additional resources, reducing running costs, or switching the service to another operator; 2) mitigate effects and preserve

data by transferring it to other network partners or making it publicly available if necessary; 3) ensure user data is moved to comparable services; and 4) provide support for users during transitions.

Our approach has already thrived in the first funding round by reallocating resources from non-viable services to more promising activities (e.g., through termination of CODI and OpenAPI). In another case, KonsortSWD has substantially mitigated the risk of service termination and moved towards a sustainable business model by developing a module for the [RDM certificate course at TH Cologne](#), which is now funded by user fees as part of a reputable program.

4.5 Impact of Changes of External Conditions/Constraints

Research Data Centres (RDCs), which are at the core of KonsortSWD, are in constant and close exchange with their users and therefore directly learn about changing user needs and adapt accordingly. KonsortSWD has added further systematic elements to assure user-driven development of our infrastructure (cf. 3.1.3). Furthermore, the organisation of RDCs as independent entities committing to common rules, quality criteria, data access standards etc. is demonstrably well suited to accommodate new RDC. Similarly, KonsortSWD has made it a key principle of its structure being open to integrate new important initiatives into its organisational bodies and work programme, for example, the Network of Educational Research Data (Verbund Forschungsdaten Bildung) in the second funding phase.

We recognize the importance of staying adaptable to keep pace with digital innovations. To maintain an up-to-date infrastructure relevant for researchers, we address four key dimensions of external developments: (1) a changing data landscape, (2) technological trends, notably AI, (3) a changing legislative environment, and (4) trends among user groups. For each dimension, we outline relevant current developments and provide procedural tools to monitor future changes. These tools will facilitate projections and function as early-warning systems, ensuring our infrastructure remains cutting-edge and responsive.

The **data landscape** is rapidly transforming. As digitalisation and automation advance, procedures to generate and collect large volumes of qualitative and quantitative data become increasingly sophisticated. For example, automatic interview transcriptions significantly reduce the cost of data generation from qualitative sources. The proliferation of digital trace data, including social media communication, highlights that much data relevant to social research is owned by large private companies. The measure FirmData (cf. M4-6) is an attempt to ease access to these data. A RatSWD working group (M1-1) seeks to provide community-based recommendations on access and utilisation of firm data for science, both activities are interwoven. We offer innovative tools to connect curated data with web data, **adding value through linking** (M2-7). Additionally, multidisciplinary use cases and strategic use of flex funds can serve to support this integration.

Second, just as everyone across NFDI, KonsortSWD faces highly-paced **technological trends**. It is evident that one of the most significant developments is the emergence of new, powerful AI tools, which makes it imperative to leverage their potential for RDM, specifically for data curation and

services to be developed in the second funding phase are designated as in “development”. Work programmes for extensions are always presented in the same measure as the corresponding operation.

Beyond that, we structure the measure descriptions as follows: a brief description of the function of each service/measure is followed by details on how and why it adds value to its target groups. In the ensuing part the existing user base is described for services developed in the first funding phase. A description, starting with a summary, of the work programme follows. To remain within the 120-page limit, we list only the work plan for key deliverables in the description. We have, however, created detailed tables of milestones and deliverables which we will use for monitoring progress.

Table 4 provides an overview of the Task Areas and their measures. Please note that the work programme only specifies the plans until the end of the current NFDI funding framework in 2028. In 2029-30, all services will switch into an operations mode (for details cf. [3.4.6](#)).

Table 4: Overview of task areas and measures

Task Area	Measures*	Responsible Co-spokesperson(s)
1 Involving Communities	RatSWD (1- 5 4), FDI Coordination (1- 2 4), Community involvement multiplier (1- 3 3), Communication and Public Relations Office (1- 4 1), Consortial Conference - KSWD (1- 5 3)	Jan Paul Heisig, Kerstin Schneider Monika Jungbauer-Gans
2 Advancing FAIRness	Federation with EOSC EU Node (2-1), Findability of Services and Data (2-2), PID Service (2-3) , RDCnet (2- 5 4), Pro-LTA (2-5) , Open Data Format (2- 4 6), Linking Textual Data (2- 3 7), QualidataNet-Metadate (2-8)	Brigitte Mathiak, Klaus Tochtermann
3 Enhancing Competences	ASSURED (3-1), Capacities for early career researchers (3-2), ELSA (3-3), Forum4MICA (3- 5 4), Helpdesk KonsortSWD (3- 5 6), QualidataNet - RDM-Portfolio & data re-use (3- 6 7), RDM Compas (3- 7 8), FAIR-RDM (Stamp) (3-8 4), VerbundFDB (3-9)	Christian Aßmann, Katarina Blask
4 Integrating Data	BASiD (4-1) , Contract Templates (4-2) , CrisesData (4- 3 1), DisclosureControl (4-4) , FDZ MoL (4- 5 2), Firm-Data (4- 6 3), LinkingData (4-7) , QualidataNet Portal (4- 8 4), StanDem (4- 9 5)	Jan Goebel, Claudia Niessner
5 Governance and Sustainability	Sustainable Business Models (5-1), Coordination Office (5-2), Financial and Contract Administration (5-3), Flex funds (5-4)	Christof Wolf

* Please note that the numbering of Measures was changed to allow continuous numbering of the remaining activities after the budget cut.

5.1 Task Area 1 – Involving Communities

TA-Lead: Jan Paul Heisig, ~~Kerstin Schneider~~ ~~Monika Jungbauer-Gans~~

Task Area 1 "Involving Communities" focuses on the interaction with and integration of users as core principles in KonsortSWD's activities.

Objectives & Measures: TA1 aligns with KonsortSWD's central objectives, particularly promoting mutual learning (O8) and meeting the needs of its user base (O5). Additionally, RatSWD will foster expansion and quality assurance in the sensitive research data-related infrastructure (O1).

To achieve these objectives, TA1 will implement various measures, including RatSWD (M1-~~5~~4), a bottom-up community-driven approach that ensures balanced representation of academic and data-producing perspectives in shaping data infrastructure policies. RatSWD also plays a key role in representing community interests in the legislative process and publishes position papers on planned research data legislation. The triennial Conference on Social and Economic Data (KSWD) (M1-~~3~~45) fosters interdisciplinary exchange on research data. Further measures include an accreditation

process for RDCs, which provides a solution for making quality-assured research data available (M1-54). Close cooperation with the FDI Committee (M1-42) helps understand the needs of RDCs. Measures M1-3 "Community involvement: multipliers" and M1-4 "Communication and Public Relations Office" enable comprehensive interaction and communication with KonsortSWD's communities.

Contributors: WZB is responsible for managing the business of RatSWD, particularly running the RatSWD office, as well as the measures for community involvement M1-3 to M1-5, all implemented by the RatSWD office. The chair of RatSWD serves as a co-spokesperson for TA1. LIfBi hosts the FDI Coordination. The communities associated with KonsortSWD encompass a diverse range of stakeholders, including 15 academic associations and over 2,600 individual researchers participating in the 2023 [RatSWD election](#), user councils and scientific advisory boards of accredited RDCs, data producers, and institutions interested in integrating KonsortSWD's services.

Risks: Main risks of development and implementation relate to funding cuts. The successful involvement of communities relies on voluntary and complementary collaboration of diverse stakeholders. Participation in developing, advancing, and implementing KonsortSWD's services varies between communities in levels of approachability and openness, making it challenging to plan the necessary effort and timelines in advance. To mitigate these risks, we pursue a differentiated approach, reaching out to different target groups using multiple actions and methods. Concepts for events, esp. the Consortial Conference, are established and tried. Implementation risks correspond with general hazards of organising and hosting large events.

Cooperation: TA1 works systematically and strategically with all measures developing and maintaining services. As a community/communication node, it cooperates with other consortia and the NFDI directorate.

Conclusion: TA1 carries forward RatSWD's approach of community involvement and user integration, ensuring that KonsortSWD's efforts are aligned with the needs and perspectives of the scientific community. This fosters a collaborative approach to advancing research data infrastructure.

M1-14: Communication and Public Relations Office

Profile: Communication and Public Relations Office						Category: Community		
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals				Section: NFDI-Communication-Circle				
DFG KPI: No. of activities for community activation				Partners: WZB				
Prop. KPI: No. of recipients/viewers of activities				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: all other measures, esp. the Coordination Office				Status: Operation				
Consortia: -				External Collab.: -				

Function: This measure administers the consortium's internal and external communication.

Value Added: This measure helps to bring the consortium's services and publications closer to the target groups and centralises the public relations efforts of the consortium maintaining the website, and providing material in the consortium's corporate design to facilitate a consistent corporate identity and to strengthen the consortium as a highly recognisable brand. Its media and social media work as well as internal communication activities support cultural change within research communities.

Existing user base: Persons from academia interested in RDM-related topics and services, RatSWD's community including academic associations; KonsortSWD measures, press contacts

Work Programme - Summary: The communication and public relations office continues and deepens its highly relevant work in promoting KonsortSWD's services via channelling its public relations activities. The office runs the website, provides templates, presentations, and merchandise in the consortium's established corporate design. It supports the preparation of papers, statements, recommendations, reports, and press releases including established publication series. It covers the media work and manages the various social media channels. The edition and layout for an external and internal newsletter are in the office's responsibility. Moreover, its staff supports the organisation of the Consortial Conference (M1-35) and the onboarding of new employees.

Detailed Plan: To communicate what KonsortSWD does remains of great importance for the professionalisation of RDM in the related disciplines. The set-up of a communication and public relations office has proven successful. However, having learned from the first funding phase that KonsortSWD is not yet as well-known as we would like it to be, we will further improve our work (also in regular exchange with other NFDI communicators via the "Kommunikationskreis") and follow a more nuanced approach especially in the social media strategy. At the annual network meeting in autumn 2023, we reviewed our communication strategy. Feedback from a consortium-internal poll in spring 2024 led to improved templates and merchandise. The objective for the second funding phase is that researchers and RDM-professionals from KonsortSWD's disciplines know and recognise KonsortSWD as the platform that offers various services to foster RDM within their research work.

Communication and Public relation activities include the following fields:

- **Corporate identity:** KonsortSWD's visual language, built on the ant KonRat, has high recognition and forms a strong corporate identity within NFDI and KonsortSWD communities. The evolving design, with nfdi4society in the subtitle, enhances recognition and promotes KonsortSWD's services.
- **Website:** Developed in the first funding phase and restructured based on user feedback, our website will be maintained with content management system (CMS) hosting, providing access to the helpdesk (M3-65) as a central contact point.

more multipliers such as RDM professionals (e.g., at libraries, universities and universities of applied sciences, or non-university research institutions), federal state RDM initiatives, research funding organisations, or specialised information services) and the Association of Social Science Institutes (ASI e.V.). This broader engagement aims to promote services more effectively, receive direct feedback, and ensure KonsortSWD remains responsive to community needs, translating them into novel or modified services.

Existing user base: existing contacts and cooperations with above-mentioned organisations

Work Programme - Summary: Building on past achievements, KonsortSWD addresses community involvement as a key objective. Maintaining and widening KonsortSWD's user base is an important goal. The community officer's role will be strengthened to this end. KonsortSWD takes a two-way approach to help researchers with RDM: make researchers aware of its services, and use their feedback to improve those services. We will provide researchers with suitable information on KonsortSWD's services, including active participation in events by multipliers, as far as resources allow.

Detailed Plan: In June 2024, we held a digital network meeting with 25 academic associations to better understand current community needs. These findings will guide our future work. Regular digital follow-up meetings are planned for the second funding phase, allowing academic associations, including those without elected RatSWD members, to participate in the development of KonsortSWD.

A community strategy will be developed (by Q34/265) to systematically broaden KonsortSWD's user base, reviewed annually, and adjusted as needed. We will continue attending academic conferences and events by different multipliers, participating in RDM sessions to introduce KonsortSWD and engage with (future) users. We will also continue to support Consortial Conferences (M1-35) through activities targeting multipliers.

To engage with different multipliers and learn from the communities, we will pursue these activities:

- *KonsortSWD meets _:* Continuing our digital dialogue format "KonsortSWD Roadshow" (e.g. Baumann et al., 2023; Miller et al., 2024; Obst, 2023), we will develop this into a forum "KonsortSWD meets _" to present the consortium's services to various stakeholders, such as the federal state RDM initiatives to discuss stakeholders' needs and solutions for data collection, handling, documentation, publication, or (re-)use.
- *Presenting: KonsortSWD @ _:* As academic associations' annual conferences are important opportunities to get in touch with communities and to learn about their needs, we will continue to present KonsortSWD at four to six conferences each year, both with interactive information booths and in RDM-related sessions, with an increased focus on early career researchers (M3-2), working on small projects (RatSWD, 2023c). Learning from experience in the first funding phase, we will focus on large conferences. Additionally, we will attend events of other consortia to support targeted engagement, as far as resources allow.

- *Community Mingle*: We will invite various stakeholders from KonsortSWD’s communities to discuss key issues and innovative approaches to identify potential interest groups and trends.
- ~~*Matchmaking*: We will facilitate one-to-one dialogues between (potential) users and service providers, cooperating with the helpdesk (M3-5) and the federal state RDM initiatives.~~
- *Broadening and Integrating*: The Association of Social Science Institutes (ASI e.V.) is currently being reformed and will become more closely linked to KonsortSWD and RatSWD to systematically integrate relevant institutes and university departments into KonsortSWD’s communities (by Q4/25). Closer cooperation with ASI e.V. with currently 45 member institutes, will significantly expand the community base. We strive to augment ASI e.V. by integrating further members (concept due Q3~~2~~/26).
- *Grounded in research funding*: We plan to include support for data archiving and curation by KonsortSWD partners in funding organisation calls. To devise promising strategies, we will collaborate with NFDI4Culture. Ideally, projects comprising data collection will be encouraged to process their data for reuse in cooperation with RatSWD-accredited RDCs or related repositories.

M1-35: Consortial Conference – KSWD

Profile: Consortial Conference – KSWD							Category: Community	
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals				Section: -				
DFG KPI: -				Partners: RatSWD members, WZB				
Prop. KPI: Number of participants at the conference				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: RatSWD (M1-1), CoO (M5-2)				Status: Operation				
Consortia: (to be invited)				External Collab.: -				

Function: Taking place every three years, the traditional Conference on Social and Economic Data (KSWD) is the main German forum for exchange on the topic of research data within and across the consortium’s scientific disciplines as well as the policy community.

Value added: The KSWD initiates and deepens an open multidisciplinary exchange and promotes the further development of the research data infrastructure for the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. It thus strengthens awareness of KonsortSWD among our target groups.

Existing user base: KSWD has already taken place nine times, with up to 300 participants from various backgrounds such as research, RDCs, politics, or administration (see, e.g., [9|KSWD in 2023](#)). An evaluation conducted in 2023 showed a high rate of renewed participation (45%).

Work Programme - Summary: This measure organises and implements the triannual consortial conference KSWD, which serves as an important forum for inter- and transdisciplinary exchange on the topic of research data (management) and brings together stakeholders from the consortium’s communities. The next conference (10|KSWD) is planned for June 2026, the scope of the conference being adjusted according to available resources number of participants, ~~the 11|KSWD is foreseen~~

~~of an RDC in order to drive forward the development of the network.~~ With new accreditations and expanded dialogue formats with repositories, data archives, networks, RDM-professionals, etc. on topics relating to the improvement of access to research data, coordinated efforts become pivotal. The committee also builds a bridge between RDCs and other services developed in KonsortSWD.

Existing user base: The user base consists of 41 RDCs accredited by RatSWD and one RDC with guest status that has not yet started the accreditation process (see [overview of data centres](#)). In view of the steadily growing number of FDI members (see [development](#) during the past decades), further accreditations are to be expected. The existing user base is expected to grow further with the implementation of permanent guests in the FDI Committee.

Work Programme - Summary: The RDCs operate independently and are coordinated through the FDI Committee, collaborating with data users in KonsortSWD disciplines. KonsortSWD funding maintains this network (via FDI Committee), ensuring the development and harmonisation of RDM standards and RDC workflows. Additionally, KonsortSWD adds value by providing services for the integration of the heterogeneous data landscape. Beyond continuing the coordination work from the first funding phase, new activities are planned: implementing new participation formats to include external parties in FDI Committee, as designed by a common working group of RatSWD and FDI Committee in 2023/2024, enhancing public relations work using Forum4MICA, organising information series similar to Meet-the-Data ([M3-2](#)) and providing a contact point for inquiries from the scientific community via the helpdesk ([M3-65](#)).

Detailed Plan: The FDI Coordination's main task is organising two annual plenary meetings of RDC representatives, including agenda items open to permanent guests. To address challenges, FDI Committee invites external RDM and international experts to its meetings (e.g., the German Federal Archives or the Federal Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information). Meetings are held alternately virtually and face-to-face (Q2 & Q3 2026 - 2028, totaling six events). Moreover, Ad-hoc group meetings are carried out as needed, hence the timing cannot be scheduled in advance. FDI working groups are coordinated. One working group will write a report on the committee's long-term funding possibilities (Report on Business Model due Q4/27). To increase usage of expert knowledge in FDI Committee, two actions will be taken: first, establishing new participation formats for non-members, such as expert-talk series (with at least one event per year, totalling three events for 2026-2028). Second, administering new permanent guests to the Committee to expand its reach, to offer new opportunities for collaboration within KonsortSWD and to offer new application cases for the services developed by KonsortSWD. Tasks for the guest status comprise (a) organising the admission process, (b) evaluating and preparing extension of temporary guest status and (c) tailoring communication towards them. Minutes and meeting documents, currently not public, will be disseminated with the support from the Communication and Public Relations Office ([M1-14](#)). We plan to publish meeting content and FDI Committee activities (one publication per plenary meeting in 2026-2028). Furthermore, we will use Forum4MICA ([M3-54](#)) and serve as a contact point for RDC-related inquiries for the KonsortSWD Helpdesk ([M3-65](#)).

The Committee's work also raises legal issues relevant for KonsortSWD. Therefore, applications for flex funds (M5-4) are planned to fund external legal opinion on these issues.

M1-54: RatSWD - German Data Forum

Profile: RatSWD – German Data Forum							Category: Community	
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals				Section: ELSA, Industry				
DFG KPI: No. of activities for community engagement				Partners: RatSWD members, WZB				
Prop. KPI: No. of downloads/recipients of recommendations				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: M1-2, M1-3, M1-4, M1- 15 , M3-2, M4- 13				Status: Operation				
Consortia: BERD@NFDI				External Collab.: Stifterverband				

Function: RatSWD is the community-linked backbone of the consortium. It organises input from the community, e.g., through its elected representatives, and continues to operate as a forum for exchange between data users and producers and serves as a voice for research communities.

Value Added: RatSWD looks back at a long history of developing services for the research data infrastructure in the social and economic sciences. As an institutionalised forum for dialogue, it has enabled the continuous exchange between data producers and data users to the end that high-quality and research-relevant data are made available. RatSWD performs as an advisory body and contributes its expertise in counselling political actors and administration. The unique representation of community and scientists' interests within RatSWD is of high value for KonsortSWD as well as the NFDI as a whole: it is a blueprint for the structural institutionalisation of negotiation processes resulting in bottom-up, community-driven, and aligned standards and recommendations.

Existing user base: researchers in KonsortSWD's disciplines, academic associations, political actors and government officials, RDCs

Work Programme - Summary: RatSWD brings together data users and data producers, it accredits RDCs and monitors the quality of its long-standing related research data infrastructure. It advises the Federal Government on data-related legislative issues and publishes recommendations. RatSWD members whose institutions are not funded by the consortium serve as the consortium's Advisory Board (see 3.4). As RatSWD's members are active on a voluntary basis, the RatSWD office organises and coordinates the committee's work. It is led by the RatSWD director who contributes a significant share of their capacities to managing the office including the scientific, community and communication officers (doctoral/postdoctoral-equivalent) and supporting staff.

Detailed plan: RatSWD will - with the support of its office - continue to:

1. contribute the expertise of its members on data-related issues to the NFDI and to political and legislative processes to further improve the accessibility and usability of high-quality data;

2. offer a forum for dialogue between data producers and data users from the diverse stakeholder communities of KonsortSWD by involving community representatives in its meetings;
3. provide recommendations and training material on RDM-related topics for researchers and data producers with a focus on sensitive data and data from administrative sources, in close coordination with the community measures [M1-23](#) and [M3-2](#);
4. accredit and ensure the quality of RDCs through an annual monitoring and reporting process conducted in close cooperation with FDI Committee and applying standards and criteria that have been updated and refined during the first funding phase. It will maintain a complaints office to address data provision-related problems between data users and the RDC;
5. act as the consortium's Advisory Board focussing on the assessment of projects applying for flex funds, with coordinative tasks being handled by the staff of the RatSWD office.

More specifically, this measure will pursue the following activities:

- RatSWD working groups (on ~~data trusteeship~~, crises data, firm data and health data) complete their papers and recommendations (~~Q4/25 to~~ Q1/26) supported by the responsible scientific officers. Results are communicated to communities, political actors and relevant actors within the NFDI (Q1/26) and presented at the Consortial Conference (M1-~~35~~) taking place in June 2026 (Q2/26). A similar process is planned for the end of the 9th appointment period in Q4/28.
- ~~Following the German Parliamentary elections in September 2025,~~ RatSWD will provide scientific policy consultation to the ~~new~~ German government concerning the accessibility of research data and the legislative measures necessary for future-oriented RDM, such as an amendment to the Federal Statistics Law (BStatG) (~~start Q4/25,~~ ongoing).
- In summer 2025, the office will start preparations for the election of RatSWD members from the scientific community, taking place in Q1/26. The election process will be completely digital, using the help of a service provider. This procedure was used in the previous elections and has proven to be efficient. Strategies for reaching more voters for the RatSWD elections will be developed and implemented before the 2026 election. The nomination of members from the data-producing institutions will be organised in Q1/26, both processes leading to the appointment by the Federal Government in Q2/26 for the 9th appointment period starting in July 2026.
- Until Q4/26, the newly appointed RatSWD will decide on its work programme for the 9th appointment period on the basis of identified community needs and will initiate suitable task forces and/or~~and up to three (new)~~ working groups that develop recommendations and position papers on RDM-related issues. This work programme will be pursued throughout the appointment period, lasting until June 2029.
- In Q~~2~~4/25, a task force will be established to deal with the future role of RatSWD within the NFDI and to develop a business or operational model for RatSWD in cooperation with TA5 and in consultation with the NFDI Directorate until Q4/26~~27~~ to contribute to OneNFDI. In this context,

an understanding with the NFDI directorate regarding advocacy and advisory tasks will be reached.

- RatSWD will continue to convene two to three times a year either in person or online. Community needs will be reflected upon and generate strategic actions, e.g., position papers and exchanges with relevant actors. To facilitate community exchange, RatSWD will meet virtually at least once a year with community representatives from academic associations.
- Members of RatSWD will act as a scientific board for the newly-established Forum Research Ethics (see [Letter of Support in A3](#), start foreseen in Q4/25, depending on successful proposal - external DFG project based on the long-term involvement and expertise of RatSWD in this area).

Activities foreseen for the years 2029 and 2030:

- Q2-Q3 2029: election/nomination of RatSWD members, appointment by Federal Government
- July Q3 2029: start of 10th appointment period (process July 2029 – December 2030 similar to processes to 2026-2028; 10th appointment period lasting until June 2032)
- Implementation of the results of the strategic process concerning business model, including the role of RatSWD within the NFDI

5.2 Task Area 2 – Advancing FAIRness

TA-Lead: Brigitte Mathiak, Klaus Tochtermann

Task Area 2 "Advancing FAIRness" bundles the information technology expertise of the consortium partners to advance the FAIRness of the data and services offered by KonsortSWD.

Objectives & Measures: TA2 aligns with several key objectives, including improving services and preparing sustainable business and operating models (O6), strategically extending national and international networks (O7), and partnering with other consortia for mutual benefit (O9). Additionally, TA2 contributes to presenting and explaining services to researchers (O4) and strengthening connections with other domains (O8).

To achieve these objectives, TA2 will implement various measures, including federating search functionality with EOSC EU Node (M2-1), improving findability for RDCs' data and services (M2-2), ~~and enabling variable registration through PID Service (M2-3)~~. Measures also focus on promoting accessibility through RDCnet (M2-45) ~~and ProLTA (M2-5)~~, enabling interoperability through Open Data Format (M2-64) and Linking Textual Data (M2-73), and promoting reusability through QualidataNet (M2-68). Measures are sorted along their (main) contribution to FAIR.

Contributors: Both GESIS and ZBW are involved in several of the measures and are represented through the co-spokespersons. Other contributors recur in their established roles: University of Bremen, DIW Berlin, University of Duisburg-Essen, and DIPF, to offer their expertise.

Risks: Since many of the measures in this TA have components of software engineering, hiring high-quality personnel is a challenge. Some of the tasks depend on a timely delivery of third parties, e.g., technical provision of the EOSC EU Node. Data providers might not implement recommendations on how to improve findability consistently. The change of the PID provider landscape may affect development and usage costs. The implementation of PIDs to partner use cases depend on the availability of software engineering and data modelling competencies. Generally, implementations depend on broadly agreed metadata and quality standards which might limit the scope of service functionalities.

Cooperation: We will work with TA1 to involve the community, in particular planned events and surveys and with TA5 to develop sustainability and a business model for the services. M2-8 will work within the QualidataNet framework, which spans from TA2 to TA4, providing direct connections to other TAs.

Conclusion: With this task area we will sustain the high standards of service from the first funding phase and continue to drive internationalisation and innovation in advancing the FAIRness of data and services within KonsortSWD.

M2-1: (F) Federation with EOSC EU Node

Profile: Federation with EOSC EU Node				Category: Support/Consulting, Workflow/ Pipeline				
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: RDCs, Data professionals								
DFG KPI: Number of executions								
Prop. KPI: Downloads of deliverables, number of repositories connected to EOSC EU node								
Internal Collab.: M5-2, TA2								
Consortia: BERD@NFDI								
				Section: Metadata				
				Partners: GESIS, ZBW				
				Basic Service: -				
				Status: Development				
				External Collab.: EOSC				

Function: In October 2024, the first version of the EOSC EU Node, provided by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) for research data management, will go online. According to the NFDI strategy, the NFDI wants to become a German National Node for EOSC. This measure will explore, design and implement how KonsortSWD, and NFDI data offers more generally, can be connected to the EOSC EU Node. KonsortSWD will do so in close collaboration with other NFDI consortia, e.g., BERD@NFDI, and Section Metadata.

Value Added: The continuation of EOSC post-2027 offers significant value by ensuring the sustainability and advancement of Open Science practices across Europe. In this context, German science policy, particularly the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, is actively positioning NFDI to play a leading role. With this measure, and together with other NFDI consortia, KonsortSWD will play a central role in this initiative. This measure is particularly relevant as KonsortSWD's engagement will enhance data sharing and interoperability, according to the FAIR Data Principles.

Existing user base: in development

Work Programme - Summary: On the technical side, this measure will explore, design and implement a technical federation of selected RDCs or data search engine providers (e.g., GESIS search engine) with the EOSC EU Node. To reduce complexity, the focus will be on the mapping of metadata schema available within KonsortSWD onto the EOSC EU Node metadata schema. Based on the results, the search indexes on both sides, KonsortSWD data providers and EOSC EU Node, can be extended. This will increase the visibility of KonsortSWD research data and services in Europe. In addition to technical aspects, we will also cope with the rules for participation, access policies, etc. as defined in the EOSC Federation handbook.

Detailed Plan: The measure will proceed as follows:

1. Exploration: Together with other NFDI consortia, we will explore the metadata schema of the EOSC EU Node, including other technical aspects (e.g., protocols, APIs).
2. Conceptualisation: Together with other NFDI consortia and Base4NFDI, we will design, at a conceptual level, how the KonsortSWD metadata schema can be mapped onto the EOSC EU Node schema and vice versa (Mapping concept: D1 Q4/26).
3. Implementation: The mapping concept from the previous step will be implemented. This also includes updating the relevant search indexes (Implemented Mapping: D2 Q4/27).
4. Evaluation: The mapping and the implementation will be evaluated according to a predefined set of criteria. (Evaluation report: D3 Q4/28)
5. Guideline: A guideline will be created to support other NFDI consortia in connecting to the EOSC EU node (D4 Q4/28).
6. The legal and governance framework for the federation with the EOSC EU node will be created according to the conditions set in the EOSC Federation handbook (D5 Q4/27).

influencing several outputs of the Working Group Search & Harvesting of the NFDI section Metadata (Mathiak, Widmann, et al., 2022, 2023).

Work Plan: This measure will continue to work on the monitoring and consulting tasks introduced in the first phase. Additionally, there will be annual monitoring reports for the years 2026 (D1 Q4/26) and 2027 (D2 Q4/27), which will include updated recommendations and new use case partners. These will entail results from an ongoing survey of the RDCs, which will be extended to other relevant repositories, analysis of web traffic and results from analysing current national and international trends, in particular from NFDI's sections, and RDA. The measure will also organise a community event to address current trends in data and service findability and to raise awareness for findability and present our results together with [M1-2](#) (Milestone 2 Q4/27).

Detailed Plan - Extension:

Lessons Learned: The consortium has learned during the first project phase that central infrastructure such as the NFDI is currently not the central hub for information for the majority of users. This means that measures to increase findability must involve external services, such as web search engines and have to be implemented with the help of individual data providers. Regarding services, the situation is even more decentralised. There are only very few and usually quite specialised platforms or registries for services and tools surrounding data. [Re3data](#) is important for data repositories. The [EOSC EU Node](#) contains some relevant services, but focuses on EOSC itself and is not (yet) widely known in the community. There are also activities in Base4NFDI, such as the new [nfdi.software](#) basic service which aims to improve access to NFDI software. An important lesson learned from previous experiences with data is that users should be met where they are. Therefore, it is vitally important to choose our partners well.

Work Plan: To increase the findability of services, the work will start by gathering a collection of KonsortSWD relevant services and their target groups, their current visibility on the web, and gaps between current and potential service usage (report on service visibility: D3 Q4/26). From this report, a strategy will be derived (Service Findability Strategy: D4 Q4/27), including [onetwo](#) or more use case partners (Milestone 1 - Implementation of service findability strategy with use case partners). The measure will devise a business model for on-going operation in close collaboration with [M5-1](#) by Q4/27. Two conceivable options are to integrate the current activities into a basic service or to attach them to one of the involved institutions as an in-kind contribution.

additional RDCs (EBDC, RWI) are presently finalising the necessary technical requirements and will integrate into RDCnet as soon as their infrastructure is ready. Although three other RDCs remain interested in participating, they currently face capacity constraints preventing them from establishing a compatible remote access structure (ZEW, LfBi, DZHW). At present, the consortium is working on the final details of the multilateral cooperation agreement. Once this has been clarified, the recruitment of the first test users starts, marking the transition from the pilot phase to the supervised roll-out.

Work Programme - Summary: Productive operations will be expanded and consolidated, new RDCs will be integrated and RDCnet will be promoted to researchers. A new website will be developed, and the booking platform will be optimised. Operational gaps will be identified and addressed as they arise in day-to-day operations. With an optimised RDCnet and a solid foundation of several RDCs and users, the focus will shift to the integration of non-RDC institutions. This will be achieved by developing an appropriate service- and cost model, where non-RDC institutions will receive RDCnet terminals for a fee, allowing their students and researchers direct access to research data. This model will ensure the long-term funding of RDCnet overheads.

Detailed Plan - Operation: The initial funding phase of RDCnet revealed significant challenges in implementing such a multilateral network, notably in establishing security criteria, technical standards and organisational processes that apply jointly to all participating RDCs. However, these hurdles have been overcome, laying the essential foundation for the RDCnet to now run a small-scale productive operation. The operation proposal will optimise the basic structures through three key instruments: 1) Public visibility through a new website providing researchers with a clear overview of the data available and their access point locations, as well as information on participation requirements for RDCs (D1 Q4/26). 2) A streamlined booking platform for the available GRWs within RDCnet that will improve and rationalise processes for both researchers and participating RDCs (D5 Q4/27). 3) A promotional campaign (including roadshow and social media) brings RDCnet closer to researchers and aims to attract additional RDCs to join the network (D6 Q4/28).

Detailed Plan - Extension: A comprehensive demand enquiry will be conducted in order to ascertain whether and which non-RDC institutions are interested in being integrated into the RDCnet, whether secure rooms for the workplace can be established on-site, and whether there is a basic willingness to pay for the service (Report on the enquiry: D2 Q4/26). Based on the aforementioned evaluation, the existing cooperation agreement between the RDCs will be extended in collaboration with all partners to include non-RDC institutions (D3 Q2/26). This will necessitate the adjustment and review of the technical and organisational measures that must apply in the data security room and at the workplaces. Thereafter, an access terminal will be implemented at a partner university to test remote access connection and to identify gaps in administrative processes.

A suitable cost and pricing model is essential to ensure that the services offered can cover the long-term overhead costs of RDCnet (website, booking platform, administration). This evaluation will be conducted as part of the business model (D4 Q4/27) and will include a legal review of the possibility

of charging for certain services (e.g., physical installation of the work terminals). Once the legal framework has been established, targeted promotion of RDCnet will commence. This will involve advertising RDCnet in online events and on-site at non-RDC institutions. The social media channels of KonsortSWD (cf. M1-4) will also be utilised, and the synergies with the promotion of RDCnet to other potential RDC partners taking place at the same time will be leveraged. This campaign will ensure that the integration of non-RDC institutions can take place as soon as possible (Public campaign to promote RDCnet: D6 Q4/28). A usage and participation report will reflect on the project progress (D7 Q4/28).

M2-5: (A) ProLTA - Promoting Long Term Availability

Profile: ProLTA				Category: Data Curation				
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: RDCs								
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated								
Prop. KPI: Datasets brought into LTA, number of repositories adopting LTA								
Internal Collab.: M2-6, M3-7								
Consortia: -								

Function: The ProLTA service will provide a reference implementation for securing the long-term availability (LTA) of data in interested RDCs and repositories and support the implementation. The improvement of LTA will increase the trustworthiness of RDCs and repositories in line with EOSC's HORIZON-INFRA-2024.

Value Added: ProLTA significantly enhances the quality of data management in RDCs and open data repositories by implementing long-term archiving (LTA) practices into their workflows. This measure ensures the continued reusability of data by mitigating risks associated with technological and institutional changes, which can jeopardise long-term access to valuable research data. The service's relevance lies in its comprehensive approach to LTA, developing a reference implementation based on the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) model that addresses both organisational and technical challenges while defining crucial metadata requirements (esp. DDI-CDI), particularly for quantitative data. By extending KonsortSWD's Open Data Format (M2-6) to include LTA contexts, ProLTA strengthens the overall preservation strategy for various data types, ensuring their accessibility and usability for future research endeavours.

Existing user base: service in development

Work Programme - Summary: The work programme is organised in three major steps that will be integrated into a coherent service at the end of the funding period: (1) The development of a meta-data scheme for LTA applications based on the DDI-CDI standard that was developed to cover all kinds of data types. (2) The integration of the Open Data Format into our reference implementation LTA to overcome the limitations of widely used proprietary formats. (3) The technical and

organisational reference implementation for LTA along the OAIS Reference Model in RDCs and repositories.

Detailed Plan:

Metadata Schema: The first step of our work programme will consist of defining the metadata required for LTA based on the DDI-CDI standard, the CESSDA DDI Profile as well as relevant metadata standards for preservation and interoperability, such as Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies (PREMIS), PROV, or Records in Context (RiC) (M1 Q2/26).

Open Data Format: The metadata schema will feed into the development of the KonsortSWD Open Data format to adapt it to the needs of LTA (M2 Q3/26). In addition, the measure will carry out a proof-of-concept to make sure the metadata schema for LTA meets the needs of LTA for survey data, transcripts of in-depth interviews and other qualitative data types (M3 Q4/26). The results of Milestones 1 to 3 will be summarised in a metadata for LTA report (D1 Q4/26).

Reference implementation for LTA along OAIS model: The measure will start with an international expert workshop on LTA for social science data for preparing the work on practical guidelines (M4 Q1/27). The first practical step is to identify the composition of the different OAIS information packages for LTA (M5 Q2/27) and to provide detailed information on the composition of the information packages for quantitative (M6 Q4/27) and qualitative (M7 Q4/27) data. The work on data-related processes is accompanied by developing a concept of policies required for LTA, especially preservation policies, versioning, deletion, etc. (M8 Q2/28). The next step consists of practical descriptions of workflows and processes (M9 Q2/28). Our preliminary work on LTA in RDCs has shown that data professionals need very specific guidance instead of abstract concepts. The results of Milestones 4 to 9 are summarised into a coherent reference implementation for LTA. We will publish the reference model for quantitative data (D2 Q4/27) and qualitative data (D3 Q2/28) separately to address the demands of our target groups.

Liaison Activities: The measure will liaise with national (NFDI) and international (CESSDA/SSHOC-EU) working groups on LTA and offer three monthly touchpoints with RDCs to receive feedback on the ongoing substantive work. It will recruit pilot users interested in implementing LTA in their RDC/repository and work with them through the different steps of the OAIS model. Towards the end of the funding period, a workshop promoting the LTA reference model for the respective data communities (M10 Q3/28) will be organised. General interest in LTA was expressed by the following RDCs: Qualiservice, DIPF, RWI, DZHW, EBDC@IFO, LIfBi, BAMF, BAuA, DeZIM, Stifterverband, ZPID. The service will also address non-accredited RDCs and repositories (external to the consortium).

Sustainability of the ProLTA service: The consortium members do not believe that a long-term service can be financed by fees for using the reference implementations or metadata schemas. Instead, a sustainable perspective will depend on the ability of the project group to integrate the

~~service into the institutional service portfolios of the project group members (M11 Q4/28). An appropriate business model will be negotiated by October 2027 (as part of D2).~~

M2-56: (I) Open Data Format (ODF)

Profile: Open Data Format						Category: Data Curation		
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals				Section: Metadata				
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated				Partners: SOEP@DIW				
Prop. KPI: Number of dataset provided in ODF by RDCs				Basic Service: PID4NFDI				
Internal Collab.: M2-3, M2-5				Status: Operation / Extension				
Consortia: -				External Collab.: CESSDA, DDI				

Function: The ODF has been developed as a standardised data format that facilitates the FAIR principles in data management, data sharing, and long-term preservation across various platforms and software (Han et al., 2022; Saalbach et al., 2023; Xiaoyao & Saalbach, 2022). This measure aims to further extend the features and applications of ODF by integrating PIDs for metadata and improving the efficiency of import/export filters for large datasets in social science research. It promotes the adoption of ODF within the research community, integrates [DDI-CDI](#), and develops additional import filters for wider software compatibility.

Value Added: The extension will improve the ODF by integrating PIDs for datasets and variables, improving data management, discovery, and long-term archiving (cf. [M2-5](#)) through stable references and enhanced interoperability. This measure is crucial as it addresses the growing need for efficient handling of increasingly larger datasets, ensuring that ODF operates efficiently in most statistical software by leveraging technologies like [Dask](#) for Python and Apache Parquet. Additionally, the integration of the anticipated metadata standard [DDI-CDI](#), which includes provenance information and machine-actionable descriptions of various data types, broadens the applicability of ODF beyond the social sciences.

Existing user base: The first data product ([SOEP-Core v38.1](#) with more than 100k variables) is already available, SOEP-IS 2021 will follow soon. Other partners in KonsortSWD (DZHW, IIfBi, and GESIS) are interested in adopting ODF during the progress of the project.

Work Programme - Summary: In the second phase, PIDs for variables will be integrated ([M2-3](#)). The performance of import/export filters for large datasets will be improved. The existing specification will be improved for long-term archiving and [DDI-CDI](#) will be integrated. RDCs are reached out to and supported with implementation grants. ODF is promoted at conferences. Together with the NFDI community, other platforms - like OctaveGNU/Matlab, Excel, SQL, SPSS, Tableau, Open Refine, Julia or Scala will be supported.

Detailed Plan - Operation: For the second phase, our primary goals are to enhance the metadata specification by incorporating PIDs and to improve the software performance developed in phase one. We aim to integrate PIDs to improve our metadata specification (D1.M1 Q4/25). This integration

will also benefit our collaboration with ProLTA (M2-5), which seeks to facilitate the long-term archival of data. Both projects share a strong interest in establishing ODF as a service for long-term archiving, and we will adapt the metadata specification accordingly (D1.M2 Q1/26). The software supporting the import and export of the ODF will be updated to accommodate the new specification features (D1.M3 Q2/26). We will then address performance improvements, including enhancing the read-and-write functions of the software packages for large datasets (D2.M1 Q3/26), and developing an alternative specification (e.g., Apache Parquet) to csv/xml to ensure an efficient operation with datasets that exceed RAM capacity (D2.M2 Q4/26). The existing software packages will be adapted to accommodate the new specification (D2 Q1/27). Additionally, we will discuss with the community, cooperating with M1-3, the long-term governance of the ODF (D5.M2 Q2/28) as relating to our business model (Q3/27).

~~**Detailed Plan – Extension:** The integration of DDI-CDI will be the main task for the extension of ODF (D3 Q4/27). Therefore, we will discuss with the community regarding the implementation of DDI-CDI in the existing specification (D3.M1 Q2/27) and adapting import/export filters to the new specification (D3. M2 Q2/27) for all software packages (D3.M3 Q3/27). Furthermore, to accommodate the needs of a wider user base in transitioning to Open Science, more software tools such as OctaveGNU/Matlab, Excel, SQL, SPSS, Tableau, Open Refine, Julia, or Scala will be supported for ODF (D4.M1 Q4/26, D4.M2 Q3/28).~~

~~Following these updates of Maintenance and Extension, we will actively promote the use of our tools by reaching out to the RDC community, the relevant sections in NFDI, and data users, assisting them in implementing the ODF, providing our support to RDCs that will adopt ODF (D2.M3 Q1/27, D5.M3 Q3/28). We will gather their feedback to continuously refine and improve the software packages (D5.M1 Q1/28). Finally, we will conduct an evaluation and issue the project report (D5.M4 Q4/28).~~

M2-37: (I) Linking Textual Data

Profile: Linking Textual Data						Category: Tools/Applications		
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers								
DFG KPI: Number of downloads								
Prop. KPI: -								
Internal Collab.: M2-6								
Consortia: Text+								
				Section: -				
				Partners: University of Duisburg-Essen				
				Basic Service: -				
				Status: Operation				
				External Collab.: Clarin, ECPR				

Function: The measure keeps the toolset, services and workflows for linking textual data and structured data as developed in the first-phase-measure Linking Textual Data (LTD) up to date with technical and technological developments in the field of entity linking and broadens usage by community outreach, training, and education, generating conditions for prospective community-driven software development.

Value Added: The toolset adds significant value by linking textual data with structured data, such as survey or administrative data, enabling new analyses in the social and economic sciences. This measure is particularly relevant because it utilises Record Linkage and entity linking techniques to connect curated data hosted by RDCs with unstructured data in the digital realm (RatSWD, 2024a), thereby enhancing research capabilities and fostering integration with broader NFDI developments.

Key deliverables include the R packages DBpedia (entity linking) and LinkTools (Record Linkage), along with data and workflows demonstrating their use. Additionally, a web service ("openCPU") offers enriched textual data via remote access. Extensions for using Knowledge Graphs beyond DBpedia, such as OpenTapioca and entity-fishing, are also included. By integrating the Gemeinsame Normdatei - GND connects KonsortSWD with the consortium Text+ and thus broader NFDI developments.

Existing user base: The toolset, developed as open-source software, can be downloaded from GitHub for local deployment. Tracking downloads and R package installations from GitHub is challenging. However, once released to the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) package repository, robust download numbers will be available. The toolset has been showcased at several workshops. Data prepared within the measure serves as exemplary data and a valuable resource for research, training, and education. The main output, "GermaParl v2," is disseminated via Zenodo. Since its public release on May 23, 2023, GermaParl v2 has been downloaded about 600 times.¹⁹

Work Programme - Summary: The work programme addresses the need to keep tools and workflows for linking textual data to the curated, structured data of the RDCs up to date, accessible and interoperable. This includes the maintenance of the developed toolset as well as the support of the maintenance of resources (DBpedia Spotlight Docker environment, regularly updated models). The measure has three main goals: First, updating the LTD-toolset code base to ensure resource availability and interoperability (on CRAN, rOpenSci). Second, supporting external resources the toolset relies on, including maintaining the Docker deployment of DBpedia Spotlight and updating its models for better performance. Third, enhancing accessibility and application through community outreach and maintaining training materials ("Open Educational Resources"). The long-term future of the open source toolset is to put its development into the hands of an active user base: Community outreach and involvement therefore is a major focus of the project.

Detailed Plan: The work plan focuses on three main goals: (a) maintaining the toolset from the first funding period of "Linking Textual Data" (LTD), (b) supporting the maintenance of related resources like DBpedia and DBpedia Spotlight, and (c) continuous community outreach through training and education to foster a community-driven approach to software development and sustainable service provision. Maintaining the LTD toolset is an ongoing effort throughout the new funding period (M1), with the main deliverable being the continuous provision of up-to-date tools and services for entity

¹⁹ Based on "total downloads" of GermaParl v2.0.0 and GermaParl v2.0.1 (Blaette & Leonhardt, 2023). Numbers last retrieved on April 29, 2024.

linking (D10 Q4/28). Regular updates will also be made to tools like polmineR, RcppCWB, and cwbttools (D5 Q2/27, D8 Q2/28). The measure supports other open-source tools needed by the toolset, focusing on DBpedia Spotlight, including local deployment support (Docker container) and language model updates (D3 Q3/26). These workflows will serve as templates for other entity-linking tools like OpenTapioca and entity-fishing. An active user base will be fostered through a comprehensive outreach strategy, including workshops and events (D1 Q1/26, D2 Q3/26). RDCs will be targeted to create connections between data producers and users. Consolidated Open Educational Resources (D4 Q1/27) will share best practices and ready-to-use data. The toolset will be used to update the GermaParl corpus, showcasing its application to a large dataset (D7 Q1/28, D9 Q3/28). Community involvement is crucial for the measure's business model: an active user base ensures tools are used and maintained. The business model will be reviewed by stakeholders before finalisation (D6 Q4/27). The measure concludes with a final report summarising results (D11 Q4/28).

M2-86: (R) QualidataNet - Qualitative Metadata (DDI)

Profile: QualidataNet - DDI						Category: Data Curation		
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs				Section: Metadata				
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated				Partners: RDC Qualiservice/University of Bremen				
Prop. KPI: Number of document downloads				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: M3-6, M4-8				Status: Development				
Consortia: NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, Text+				External Collab.: SSHOC, ISDFPN, DDI-Alliance				

Function: Extension of the international DDI-CDI model of the DDI-Alliance to provide means for the FAIR description of qualitative research data.

Value Added: The extension of the [DDI-CDI metadata model](#) adds significant value by increasing the reusability of qualitative data across different disciplines, offering a standardized way to represent such data in an interoperable manner. This measure is particularly relevant as it enables researchers from diverse backgrounds to utilize the model for their research questions while providing data providers with a metadata structure that meets the needs of researchers, supports the implementation of research outputs like annotations of audiovisual data, and enhances the FAIRness of qualitative data. Additionally, the measure deepens the connection with [W3C](#) specifications and explores the adoption of DDI-CDI components such as the variable cascade. By engaging with FAIR initiatives led by the RDA and the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF), it supports development of implementation recommendations based on common, domain-independent metadata standards aligned with the core functionality requirements of FAIR.

Work Programme - Summary: To advance FAIRness of qualitative data, QualidataNet and the DDI-Alliance have established an international [working group](#) of infrastructure engineers and researchers. The project team is already part of this group which will extend its scope and collaboratively develop the DDI-CDI metadata model for qualitative data. Planned activities include testing and evaluation of the DDI-CDI model for qualitative data in interdisciplinary use cases, and

formulation of recommendations for the adaptation of the model and its implementation in RDC-infrastructure.

Detailed Plan: In order to increase the FAIRness of qualitative data and to promote its re-use, the provision of FAIR (meta)data is a crucial condition. The work of the measure includes the coordinated further development of the DDI-CDI model for qualitative data within the framework of an already established working group of international players. QualidataNet is responsible for the moderation and planning of the working group, the preparation of templates and the coordination of use cases from different disciplines. After preparing evaluation instruments (M1 Q4/25) and identifying heterogeneous interdisciplinary use cases on which to test the model, the model will be further developed based on the feedback from the test cases and the [W3C](#) standards (M2 Q4/27). Best practices will be identified and solutions for an integrated and standardised cross-disciplinary description of qualitative data will be presented and proposed for integration into the DDI-CDI specification, e.g., as a new module of the model. Finally, a report on the tested use cases and best practice solutions with which the implementation of DDI-CDI would improve the interoperability of qualitative data will be published, and we strive to guide the implementation of these best practices within different communities (D1 Q1/28). This activity is one-off and will not prepare a business plan for sustainability.

5.3 Task Area 3 – Enhancing Competences

TA-Lead: Christian Aßmann, Katarina Blask

Task Area 3 (TA3) bundles, continues, and develops infrastructure for training and consulting in the professional RDM context as well as services that enhance researchers' competencies in managing and accessing research data. This is reflected in the nine measures of TA3 whose efforts aim at addressing aspects of our RDM strategy, improving professionalism of RDM in the target communities, enabling expansion and scaling of RDM related techniques in our communities, and fostering FAIR data.

Contributors: GESIS, DIPF, and ZPID are involved in multiple measures. In addition to measure participation, LIfBi and ZPID are represented through the co-spokespersons. Further measure participation comes from WZB, University of Bremen, DZHW, Archive for Spoken German (AGD), DIW Berlin, eLabour, IQB, DIE, RWI, and AIP.

Objectives & Measures: TA3 addresses several key objectives, including expanding RDM competences (O2), smoothing the usability of infrastructure by automating and standardising RDM (O3), presenting and explaining services to researchers with RDM needs (O4), establishing a sustainable business model (O5), and strengthening connections with other domains (O8). To a lesser extent, TA3 contributes to objective O1 by making new qualitative data sources available.

To achieve these objectives, TA3 will implement various measures, including RDM Compas (M3-7), interlocking with competence-related activities (M3-1), and operating a nationwide helpdesk (M3-5)

in cooperation with Forum4MICA (M3-4), VerbundFDB (M3-9), and QualidataNet (M3-6). Additionally, TA3 will standardise and integrate requirements of different disciplines through Stamp and FAIR-RDM (M3-8) and support harmonisation of RDM with qualitative data through QualidataNet (M3-6). TA3 will also establish KonsortSWD as a known and reliable source for RDM services, particularly for early career researchers and third-party funded projects (M3-2, M3-5, M3-4, M3-9). Measures are sorted alphabetically.

Furthermore, TA3 will strategically partner with other consortia, such as GHGA, BERD@NFDI, and NFDI4Memory, to promote mutual benefit and facilitate the integration of basic services as well as the re-use of qualitative data through QualidataNet (M3-6).

Risks: Main risks of development and implementation relate to funding cuts and delays in staffing the workforce arising possibly from non-competitive salaries and retaining staff under the conditions of project funding, thus not being able to implement the work programme in the scope intended, and in the available time. Furthermore, target groups not participating in the offered training constitutes another risk of implementation. To mitigate the risks, we conduct continuous risk assessments and hold regular workshops to keep the team updated on technologies and best practices.

Cooperation: TA3 cooperates closely with TA1 to promote the events and services among our target groups and will work with TA5 to develop sustainable business models for the services. Several of the measures cooperate with QualidataNet spanning TA2 to TA4 and thus directly connects to all other TAs. Moreover, single measures from TA3 cooperate with RDCnet (M2-4), Findability of Services and Data (M2-2), ProLTA - Promoting Long-term archiving (M2-5) in TA2, and with Contract Templates (M4-2) and Firm Data (M4-6) in TA4.

Conclusion: TA3 is strongly connected within KonsortSWD, where the measure bundle of TA3 is chosen to ensure strongest connections within the TA to build a coherent infrastructure for training and consulting in the professional RDM context as well as services that enhance researchers' competencies in managing and accessing research data.

M3-1: ASSURED

Profile: ASSURED							Category: Training	
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals				Section: ELSA, EduTrain				
DFG KPI: Number of training activities				Partners: DKFZ, GESIS, LMU				
Prop. KPI: Number of registered users				Basic Service: IAM4NFDI				
Internal Collab.: M3-7				Status: Development				
Consortia: GHGA, BERD@NFDI				External Collab.: University of West of England, CESSDA, EOSC-ENTRUST, ODISSEI, ISDFPN				

Function: ASSURED (Accrediting Safe Use of Research Environments) facilitates “safe research by safe people” by providing an e-learning and accreditation program covering topics such as data protection and statistical disclosure for users of sensitive data and professionals working in data governance roles.

Internal Collab.: KonsortSWD: M1-3, M3-1, M3-7, all other measures comprising training modules

Status: Operation

Consortia: -

External Collab.: Graduate schools, Research Training Groups, Clusters of Excellence

Function: The measure contributes to RDM capacity building among early career researchers by bundling existing training formats, heightening their profile, and making them sustainably available and easily accessible.

Value Added: Training early career researchers builds the foundation for their future research and teaching, sensitising them to the importance of RDM topics early in their academic careers. This measure is particularly relevant as it fosters a common understanding that RDM is important and improves competencies among this target group. By integrating existing training materials, such as tutorials and webinars in collaboration with RDM Compas (M3-7), and the Meet-the-Data series, it provides RDM professionals, and those training early career researchers with access to target group specific resources. Additionally, outreach initiatives will be expanded through KonsortSWD and NFDI channels, offering valuable opportunities for smaller or regional training initiatives to benefit from these resources.

Existing user base: Early career researchers

Work Programme - Summary: Reaching early career researchers has proven to be more difficult in the first funding phase - e.g., in the context of a [call for RDM contributions](#) amongst doctoral candidates. This measure will therefore offer customised support by integrating existing training information as mentioned above. Initially targeting doctoral candidates in structured programs, we also plan to reach predoctoral researchers and early postdocs through suitable intermediaries and events.

Detailed plan: The measure adds RDM training and informative resources targeting early career researchers to KonsortSWD. It assesses their needs, consolidates existing tools, and creates new ones if needed, promoting visibility and making tools available to target communities.

Training Material Placement: We will provide RDM training material to those educating early career researchers. This includes RDM professionals or data stewards at universities (of applied sciences), non-university institutions, and those responsible for training early career researchers at disciplinary related graduate schools or centres, Research Training Groups (Graduierkollegs), Clusters of Excellence, or Workshops for Early Career Investigators (Nachwuchsakademien). We will closely cooperate with RDM Compas (M3-7), with other measures providing training material as well as the platform [forschungsdaten.info](#), which also provides broad information on RDM topics. A concept for training material placement is due in Q234/265.

Meet-the-Data: Launched in autumn 2023 in cooperation with the German Network of Educational Research Data (VerbundFDB), this monthly lunch lecture series introduces datasets to researchers and students. Attended by 226 participants up to July 2024, we will further develop and

institutionalise the series, presenting new datasets and deepening PR activities in cooperation with M1-4. The aim is to directly reach out to people at universities who teach empirical methods in order for them to advertise the lecture series in their own lectures. The series will take place six to nine times a year in cooperation with the Coordination Office (CoO, M5-2) and VerbundFDB (M3-9).

Specifying Community: We will establish and maintain contacts at graduate schools and centres, Research Training Groups, Clusters of Excellence, or Workshops for Early Career Investigators to promote the Meet-the-Data series and other KonsortSWD services to early career researchers.

Matchmaking: As far as resources allow, wWe will support coordinators of graduate institutions and RDM professionals in identifying suitable methodological or RDM training content for graduate programs, facilitating one-to-one dialogues to obtain necessary material and tools. So far, we have identified the following partners for cooperation: the DFG-funded project FDLINK, the CESSDA Training Working Group, the TH Köln (certificate course in RDM), the Junge Akademie, the German University Association of Advanced Graduate Training (UniWiND/GUAT), and the AK Forschungsdaten of the Leibniz Gemeinschaft. A matchmaking concept will be delivered by Q4/26.

M3-3: ELSA – Contact person for data protection

Profile: ELSA - Contact person for data protection					Category: Support/Consulting			
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals					Section: ELSA, TF Data Protection			
DFG KPI: -					Partners: LIfBi			
Prop. KPI: Number of meetings or consultations					Basic Service: -			
Internal Collab.: M3-5					Status: Operation			
Consortia: All present on task force (~14)					External Collab.: -			

Function: The measure handles current data protection issues in the context of RDM. Its aim is to support research-friendly best practice solutions in this field – based on an interdisciplinary exchange in NFDI Section ELSA.

Value Added: Contribute KonsortSWD’s specific know-how in this field to “OneNFDI” and facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration by co-leading Task Force (TF) Data Protection together with BERD@NFDI, develop and publish best practices for data protection issues.

Existing user base: Users represented by consortia working on NFDI’s TF Data Protection in Section ELSA

Work Programme - Summary: KonsortSWD’s partners have substantial knowledge and experience relating to data protection, including identifying practical and research-friendly solutions. This measure contributes this knowledge to NFDI and supports knowledge transfer in terms of exchange and best practice outputs.

Detailed Plan: As part of the lead-team of TF Data protection, this measure co-organizes meetings and participants in setting the TF’s agenda and strategic plans and the documentation of progress towards results (ongoing activity). It contributes specific expertise on how the FAIR Principles can

be realised in compliance with data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In this context, contributions are focussed on four topics the task force has identified: a) Reusability through Pseudonymisation and Aggregation, b) Data and Record Linkage in compliance with Data Protection Regulations, c) Metadata in compliance with Data Protection Regulations, and d) Informed Consent and FAIR principles. Deliverables are tied to progress in the TF and include a community workshop (Q3/26) as well as best-practice recommendations (ongoing). A report or working paper on FAIR Principles and Data Protection will be published (Q4/28). Moreover, work and expertise of the measure and the contact person for data protection contribute to other aspects of KonsortSWD's work. Links will exist throughout the TA and to the Helpdesk (M3-5).

M3-4: Forum4MICA: Online Exchange Platform on Research Data Issues

Profile: Forum4MICA						Category: Support/Consulting		
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals				Section: -				
DFG KPI: -				Partners: LIfBi				
Prop. KPI: Number of unique user visits				Basic Service: IAM4NFDI				
Internal Collab.: M1-2, M3-5, M3-6, M3-9				Status: Operation/Extension				
Consortia: -				External Collab.: GesundFDM				

Function: Forum4MICA is a user-driven online discussion platform for exchanging knowledge on research data provided by RDCs and RDM topics in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. It already functions as a dynamically growing knowledge archive. The forum will continue expanding its user and topic base, and be enhanced with new functionalities and partners or links within and beyond KonsortSWD.

Value Added: Forum4MICA adds significant value by introducing a dynamic and transparent approach to traditional data documentation from RDCs, enabling researchers to actively engage with experts, foster dialogue, and present their own solutions. This measure is particularly relevant as it addresses the need for a more interactive and problem-centred platform, as demonstrated by the successful establishment of Forum4MICA in the first funding phase. The proposed extensions for the second phase aim to improve user-friendliness and broaden the application of Forum4MICA, including international access. Enhanced search options, an expanded reward system for participation, and collaboration with new partners in diverse thematic areas will also be added, creating a supportive and technically stable service that grows through increased use.

Existing user base: By 1 June 2024, 18 RDCs had committed to an active partnership in Forum4MICA. Since February 2023, 175 new participants registered, 581 posts were written and there were more than 1,500 unique visits by registered users. Demand and use are expected to grow with intensified publicity strategies.

Work Programme - Summary: Key tasks for maintaining the high-quality operation of Forum4MICA include moderation, administration, first-level support, and technical maintenance. Service extension involves the implementation of new functionalities and the integration of additional partners, aiming to attract a larger user base and establish it as a reliable, growing knowledge archive on research data management.

Detailed Plan - Operation: Experience since Forum4MICA's launch shows the importance of regular and personal exchanges with participating and potential partners and explicit inclusion of feedback from the scientific community. Following the bottom-up approach of NFDI, semi-annual workshops with stakeholders from the RDCs and RDM landscape (Q4/25; Q2 & Q4/26-2028) and biennial online surveys among registered forum participants (Q3/26 & 2028) are planned. Reports on user surveys and on user development will be published in Q4/26 and Q4/28. Another key aspect of service operation is the central administration and moderation of the forum. Consistently structuring content to make information easy to find, ensuring prompt responses, assigning and maintaining different user authorisations, and protecting the system against misuse and violations of the terms of use, are elementary tasks to ensure user-friendliness and integrity. Equally essential is the technical maintenance of the software, involving testing updates on a developer platform before a yearly system relaunch (Q1/26, 2027, 2028) to avoid any application problems or system failures during operation.

Detailed Plan - Extension: Supplementing the functional scope of the platform, tasks include adding a translation tool (Q4/25), a calendar and event tool (Q2/27) and an area for the provision and discussion of analysis syntaxes (Q3/28). Technical enhancements involve optimising the findability of the service on the internet with SEO measures to be implemented in Q4/26, and facilitating registration through a broader identity and access management (IAM) connection. For improved IAM, possibilities to integrate NFDI basic service IAM4NFDI with Forum4MICA will be evaluated in a trial of the extended IAM system (Q4/27). To increase the attractiveness of active participation in Forum4MICA, the non-monetary incentive system is to be extended by Q1/28. With the implementation of multilingualism, the basis for further efforts to strengthen the internationalisation of the forum is given, including a workshop with international research data infrastructures in Q2/28. Other events are scheduled with QualidataNet (M3-6) to integrate a discourse on qualitative research data and its re-use (Q1/26) as well as with experts on the utilisation of suitable AI tools (Q1/27). An FAQ section from the KonsortSWD Helpdesk (M3-5) will be added in Q3/26. Besides the work on the forum itself, presentations at scientific conferences like the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI) (Q3/27) as well as reports such as a "best-practice" manual for setting up a platform like Forum4MICA (Q4/26) and a paper on findings from concomitant research on the use of this service (Q4/28) will be prepared and published. A business model for sustainable operation of the forum beyond the funding phase will be developed by Q4/27. All extension steps of Forum4MICA are based on experiences since its launch and are closely coordinated with service operation tasks.

M3-5: Helpdesk KonsortSWD

Profile: Helpdesk KonsortSWD					Category: Support/Consulting			
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals				Section: NFDI Working Group Helpdesks				
DFG KPI: Number of user consultations				Partners: DIPF, GWDG				
Prop. KPI: Number of incoming processed tickets				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: All measures and RDCs				Status: Operation				
Consortia: Helpdesks of consortia				External Collab.: Specialised Information Services, German federal state RDM initiatives				

Function: KonsortSWD’s helpdesk is a central contact point offering support and guidance on RDM best practices, including data management planning. It processes and responds to incoming queries, connects users with relevant RDM experts, and develops a comprehensive RDM knowledge base to support the user-oriented expansion of KonsortSWD's services.

Value Added: The KonsortSWD helpdesk adds significant value by assisting researchers, infrastructure practitioners, and other users in effectively navigating the portfolio of KonsortSWD services, ensuring they have access to essential expertise in data production, management, access, reuse, and archiving. This measure is relevant as it addresses the need for a support system that can provide expert guidance and facilitate knowledge exchange between stakeholders, ultimately enhancing the overall RDM support for the research community. The helpdesk's systematic analysis of incoming queries and inter-consortial helpdesk exchange also promote evidence-based development of KonsortSWD services and cross-consortium collaboration.

Existing user base: Service in development

Work Programme - Summary: The helpdesk, launched in late 2024, solidifies its role as the central point of contact for KonsortSWD services in the second funding period through five actions. It coordinates ticket processing (A1), establishes an interactive knowledge base in Forum4MICA (A2), expands its expert network (A3), informs need-based development (A4), interacts with NFDI and implements dissemination (A5).

Detailed Plan:

(A1) Ticket Processing: Incoming tickets will be processed and answered directly if possible or forwarded to the experts in KonsortSWD’s network, using a GWDG-hosted ticket system. A monitoring process will be established that includes the recording of inquiries for evaluation. By analysing the requests, the helpdesk service can be continuously evaluated and improved (recurring deliverable with analyses carried out in Q2/26-28), with analyses published in Q4/27.

(A2) Knowledge Base in Forum4MICA: The helpdesk will address RDM questions in Forum4MICA, publishing selected queries as FAQs starting Q3/26 in order to create an interactive knowledge base on RDM for the community. Content will be updated regularly (updates in Q3/27 and 28).

(A3) Expert Network: The expert network will be expanded, establishing best practices in RDM counselling. The starting point is a survey among the experts involved on the prototype structures and processes (Q1/26). In addition, internal FAQs for experts will be implemented in Q2/26 and regularly updated for consultation purposes in Q2/27 and Q2/28. Processes and quality assurance of the helpdesk service are continuously optimised in collaboration with the experts and partners involved, e.g., via expert and partner network meetings in Q2/26-28.

(A4) Need-Based Development: The evaluation of consultation requests is also used for reporting to the Coordination Office (M5-2) and other relevant actors (e.g., FDI Committee) aiding in the development of KonsortSWD services. Reports are scheduled for Q3/26-28. This includes cooperation with other measures like RDM Compas (M3-7), Stamp (M3-8) or Forum4MICA (M3-4).

(A5) Dissemination, Sustainability, and NFDI Integration: Helpdesk PR is supported by the Communication and Public Relations Office (M1-4). The helpdesk will be represented at relevant infrastructure conferences (Q1/26, Q3/27) in order to further expand the network of experts and partners. It participates in networking initiatives and is actively involved in the NFDI Tools and Helpdesk Taskforce (Overview helpdesks). The helpdesk will exchange with infrastructures such as existing helpdesks in other consortia, federal state RDM initiatives and scientific institutions to reflect on and improve processes. A long-term business model will be developed with KonsortSWD, the IT partner GWDG, and DIPF (Q3/27).

M3-6: QualidataNet – RDM and Re-Use of Qualitative Data

Profile: QualidataNet - RDM and re-use of qualitative data				Category: Support/Consulting, Data Curation				
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs								
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated								
Prop. KPI: Number of visits								
Internal Collab.: M2-8, M3-9, M4-8								
Consortia: NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, Text+								

Function: Coordinated by the RDCs and archives of QualidataNet, this service consolidates and expands a common, professional RDM portfolio tailored to qualitative research (Gebel et al., 2021; Gebel & Meyermann, 2021; Hollstein, 2021; Mozygamba et al., 2023). It ensures high data quality, community involvement, and FAIRness of qualitative datasets while optimising the re-use potential of qualitative data. To further promote re-use of qualitative data, researchers' needs, and existing solutions are systematically collected, and re-use scenarios, best practices, and examples from research and teaching are prepared in cooperation with researchers and communicated to aid secondary use.

Value Added: Firstly, the measure offers a sustainable, centrally accessible FAIR RDM service for sensitive qualitative data, providing researchers with tools and guidance for sharing qualitative (less

structured, typically personal) research data. It addresses discipline-specific and data type-specific needs, essential for acceptance in qualitative communities. The service helps researchers prepare data for optimal re-use, maintaining a portfolio that adapts to evolving qualitative research requirements, including technical, ethical, and legal aspects. Coordination among QualidataNet RDCs (M4-8) fosters synergies, prevents duplication, and enhances cost efficiency. Secondly, the measure provides re-use scenarios and best practices for qualitative data, filling a gap in examples of data re-use. Unlike quantitative data, qualitative data re-use is nascent and not very visible. Currently, there is no platform providing examples of re-use scenarios and best practices for secondary analysis of qualitative data or facilitating user exchange, despite significant demand for practical solutions and examples of data sharing and secondary research revealed by needs analyses. This measure addresses these gaps, integrating insights into methodological training to refine portfolio development and data curation strategies.

Existing user base: The QualidataNet website was launched in December 2023. Since January 2024, researchers have been requesting advice via the contact form or by e-mail.

Work Programme - Summary: Planned activities include maintaining and developing the RDM portfolio (tools, services) for the adequate preparation of qualitative data to establish standards and to optimise their FAIRness. These activities involve collaboration with qualitative communities from different disciplines, dissemination and implementation of the RDM portfolio in user events and at conferences and translation of community needs into further advancement. In close cooperation with researchers, scenarios and best practices for qualitative data re-use will be developed and shared to promote data re-use. Activities also include evaluation of re-uses and application potentials, the development of a systematic overview of qualitative secondary analyses, the identification of best practices and practical challenges for secondary use of qualitative data and their dissemination via publications, workshops, and Forum4MICA.

Detailed Plan: The measure expands and improves the common core portfolio of professional RDM tailored to qualitative research data developed during the first funding phase of KonsortSWD. It will publish results on qualitative data documentation and contextualisation in a paper (Q2/28). The long-term goal is for researchers to use already developed data curation instruments during research, allowing subsequent curation at the RDCs to begin without delay. The portfolio will be supported by research-focused user training (Q2/26). Forum4MICA (M3-4) will serve as an additional communication channel to researchers, where we provide the RDM-portfolio and related RDM-consulting services (Q2/26); referencing outputs on RDM Compas (M3-7) will help reach data stewards as target group. To promote the secondary use of qualitative data and to increase its FAIRness, QualidataNet will work with researchers from different disciplines to evaluate the state-of-the-art with respect to the re-use of qualitative data, their experiences, possible solutions and needs. This involves qualitative researchers from consortia like Text+, NFDI4Culture, and NFDI4Memory. The status quo evaluation is supplemented by a systematic review (published Q4/27) of internationally published secondary analysis studies reflecting methodological approaches as well

Work Programme - Summary: The information and training offered along the data curation cycle will be updated and expanded regularly through continuously monitoring the professional landscape and new developments in terms of methods and data types. Generic information created in the first phase of RDM Compass will be more tightly tailored to social science needs. User studies will guide content disseminating beyond social sciences, and data stewards will be trained ~~as coaches~~ for quality assured RDM implementation.

Detailed Plan - Operation: This measure keeps information in the knowledge base and trainings on the training platform up-to-date, adding new content, e.g., from other measures within KonsortSWD and NFDI (Q4/25-28). In the context of KonsortSWD, collaborations include 1) the ProLTA service (M2-5) that will provide solutions for the long-term availability (LTA) of data in RDCs and repositories, 2) QualidataNet Re-use aimed at promoting re-use of qualitative data (M3-6), 3) ASSURED (M3-1), a measure targeted at implementing an e-learning programme enabling researchers and RDM professionals secure handling of sensitive research data, and 4) Stamp and FAIR-RDM (M3-8) aimed at increasing the (re)useability of the Stamp. At the NFDI level, an important aspect will be indexing training materials in the Data Literacy Alliance (DALIA) annually (Q4/25-28) and interacting with section EduTrain. On a technical basis, RDM Compass will be regularly updated to provide an error-free, secure and performant platform (regular milestone in Q3 of every year). Also, a sustainable operation model will be developed by Q3/27.

Detailed Plan - Extension: RDM Compass supports sustainable and future-proof RDM by a) fostering skills development through the first central learning and training platform for data curators, data stewards, and other RDM professionals, and b) responding to new curation needs within the community by, for instance, including new data types in RDM Compass, ~~and c) supporting RDM professionals in their role as RDM coaches~~. These actions are aimed at comprehensively aligning the service with the needs of the community and expanding the platform's influence on the work processes at the RDCs and beyond. We are expanding our scope to include a broader range of RDM professionals, like data curators, consultants, and trainers. The measure starts with an extension of the knowledge base and training platform in two directions. On the one hand, covering all social science disciplines and including RDM professionals offering RDM consulting to social science researchers. Key deliverables include 1) publications and presentations on conferences as well as informational events within the NFDI community on data curation differences in the social science disciplines (Q3/26-28) and 2) a correspondingly adapted content and structure of the knowledge base (Q2/276) and training platform (Q3/276), ~~and~~ 3) the development and evaluation of trainings with members of the relevant target groups (Q2/28), and 4) a publication describing the platform and relevant usage scenarios (Q4/28). ~~A coaching program for data stewards in their role as process facilitators (building on existing concepts) in the generation of quality-assured data curation solutions tailored to the individual requirements of each research project will be created. It is based on the implementation of a coaching concept for data curators and other RDM professionals (Q2/28), a report on the coaching programme (Q4/28) and publication of the programme via the~~

needs of the respective discipline. The current use of Stamp shows that it is well-suited to the needs of educational research. Stamp (Version 0.9) has been available for download via the website of the VerbundFDB since March 2023. Until the end of 2023, we had almost 1,700 visits to the website and 469 downloads. Version 1.0 has been available since February 2024. Stamp has already been introduced to an interested audience of over 200 persons from various NFDI consortia (Künstler-Sment et al., 2023, 2023; Netscher et al., 2022a, 2022b). This broad interest highlights the potential for cross-disciplinary application of the Stamp.

Work Programme - Summary: To implement a KonsortSWD-service on RDM, the Stamp 1.0 will be evaluated and adapted to design Stamp 2.0, integrating into online applications (RDMO and DataWiz 2), an XML version will be created and assisting materials will be incorporated into RDM Compas. A business model will be established considering further NFDI approaches and RDM developments.

Detailed Plan: The measure has three actions:

(A1) Evaluate Requirements: By Q1/26, evaluate requirements of the disciplines addressed by KonsortSWD to adapt Stamp 1.0 for Stamp 2.0. Previously, Stamp 1.0 was developed for educational research e.g., regarding the types of data employed, such as survey data, interviews, observations etc., and the sometimes highly sensitive research population, such as children or teenagers. In 2022 and 2023, preparations have been made to extend Stamp 1.0 to sociology and political science. In total, KonsortSWD funded four workshops to examine and discuss the usability of the Stamp beyond educational research with researchers, data stewards and data curators. Building on these preliminary steps, the Stamp 1.0 will be adapted to create Stamp 2.0. Adaptations will cover KonsortSWD disciplines, with assisting materials created by Q3/26 to promote the use of the Stamp 2.0 and researchers' RDM. Activities will be coordinated with RDM Compas (M3-7).

(A2) Technical Integration: First, update and extend Stamp 1.0 in RDMO to Stamp 2.0 by Q2/27, enabling researchers and RDM-consultants to submit their structured DMPs online. Second, integrate Stamp 2.0 and its materials into RDM Compas by Q3/27, fostering low-threshold accessibility and usage of the Stamp. Third, integrate Stamp 2.0 into DataWiz ²¹ as an alternative online application by Q4/27, to further foster online usability of the Stamp 2.0. Fourth, create an XML version of Stamp 2.0 by Q2/27 for use in additional applications.

(A3) Sustainability and Integration: Action 3 (own contribution) focuses on sustainability and integration of the KonsortSWD-service on RDM in the NFDI and beyond. We will develop a business model for Stamp 2.0's long-term operation and its various implementations in online applications by Q3/27. Moreover, we follow ongoing RDM developments (in the NFDI) and integrate the new KonsortSWD-service into other NFDI approaches, e.g., Base4NFDI. Among others, action 3 relates to DMP4NFDI). This will ensure that the Stamp is integrated into the NFDI-wide service as the

²¹ <https://datawiz2.dev.zpid.de>, under development. User base of DataWiz 1.0: 870 unique users (as of July, 01 2024).

standardised, machine-readable, and interoperable DMP template for the disciplines addressed by KonsortSWD.

M3-9: VerbundFDB – Network of Educational Research Data

Profile: VerbundFDB				Category: Database, Support/Consulting, Training				
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, Data professionals								
DFG KPI: Number of visits								
Prop. KPI: -								
Internal Collab.: M2-5, M3-2, M3-5, M3-7, M3-8, M4-2, M4-8								
Consortia: -								
				Section: -				
				Partners: DIPF, DIE, DJI, DZHW, GESIS, GU, IQB, Qualiservice, ZPID				
				Basic Service: -				
				Status: Operation				
				External Collab.: Specialised Information Service Education; professional associations in educational sciences (GEBF, DGfE, GfD)				

Function: VerbundFDB is a permanently funded infrastructure providing data for educational research. It includes a comprehensive search for educational research data, a federated archiving workflow, as well as consulting, information, and training services for research data management. Through this measure, VerbundFDB intensifies its close cooperation with KonsortSWD and NFDI.

Value Added: Closer cooperation between VerbundFDB and KonsortSWD will increase usability for researchers and help integrate processes. This connection enhances a coherent external presentation and increases the findability of data services for researchers. By collaborating more closely with VerbundFDB, KonsortSWD can expand its reach in educational research communities. Additionally, both networks can capitalise on synergy effects. For example, VerbundFDB will support tasks relating to educational research in the KonsortSWD Helpdesk, RDM Compas, and Stamp and FAIR RDM. An example of successful cooperation is the monthly [Meet-the-Data](#) series that is jointly organised by VerbundFDB and KonsortSWD. Moreover, VerbundFDB offers specialised expertise and services for the creation, management, and archiving of niche and less common research data. Overall, the integration of VerbundFDB will strengthen KonsortSWD's portfolio in the field of RDM support and training, and in the field of data sharing for small projects (RatSWD, 2023c).

Existing user base: Usage figures show a high and growing impact over the past years: number of website visits (2023: 79,041), number of users of the data search (2023: 7,835), number of data listed in the data search (2023: 876) number of data uploads (2023: 34), number of consultation requests (2023: 92), and active use of RDM materials, webinars and podcasts.

Work Programme - Summary: VerbundFDB will use its links to KonsortSWD and NFDI to deepen existing connections and identify further collaboration areas, such as federated data archiving. Additionally, it will support educational research tasks in other KonsortSWD services such as Helpdesk, RDM Compas, Stamp and FAIR RDM, and the Meet-the-Data series, coordinate public relations measures, and enhance service interlinking.

Detailed Plan: This measure contributes with three actions to the success of KonsortSWD.

(A1) Coordinate PR and Outreach: VerbundFDB will align its PR, outreach, and networking activities in close cooperation with the Coordination Office (M5-2), Community involvement measure (M3-2), and the Public Relations Office (M1-4) (Action 1), ensuring regular exchanges by Q2/26. This has already started successfully with regard to the jointly organised Meet-the-Data series.

(A2) RDC Network Meetings ~~Exchange Forum~~ Coordination: VerbundFDB will manage its established RDC (monthly) network meetings ~~exchange forum~~ and corresponding working groups. In the ~~network~~forum, partners work closely together to improve services for RDM for educational data. Working groups work on topics such as automatization of ingest practices, log data, or data anonymisation. VerbundFDB will interlink its contributions with KonsortSWD, so that they can act as incubators like Stamp (M3-8), for example, already has.

(A3) Operate Data Infrastructure: VerbundFDB will maintain the data infrastructure for educational researchers through its portal forschungsdaten-bildung.de as a central point of contact. Infrastructure services include data search, federated data archiving, and RDM support. Service offers will also be advertised through KonsortSWD and NFDI channels.

5.4 Task Area 4 – Integrating Data

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Task Area 4 "Integrating Data" (TA4) focuses on developing and implementing innovative technologies and methods for the integration, anonymisation, and harmonisation of data. These initiatives are crucial for improving data quality and ensuring secure access to important datasets. The primary goal is to facilitate comprehensive and seamless data integration, thereby enhancing scientific research and evidence-based decision-making through high-quality, accessible, and secured datasets.

Contributors: Both KIT and SOEP/DIW Berlin are involved in measures and jointly represent the role of co-spokespersons in TA4. In addition, other measure participation comes from IAB, DRV, DZHW, Destatis, BAMF, RWI, ifo, University of Bremen, and GESIS. Other contributors recur in their established roles: DIPF, FDZ-BO, IDS and eLabour to offer their expertise.

Objectives & Measures: TA4 aligns with five key KonsortSWD objectives: expanding data access (O1), automating and standardising RDM (O3), assuring reliability of services (O6), learning through collaborations (O8), and in particular, linking data across domains (O9).

To achieve these objectives, TA4 will implement nine targeted measures. These measures include providing centralised access to specific disciplines or data types through QualidataNet (M4-8), FirmData (M4-6), and FDZMoL (M4-5), as well as offering standardised contract templates (M4-2) and automating anonymisation and output control (M4-4). Additionally, TA4 will develop a framework for direct data linking (M4-7), link social security data through BASiD (M4-1), enhance the crises-related data platform (M4-3), and support standardised sociodemographic measurement through StanDem (M4-9). By advancing data integration, TA4 aims to provide researchers with high-quality,

well-curated data, ultimately supporting robust scientific inquiry and thus indirectly policymaking. Below, measures are sorted alphabetically.

Risks: While TA4 aims to enhance data integration and accessibility, several risks must be addressed. One major risk is the potential for reduction in the requested funding, which could hinder development and implementation. Additionally, recruiting and retaining skilled personnel under project-based financing is challenging, especially in a competitive job market for data scientists and IT professionals, potentially impacting project continuity and success.

On a technical level, the complexity of automating anonymisation processes and ensuring secure data linking involves inherent risks. Technical failures or delays in these areas could compromise the overall objectives of TA4. To mitigate these risks, we have continuous risk assessments. Implementing regular workshops within the Task Area can help keep the team updated on the latest technologies and best practices. For example, to prevent incomplete data integration due to varied formats, we provide comprehensive training for data providers (M4-4). To address firms' data privacy concerns, we establish strong data privacy protocols and offer clear communication about security measures (M4-6). To overcome technical difficulties in providing remote access, we invest in robust IT infrastructure and offer continuous technical support (M4-5). To improve limited access to social security data despite bureaucratic hurdles, we partner with government agencies and streamline access procedures (M4-1 and M4-3).

Cooperation: We will work with TA1 to involve the community, in particular planned events and surveys. TA4 also cooperates with TA5 to incorporate the possibilities of business models for consolidated services. There is a connection to TA2 and TA3, as the QualidataNet framework is represented with measures in all of the three Task Areas from TA2 to TA4. Especially for providing FAIR access to integrated data, we cooperate with TA2.

Conclusion: While TA4 presents various challenges, targeted solutions, and proactive risk management strategies can effectively mitigate these risks, ensuring successful data integration and accessibility.

M4-1: BASiD – Administrative Data Linkage for Research and Policy Advice

Profile: BASiD				Category: Data Curation				
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs				Section: -				
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated				Partners: BA, DRV, IAB				
Prop. KPI: Number of users of datasets				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: -				Status: Development				
Consortia: BERD@NFDI, NFDI4Health (planned)				External Collab.: SHARE, Public Employment Services				

~~**Function:** This project aims to link social security data from different sources to create a comprehensive and extensible administrative dataset for the international research community,~~

enabling research on the life course of socially insured people in Germany and on public policy evaluations. This project can serve as a blueprint for future linkage opportunities.

Value Added: The proposed project adds substantial value by developing a harmonised multi-purpose research data product that combines invaluable administrative datasets from the Statutory Pension Insurance (DRV) and the Federal Employment Agency (BA), significantly enhancing research quality and enabling diverse research projects simultaneously. The best sources for research on employment, social security in old age, and unemployment are provided by the DRV and the BA. However, both lack information the other could deliver. For example, data from the Institute for Employment Research (IAB) lacks details on fertility, care duties, or divorce, while DRV data lacks information on job search and work environment. A combined, harmonised dataset will enhance insights into human behaviour, social dynamics, and policy impact, providing evidence-based information for policymakers, practitioners, and other stakeholders. This measures' final dataset will provide cleaned data with German and English documentation, enabling easily reproducible and comparable results with less time expenditure compared to individually linked datasets. The proposed data product renews the linkage of confidential social insurance data, similar to the existing dataset BASiD 2008 "Biographical Data of Selected Insurance Agencies in Germany" (Hochfellner et al., 2011). It includes a 1% representative sample of the DRV population and is enriched with administrative data from the Federal Employment Agency (BA) provided by the IAB. BASiD has been widely used in numerous national and international research projects. The new project will build on this successful linkage of administrative data in a future-oriented and sustainable way by increasing the sample size to 2% (1.4 million insured persons). Other social insurance institutions can contribute their data to close knowledge gaps, and harmonisation scripts will enable future linkage projects to join BASiD.

Existing user base: Until mid-2024, 103 researchers from 56 projects have used BASiD at IAB. Additionally, 164 researchers in 66 international research projects used the scientific-use file published by DRV. Researchers from institutions such as London School of Economics, University of Michigan, Oxford, Stanford, and Stockholm Universities have applied for BASiD. The international outreach will likely grow through this measure's expanded data access points and improving remote data access at RDCs.

Work Programme – Summary: The project starts with conceptual work to harmonise data between the two major social insurances, as they store data differently. A second step includes data pre-processing, linkage, and creating standardised routines for periodic updates. Additionally, standard contracts for collaborating institutions and standardised programming routines for periodic updates will be implemented.

Detailed Plan: The project starts after the completion of preparatory works, such as cooperation contracts, exchange with data protection officers, data preparation, and data access between the cooperation partners. This is planned for late 2025 and early 2026. 2026 also includes population sampling, data linkage on individual level, harmonisation of parallel events like employment and care

work, and the creation of a first linked dataset. In addition, the PhD students involved in the project start their empirical work with a research question to verify the harmonisation of the linked data. The second year, 2027, focuses on four modules. Firstly, a concept of sustainability of the data product in terms of expansion and periodic updates, independent of funding. The second module is a concept for extension to other social security institutions such as accident insurance or health insurances (in cooperation with NFDI4Health). The third module will focus on test projects with researchers, which will be open to different disciplines within and outside NFDI. Fourthly, the PhD students will present their own work at conferences, and the project team will promote the upcoming data product at various events, concentrated in the research community and the European social security infrastructure as well as interested NFDI consortia, CESSDA and networks like the International Data Access Network. As a result of these modules, a business model for periodic updates of BASiD and linked data components will be established (Q4/27). The third year, 2028, will focus on feedback from the test projects through community workshops (Q2/28), updating the data documentation, and releasing the data in line with the FAIR principles to the international research community (Q3/28).

M4-3: CrisesData – Establishing Infrastructures for Rapid Responses in Societal Crises

Profile: CrisesData							Category: Databases	
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers								
DFG KPI: Number of visits								
Prop. KPI: Number of downloads of survey instruments; number of cooperation partners								
Internal Collab.: M1-1, M4-9								
Consortia: NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Health								

Function: The project, which has been funded through the consortium’s network development grants since December 2023, (1) facilitates the access to crisis-related data from different scientific disciplines and non-academic contexts, (2) provides a collection of tested, crisis-related survey instruments, and (3) establishes a structure to enable the coordination between researchers, practitioners, and decision-makers in immediate crisis and disaster situations.

Value Added: The CrisesData service adds value by strengthening the infrastructure for analysing the vulnerability, preparedness, and resilience of individuals and social structures in crisis and disaster situations. This measure is particularly relevant as it addresses the need for improved findability, accessibility, and cross-disciplinary linkage of crisis-related data from various sources, building on the project “Better results through interoperability and standardised research data management (**BestFDM**)” (Lenzner et al., 2022; RatSWD, 2023d, 2023f). By collaborating with other NFDI consortia, such as NFDI4Earth and NFDI4Health, and emphasising a social science perspective in crisis research, the service supports the interdisciplinary exchange of competencies and facilitates more efficient contributions from KonsortSWD and external partners, ultimately making vital data accessible to new stakeholders like civil protection organisations and policymakers. The service also aims to improve data interoperability by harmonising crisis-related survey instruments and establishing a coordination centre for rapid knowledge exchange.

Existing user base: Service in development

Work Programme - Summary: In the second funding phase, ongoing processes of the first phase will be concluded, namely the analysis of the German panel infrastructure regarding the needs for crisis-related information, the addition of a security and defence perspective and the development of a survey module on crises and disasters. The information platform on crisis-related data and survey instruments will be consolidated and improved. ~~In the second funding phase, the crisis-related data platform and survey instruments will be consolidated and improved.~~ A coordination centre at the RatSWD office (**M1-1**) will unite researchers, practitioners, and decision-makers in immediate crisis and disaster situations, improving quick access to quality-secured data.

Detailed Plan: The project will conclude the analysis of the major German panel studies regarding the needs for crisis-related information and hold a second exchange meeting with representatives

from crisis research and social sciences infrastructures in Q4/25. In collaboration with the Bundeswehr Centre of Military History and Social Sciences, additional empirical knowledge requirements on individuals, households and companies will be identified, broadening the project's thematic scope by including a perspective of security and defence research. In Q1/26, a respective paper will be finalised and submitted to a suitable journal. A module for a survey instrument on a relevant crisis-related topic will be developed by Q1/26. In ~~Q2/26~~ ~~Q4/25~~ and ~~Q1/26~~, the information platform and survey instruments will be evaluated through a user survey on usability, missing information, and improvement suggestions. The findings will be documented in an evaluation report (Q3/26) with recommendations for modifications. Technical expertise will guide suitable modifications to the website, including structural design and content expansions. The survey instruments will be enhanced for usability and additional topics, and integrated into the [ZIS Open Access Repository](#) where possible. A coordination centre concept will be developed with a RatSWD working group accompanying this project, outlining procedures to unite researchers, practitioners, and decision-makers in crisis and disaster situations, ensuring quick access to quality-secured data and rapid responses (Q3/26). The concept will formulate general steps and specific crises scenarios. A stakeholder workshop will review the concept in terms of feasibility and possible integration into existing structures, followed by the launch of the coordination centre (Q4/26). To consolidate the network and strengthen cross-sector linkages, a crisis data network meeting will be organised after one year (Q4/27). This meeting will discuss current developments in crisis research and management and their implications for data infrastructures. In the case of further continuation of the service after 2027, the network meeting should take place once a year. With the support of [M5-1](#), the project will develop a business model (Q4/26-Q2/27) to consolidate the service and ensure long-term sustainability. This process will begin at least one year before funding concludes, incorporating the advice of the RatSWD working group and NFDI project partners, while considering existing structures in crisis and disaster research and management. Over the entire duration of the project, its three pillars (information platform, collection of survey instruments, coordination centre) will be promoted among the stakeholders relevant to crisis and disaster fields, including different scientific communities and data-interested practitioners. Over the entire duration of the project, it will be promoted among the stakeholders relevant to crises and disasters. Existing collaborations with the Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK), the German Committee for Disaster Risk Reduction (DKKV) and notably NFDI4Earth, and NFDI4Health will be leveraged and expanded through collaborative opportunities. The service will closely cooperate with the Public Relations Office ([M1-4](#)) and develop further strategies of dissemination.

~~M4-4: DisclosureControl – (Semi-)Automatic Disclosure Control for RDC~~

Profile: DisclosureControl				Category: Workflow/Pipeline				
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs				Section: -				
DFG KPI: Number of executions				Partners: BAMF, Destatis, IAB, KBA				

Prop. KPI: Number of stakeholders implementing the solution, number of data users benefiting from the solution	Basic Service:
Internal Collab.: M2-6	Status: Development
Consortia: NFDI4Health, BERD@NFDI, GHGA, NFDI4Memory	External Collab.: UNECE, IDAN

Function: ~~This service will (semi-)automate the post-tabular disclosure control of results from external researchers using highly sensitive data.~~

Value Added: ~~The proposed measure adds value by implementing a semi-automated disclosure control solution for RDCs handling highly sensitive data (e.g., Perry & Rammstedt, 2016), improving efficiency and reducing risks associated with manual processes. This measure is particularly relevant as it addresses the challenges of resource allocation, speed of results delivery, and transparency in disclosure control practices across RDCs, where manual disclosure control is currently a time-consuming and resource-intensive task that binds highly skilled staff. By semi-automation, researchers can receive results more swiftly, thus minimising waiting times and ensuring that output is consistently checked against standardised rules, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of services provided by RDCs.~~

Existing user base: Service in development

Work Programme – Summary: ~~The measure develops a concept for semi-automating the disclosure control of sensitive data and implements a tool that can be used by various stakeholders. First, requirements for disclosure control and (IT) infrastructure are collected incorporating stakeholder needs. Building upon existing partial solutions, code is developed. The open-source solution allows stakeholders to adapt it to institutional requirements, contribute improvements, and guarantee its sustainability. Transparent documentation and training tools enable researchers to understand and comply with the rules implemented. Re-use scenarios of the tool will be discussed with other consortia handling sensitive data.~~

Detailed Plan: ~~The measure develops a tool that (semi-)automates disclosure control. Most data providers have developed routines and rules for manual or even partially script-based disclosure control. Therefore, the measure first collects pre-existing solutions and rules, as well as the stakeholder’s needs for a semi-automated solution. Then, a concept including criteria for the programming of the solution is designed (Q3/26). During this stage, a close collaboration with the stakeholders is necessary to ensure that the solution to be developed is useful to a broad target group. The concept is then programmed and tested. For the solution to work for as many stakeholders as possible, the program has to be open source and easily adaptable. Thus, a suitable software has to be chosen. Once a minimum viable product (MVP) is designed and documented, the solution will first be tested and debugged within the group of partners in this measure (Q4/26). Thereafter, stakeholders identified in the beginning of the work package will be asked to participate in the testing to further develop the solution. Throughout the programming and testing phase, transparent documentation for data users is developed resulting in a final report with a business model (Q4/27). The documentation’s goal is to make the rules of disclosure control transparent to~~

~~data users and foster a deeper understanding of its importance. Additionally, training tools (for example videos, documents, etc.) are developed to further enable data users to code in a way that makes disclosure control as little restrictive as possible (Q2/28). For long-term sustainability, all programs, documentation, and training tools are made available via open source such that all potential stakeholders can benefit and further develop the service (Q4/28).~~

M4-5: RDC Motor Performance and Physical Fitness – First RDC for Sports Science Data

Profile: RDC Motor Performance (FDZ MoL)					Category: Data Curation			
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDM professionals				Section: Infrastructure				
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated				Partners: KIT				
Prop. KPI: Number of datasets published, downloads				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: M2-4, M3-6, M3-7, M4-8				Status: Development				
Consortia: NFDI4Health				External Collab.: Leibniz Science Campus DiTraRe				

Function: This RDC supports sports scientists in sharing and reusing sensitive data and in acquiring expertise in research data management.

Value Added: As an interdisciplinary field, sports science bridges the humanities, social-, and natural sciences, creating synergies that benefit all stakeholders. In summer 2023, the German Sports Association’s ad hoc committee “RDM in sports science” (co-chairperson: Katja Keller) surveyed 122 researchers at different career stages about RDM. The results illustrate that researchers work with multiple data types and follow a multiple-storage strategy, mainly using business computers and institutional servers for data storage. With the first repository (MO|RE data) and RDC in sports science, the RDM group at the KIT’s sports institute serves as the primary contact for sports science researchers and from related fields in KonsortSWD, like education, economics, or social sciences.

Existing user base: The MO|RE data repository underpins the RDC with public use file access (Klemm, Bös, et al., 2024). It stores 41 datasets (19 aggregated, 22 raw) by 58 authors, totalling 63,117 items. Datasets include motor performance data of 23 harmonised test items and additional data as age, gender and body composition and were published between 1970 - 2024.

Work Programme - Summary: Building on the foundation of the RDC for Sports Science in the first funding period (Klemm, Kron, et al., 2024), with initial access to sensitive data from 2024-25, the following goals are being pursued: further development of interdisciplinary data use (mapping/harmonisation, metadata), enhancing RDM support for sports scientists, creating a dashboard for RDC data, and developing remote access to analyse sensitive data without data exchange.

Detailed Plan: A key deliverable is a robust database that will house all the data collected and processed by the RDC (Q4/27). This database will serve as a valuable resource for researchers and stakeholders involved in the project. Among the project’s milestones is the development and

implementation of a revised mapping scheme (Q3/26). This will involve updating the existing mapping scheme to enhance data visualisation and interpretation. We will also create a revised metadata scheme, in line with KonsortSWD practice, that will improve the organisation, accessibility, and usability of the data stored in the RDC database (Q3/26). A significant milestone is the launch of a Data Dashboard (Q4/26). This interactive platform will allow users to easily navigate, analyse, and interpret the data stored in the RDC database. Finally, we plan on implementing a concept for remote access (Q3/27), (M2-4). This will enable researchers to access the RDC database remotely, increasing accessibility. We also plan to develop a comprehensive business model (Q4/27) that will be implemented post-2027. This model will outline the strategies, revenue streams, and operational plans to ensure the sustainability and growth of the project.

We regularly present the RDC's progress in digital exchange formats such as NFDI Talks and at relevant national and international conferences in the fields of RDM, sports, and health sciences.

M4-6: FirmData – Continuous Provision of Firm Data (A)

Profile: FirmData					Category: Data Curation			
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers								
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated								
Prop. KPI: Usage of datasets								
Internal Collab.: M2-4, M3-7								
Consortia: BERD@NFDI								
					Section: Industry			
					Partners: EBDC, RDC Ruhr at the RWI, ifo			
					Basic Service: -			
					Status: Development			
					External Collab.: Stifterverband			

Function: Continuous Provision of Firm Data is an extended service based on the project "Access to Firm Data" from the first funding phase, also turning from a *support* to a *data curation service*. It provides data through cooperations with firms as well as a systematic collection of research (data) cooperations between academia and firms using well-established German firm surveys.

Value Added: The measure provides sustainable, long-term, data access to firm datasets, usually inaccessible to research (Gottschalk et al., 2023), and documents firms' data-cooperation with academia.

Existing user base: Service in development

Work Programme - Summary: The FirmData measure focuses on the sustainable and long-term provision of FAIR data products for the social and economic sciences, derived from firm cooperations. We develop semi-automatic curation routines to streamline future data deliveries from firms, minimising the cost of data provision. Additionally, established ifo Surveys will gather detailed overviews on cooperations between firms and researchers.

Detailed Plan: "Access to Firm Data" initiates firm cooperations and provides obtained data to the scientific community, offering significant value for empirical research across various fields. This typically inaccessible data is curated and documented in a FAIR form. However, the initial data provision will become outdated over time and therefore of limiting use for future policy-relevant

research. For this reason, the first work package of the extended service focuses on the sustainability and extension of the data provision initiated during the first funding period. On the one hand, firm cooperations are to be reorganised in such a way that sustainable data provision is made possible (Q1/26). On the other hand, reusable coding pipelines and routines are to be developed (Q2/26) to enable the low-cost, nearly standardised, and automatic curation of additional (data) waves, even after the end of the project. In the second work package, the measure aims to create a systematic and long-term overview of existing data cooperation between German companies and the scientific community through expert interviews and data from ifo Business Survey and Management Surveys (Q4/25 and Q1/26). Our goal is to provide up to three datasets from firm cooperations on a long-term and sustainable basis (Q3/26). To make them known throughout the desired research community, we promote the new data products on websites and social media platforms, e.g., with the Public Relations Office (M1-4) as well as Forum4MICA (M3-4) (Q4/26). The two work packages are linked to the initiatives mentioned in the profile table above and will each develop a suitable business model for the data products (Q4/27).

M4-7: Linking Data

Profile: Linking Data				Category: Data-Curation				
DFG-Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs				Section: -				
DFG KPI: Number of datasets curated				Partners: BAMF, Destatis, IAB				
Prop. KPI: Number of linkage projects, downloads of templates				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.:				Status: Development				
Consortia: BERD@NFDI, NFDI4Health				External Collab.: German Record Linkage Center				

Function: ~~This measure enables the linkage of sensitive data for the same individuals held by different RDCs and other data owners for the scientific community.~~

Value Added: ~~Value is added by creating a vast data treasure that opens new analysis potential for the scientific community while providing essential support to facilitate the creation of linked datasets, effectively breaking down existing data silos. This is especially relevant as linking sensitive datasets from different data holders is currently limited by legal frameworks and discrepancies in methodology and definitions among data providers, hindering the full potential of data analysis and research. By developing a generic framework to facilitate the practical implementation of specific linkage projects, preparing for future projects through coordinated workflows, and providing funding for specific linkage projects, this measure addresses the practical, financial, and methodological barriers to linking datasets, ultimately enabling the scientific community to open up new analysis potential and advancing research in the field. Further linkage projects can be modelled from NFDI4Health or BERD@NFDI. This approach is analogous to linkage projects funded by the Austrian Academy of Science.~~

Existing user base: Service in development

Work Programme – Summary: Based on extensive experience from related projects (German Record Linkage Centre by IAB), a pilot project between the Deutsche Bundesbank and the Federal Statistical Office (Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis), 2023), as well as an EU-funded project to link migration register and survey data (BAMF), this measure will provide a generic and versatile framework to facilitate the practical implementation of different linkage projects. It will also support the implementation of selected linkage projects. The service “Linking Data” supports data-holding institutions by providing organisational expertise concerning data linkage projects, legal expertise and financial support for these, as well as best practices for the technical process of linkage data from different data holders.

Detailed Plan: The service “Linking Data” provides a versatile basis for linking data from different sources via two actions. As a basis, it enables data-holding institutions to link their data amongst each other. In addition to flexible financial support for linkage projects, action 1 will provide a generic framework, developed as part of the work package, to facilitate the practical implementation of specific linkage projects and re-use their data. Both aspects are substantial challenges for administrative data in Germany. Initially, organisational, technical and legal challenges will be identified. Given the partners’ highly specialist experiences from previous linkage projects, earlier observed challenges can be avoided. The aim is to create and publish essential documents that are necessary for the realisation of linkage projects, such as declarations of consent for linkage permission or templates for contracts between data owning institutions (Q1/27). A further focus lies on developing workflows (Q1/27) that are required to make the linked data products re-usable for the scientific community via RDCs in the long term. The service thus aims to overcome existing hurdles and prepare for the expansion of linkage projects that will follow the implementation of the planned Research Data Act. Against this backdrop, it will also develop a business model to sustain linkage projects re-using the methods developed here (Q3/27). Action 2 will support promising linkage projects through application and selection processes (Q1/26). This includes tender texts or templates for the expression of interest. The project will draw on experiences from other NFDI consortia for these steps. Moreover, a catalogue of evaluation criteria will be developed (Q1/26). The selection of projects will be aligned with the selection of flex funds (cf. 3.4.5) whenever possible.

M4-8: QualidataNet Portal – Federated Archiving Infrastructure and Technical Solutions for Qualitative Data

Profile: QualidataNet Portal					Category: Web Application			
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs, Data professionals					Section: ELSA, EduTrain, Metadata, Infrastructure			
DFG KPI: Number of visits					Partners: DIPF, DIW Berlin, DZHW, eLabour, IDS, RDC Qualiservice/ University of Bremen			
Prop. KPI: Number of downloads					Basic Service: -			
Internal Collab.: -					Status: Operation / Extension			
Consortia: NFDI4Health, Text+, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Culture					External Collab.: SSHOC, ISDFPN			

Function: Promote and facilitate access to and findability of qualitative data by providing a coordinated, user- and service-oriented infrastructure. Beyond service operation and network extension, QualidataNet will be extended to include: a) a data protection-compliant anonymisation tool suited for the complex anonymisation and pseudonymisation of text data ~~and b) a survey on the need for common technical service components for the preparation, archiving, and provision of qualitative research data at the RDCs and data holders.~~

Value Added: For the first time, QualidataNet offers a central point of entry for finding, managing, sharing, and re-using sensitive qualitative data (Mozygemba et al., 2023). QualidataNet connects relevant actors and addresses the needs of different qualitative communities in a coordinated manner, thus counteracting fragmentation and parallel developments in this area. The integration of further qualitative archives and RDCs increases the scope of the network. Researchers get advice on archiving options and find the archiving partner that suits them best. The joint platform increases the FAIRness and visibility of qualitative data. This FAIRness is also optimised by the controlled vocabulary “QualiTerm”. Low-threshold networking in QualidataNet also enables smaller archives to participate in exchange and joint development of quality criteria and standards. QualidataNet also maintains and provides an existing [data protection-compliant anonymisation tool](#) as service for textual data for researchers and RDCs. This tool will be maintained ~~and developed further~~ as part of KonsortSWD’s portfolio. The tool significantly facilitates the complex anonymisation and pseudonymisation of text data by offering flexible replacement levels and transparent documentation. It reduces costs and increases reliability of the time-consuming processing of qualitative data. Exportable replacement concepts enable researchers to share topic-specific replacement schemes, which can be further developed by RDCs and scientific communities. ~~Previously unmet needs of the communities (e.g. implementation of semi-automatic recognition in the marking of sensitive information, options for teamwork on an anonymisation project, the integration of the anonymisation of audio files etc.) will be addressed and possibilities for implementation will be examined. Finally, a survey on the need for technical solutions and service components for preparing, archiving, and providing qualitative data will lay the groundwork for advancing the services of qualitative RDCs.~~

Existing user base: Launched in December 2023, the QualidataNet website had 700 visits in its first month. Several RDCs using qualitative data have integrated elements of the “QualiTerm” vocabulary into their metadata descriptions. The QualidataNet network consists of six data providers, with others interested in joining. Since 2021, around 500 users have downloaded the [anonymisation tool](#), with regular requests for use and development from various disciplines. RDC Qualiservice applies the tool in data curation, and it was presented in an international [webinar](#) at the International Association for Social Science Information Service & Technology (IASSIST) qualitative working group.

Work Programme - Summary: The measure continues and expands QualidataNet as the central point of entry for qualitative research. Activities include network coordination, exchange on quality

standards for data curation workflows, services for researchers, advancement of FAIR metadata, and controlled vocabularies for qualitative data. Services for researchers include information and advice on suitable archiving partners, qualitative datasets, and aspects of data sharing. The network continuously integrates new partners. The measure also includes the representation in committees and the creation of a business model for sustainable operation.

Detailed Plan - Operation: Action 1 provides the continuous operation and further expansion of QualidataNet, which was successfully implemented as the central point of entry for qualitative data. It coordinates the exchange within the network and joint reconciliation of quality standards as well as the integration of further network partners beyond KonsortSWD. Researchers from various disciplines receive support in finding suitable archiving partners, which will be further facilitated by an archive-wizard (Q3/27). Data-holding institutions receive support in questions of archiving and the provision of qualitative research data. The measure includes the continued operation, maintenance, and expansion of the search portal and the harvester, the integration of additional datasets, the optimisation of the searchengine, and the support of data holders in questions of metadata standards for the description of qualitative data as well as the maintenance and provision of the controlled vocabulary QualiTerm in order to refine the search results and increase the FAIRness of qualitative (meta-)data. The measure will also develop a business model for the sustainable and long-term operation of the service (Q4/27).

Detailed Plan - Extension: Action 2 adds new functionality to QualidataNet. To support anonymisation, QualidataNet is extended through an existing [tool](#) and related user [basic](#) support. The tool will be maintained ~~developed further in line with user requirements (e.g., implementation of semi-automatic marking of certain entities)~~ (Q2/28). ~~Prior to new versions, the~~ [A](#)nonymisation concepts and replacement schemes developed by RDCs and the communities will be made accessible via QualidataNet (Q4/26), allowing researchers to apply and develop existing replacement-concepts that fit their thematic focus. A business model will also be developed for this tool (Q4/27). ~~Action 3 carries out a needs analysis. It includes 1) developing an overview of workflows, problems and efforts in the preparation, archiving, curation and provision of qualitative research data through workshops (Q1/27); 2) members of qualitative RDCs and selected data producers in different user communities will be interviewed and possible services will be discussed in focus groups; 3) the data is analysed, needs, requirements, and user preferences are identified, published, and discussed with researchers and infrastructure providers (Q3/27).~~

M4-9: StanDem

Profile: StanDem						Category: Support/Consulting		
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: Researchers, RDCs				Section: -				
DFG KPI: -				Partners: GESIS				
Prop. KPI: Number of projects supported				Basic Service: -				
Internal Collab.: M3-4, M3-5, M4-3, "AG Demographische Standards" through M1-1, FDI Committee				Status: Operation				
Consortia: NFDI4Health				External Collab.: ZIS by GESIS				

Function: This service continues work on [Harmonised Variables](#) from the first funding period and promotes the quality and comparability of widely used sociodemographic measures across datasets in Germany through the "tandem" of harmonisation methods: input harmonisation (using standardised questionnaire items) and output harmonisation (using standardised variables in datasets).

Value Added: StanDem (short for "Standardising (Socio-)Demographic data" improves the (substantive) interoperability and reusability of data across data sources by a) facilitating data analysis since key variables are already appropriately coded in the data, and b) easing the combination of data from different sources, e.g., to enable analyses of small subpopulations not feasible with data from just one source. StanDem builds on the well-recognized work of the working group "Demographische Standards" (Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik et al., 2016, 2024) and recent work of RatSWD (RatSWD, 2023d).

Existing user base: Roundtables held in 2021 and 2022 included dozens of survey project representatives from various institutions and disciplines. Sociodemographic Standard Variables from the first funding round were implemented in two major datasets, the German General Social Survey (ALLBUS) and the National Educational Panel Study (NEPS) SC6. Publications (Ortmanns, 2020; Schneider et al., 2022, 2023) were viewed over 1,200 times and downloaded nearly 1,000 times. Documentation for each sociodemographic characteristic has been published at the [ZIS Open Access Repository](#) since December 2023, with entries viewed 108-214 times and downloaded 5-14 times a month.

Work Programme - Summary: StanDem will offer consulting and support to data producers wishing to apply sociodemographic standard questionnaire items, and to RDCs, harmonisation projects and data users wishing to use the sociodemographic standard variables. It will also continue an annual roundtable (Q3/26-2028) bringing together data projects from various domains, RDCs, researchers, and the "AG Demographische Standards" to discuss current issues and challenges in standardising sociodemographics.

Detailed Plan: The measure will present the service to the extended FDI Committee ([M1-2](#)) to illustrate the potential for data interoperability inherent in sociodemographic standard variables. It will link to the helpdesk ([M3-5](#)) and Forum4MICA ([M3-4](#)) and existing consulting services at GESIS

to provide support. The latter will be documented to help improve the service by adding use cases and solutions to the documentation. An annual StanDem roundtable meeting will be organised, following the positive experiences from the first funding period. The measure will continue to bring interested parties from KonsortSWD and relevant other NFDI consortia (e.g., NFDI4Health) together to discuss challenges, present solutions and identify gaps in the existing documentation of sociodemographic standard items and variables. Challenges and gaps will be documented, and funding for potential extensions may come from KonsortSWD's flex funds. Identified needs for new standard questionnaire items will be communicated to the "AG Demographische Standards". A business model will be developed in the first two years of the project as well (Q4/27). At the end of the funding period, an updated and extended version of the existing documentation (Schneider et al., 2023) will be published, including tightened specifications using lessons learned during the second funding phase (Q4/28). An indirect output will be further datasets with sociodemographic standard variables published by RDCs.

5.5 Task Area 5 – Governance and Sustainability

TA-Lead: Christof Wolf

Task Area 5 - Governance and Sustainability is a critical component of KonsortSWD's proposal for continuation as an NFDI consortium and for securing a sustainable provision of its services. It focuses on coordinating efforts across the consortium, in particular to develop viable business models for a sustainable operation of RDM services by 2027, closely cooperating with NFDI4Culture leveraging expertise from both consortia. Such coordination ensures the long-term viability and effectiveness of KonsortSWD's services beyond the current funding.

Contributors: DZHW contributes to developing business models. DIW, IIfBi, GESIS, and WZB contribute to coordination; as lead institution, GESIS handles financial administration and monitoring.

Objectives & Measures: TA5 aligns with three key KonsortSWD objectives: at the core, assuring the reliability necessary to build research strategies on our services (O6), making KonsortSWD known as the platform for RDM services within our communities and integrate our services with third-party funded projects (O5), and helping develop strategic partnerships (O9).

To achieve these objectives, TA5 will implement four measures. A systematic assessment of existing business models, workshop series, individual consultations, and a conference on integrated sustainability approaches are conducted (M5-1). A Coordination Office (CoO) is established to support TAs, facilitating consortium-wide events, and ensuring integration with NFDI and international activities (M5-2). Proper management of finances, contract negotiations, and implementation of a refined monitoring system are ensured (M5-3). Flex funds are administered, providing flexibility for emerging opportunities (M5-4).

M5-1: Sustainable Business Models

DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: internal; NFDI								
DFG KPI: -								
Prop. KPI: -								
Internal Collab.: all services								
Consortia: NFDI4Culture								

Function: A consistent framework for developing business and operating models for KonsortSWD’s services is created and supports implementation and consolidation.

Value Added: Creation of long-term perspectives for developed services

Existing User Base: n.a.

Work Programme - Summary: This measure establishes concepts and an organisational framework for developing and consolidating business and operation models for KonsortSWD services. Building on existing models, the approach is tested with two selected services. On this basis ~~Operationally~~, individual concepts will be prepared in a workshop series, tightly coordinated with NFDI4Culture to share experiences, bringing together distributed expertise from both contexts, and utilising the structural similarities in the communities involved.

Detailed Plan: Sustainable business models are crucial indicators of mature services in RDM, transforming them into indispensable infrastructures (Fecher et al., 2021) and ensuring long-term viability and reliability, and fostering embeddedness of services in research practices. However, developing these models is challenging in the evolving RDM landscape, where user engagement and revenue generation experiences are not at all widespread. There is an urgent need to systematically connect and synthesise knowledge about effective business models in this domain. KonsortSWD is committed to developing viable business models for its services by the end of 2027. This approach aims to create models that can adapt to the post-2028 NFDI, potentially integrating elements into permanent NFDI structures.

KonsortSWD has identified several funding models (cf. 4.4.4) as components of sustainable business models. These include community-based operations, consortium-shared costs, individual and institutional fees, membership-based funding, existing and top-up institutional funds, and third-party funding. In addition there a number of business and operating models for RDM services that have been described in the literature. ~~The work programme includes planning to adapt the business model to changing research demands, technological innovations, and new environmental expectations and conditions. This ensures the model remains relevant and effective over time.~~

To address this critical task, KonsortSWD builds on expertise from science research at DZHW and has partnered with NFDI4Culture (their measure “Sustainability Framework” TA4-M2), combining management, business, administrative, and academic expertise. The collaboration will involve joint events and potentially a conference (see below, A4). It might be extended to other consortia.

Measure M5-1 comprises four main actions:

Value Added: Pools resources previously allocated to individual TAs to facilitate flows of information and exploit synergies. Also integrates a Service Advocate for Basic Services

Existing Communities: n.a.

Work Programme - Summary: Act as unified and tightly integrated forum for coordinating execution of KonsortSWD's work programme

Detailed Plan: To synchronise activities throughout our growing network and keeping track of the developments in NFDI, KonsortSWD will redesign the organisation of its coordination. Learning from NFDI4Culture, the Coordination Office (CoO) will be headed by an executive director and will bundle all coordination capacities previously allocated to the TAs. This also includes the director of the RatSWD office, who will contribute a significant share of their capacities to the CoO. The CoO will also provide PR and event planning support to all the consortium's activities. This measure will additionally have funding to support consortium-wide events like the annual Network Meeting. A Service Advocate will be appointed to liaise with Base4NFDI and relevant basic services to facilitate integration into the KonsortSWD landscape. In terms of staff, KonsortSWD will be able to build on the invaluable experience collected in the first funding phase. The CoO will focus on three actions:

A1: Support of TAs: Prepare meetings within TAs, of the Executive Board, and of the Steering Committee monthly (ongoing); prepare consortium meetings in the NFDI association twice a year (ongoing); document meetings (minutes and materials) in TAs, of the Executive Board, and of the Steering Committee (ongoing); facilitate information exchange between TAs and NFDI activities (ongoing).

A2: Consortium-wide events and efforts: Initiate and coordinate consortium-wide activities, e.g., interactions at conferences, cooperation with federal state RDM initiatives and other RDM stakeholders (ongoing); organise the annual Network Meeting (yearly); provide support for various consortium activities, for onboarding of new staff and internal dialogue in established formats like the "KonsortSWD Mingle", develop further community events (ongoing); to optimise collaboration and efficiency, an externally moderated workshop at the beginning of the second funding phase will review communication processes and tool development procedures between content and technical managers, utilising existing, easily adaptable templates (Q4/25).

A3: NFDI and International Integration: Systematically monitor activities in NFDI through the TAs; collaborate with TAs to maintain and develop contacts with other consortia, international partners, and initiatives; maintain an overview of activities in various sections; coordinate KonsortSWD's contribution to NFDI-wide activities and strategies through a Service Advocate, liaise with Base4NFDI and relevant basic services to facilitate integration of basic services into the KonsortSWD landscape (cf. 3.2.4); integrate international activities into the work programme (all of the above: ongoing).

Grounded in research funding: We plan to include support for data archiving and curation by KonsortSWD partners in funding organisation calls. To devise promising strategies, we will

collaborate with NFDI4Culture. Ideally, projects comprising data collection will be encouraged to process their data for reuse in cooperation with RatSWD-accredited RDCs or related repositories.

M5-3: Financial and Contract Administration and Quality Management

Profile: Financial and Contract Administration and Quality Management								Category: -	
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
Target Group: internal									
DFG KPI: -									
Prop. KPI: -									
Internal Collab.: all measures									
Consortia: -									

Function: To allocate funds, trace their spending in accordance with DFG regulations and run and develop further a consortium-wide quality management

Value Added: Assures proper, efficient, and well-communicated administration of funds and contracts plus a transparent, indicative quality management

Existing Communities: n.a.

Work Programme - Summary: This measure has three actions - 1) Financial Administration, 2) Contract Administration and 3) Quality Management

Detailed Plan: For action 1, tasks include managing the consortium's finances, ensuring compliance with funding conditions, and reporting to funders. A crucial component is a constant dialogue with financial administrators at all funded partner institutions. In this function, this measure will also continue to co-lead the exchange of financial administrators in NFDI (Finanzkreis), a best-practice forum of exchange. For action 2 this measure will manage contracts between all partners, negotiate new contracts (e.g., with new partners), or terminate contracts with partners whose services are no longer part of KonsortSWD's portfolio. This will include contracts related to Base4NFDI's financing mechanism. For action 3, the measure will process short, standardised reports on measure and TA progress as well as the status on agreed KPIs (cf. 4.1). Based on this information, standardised reports and KPI data will be prepared for the Steering Committee, the Advisory Board, for DFG, the NFDI association and other relevant stakeholders. Building on the successful setup since 2020, KonsortSWD will refine its monitoring for the second funding phase and evaluate a) the transparent presentation of KPIs on our services (e.g., in a dashboard which could be adapted from the [Scorpion KPI Dashboard](#) developed at NFDI4Biodiversity) and b) project-wide usage of NFDI's [Open Project](#) instance. We will continue to contribute to NFDI's Task Force Evaluation and Monitoring to shape the debate to which extent and based on which performance indicators the success of NFDI can most aptly be evaluated.

M5-4: Flex funds

Profile: Flex funds							Category: -	
DFG Key Points	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Target Group: -								Section: -
DFG KPI: -								Partners: GESIS
Prop. KPI: -								Basic Service: -
Internal Collab.: -								Status: -
Consortia: -								External Collab.: -

Function: Allocate flex funds to shape services along community needs, and address new developments. After 2028 for adaptations following from the German Science Council's recommendations

Value Added: Flexibility in funding and transparent allocation process

Existing Communities: n.a.

Work Programme - Summary: Supports the selection process and administers flex funds.

Detailed Plan: Funds will be allocated based on a well-defined process (described in [Allocation and Spending of Funds and flex fund](#)). Those funds will continue to ascertain that KonsortSWD can dynamically respond to challenges in RDM and those relating to building OneNFDI (Q4/25, ongoing). This activity will gain importance in 2029-30 (cf. [3.4.6](#)).

6 Additional Aspects

6.1 Equal Opportunity and Diversity

KonsortSWD emphasises equal opportunities and diversity in its functions and organisational structures. The consortium's leadership (co-spokespersons) include both male and female representatives, with four of five Task Areas having a female and a male lead. Among co-spokespersons, 6 out of 17 are female. RatSWD, part of KonsortSWD, maintains gender parity, further promoting inclusive representation. Positions in KonsortSWD have been nearly equally allocated between genders, with a slightly higher proportion for female scientists. In 2023, 54.6% of staff were female, 44.3% male, and 1.1% were not classified. Additionally, KonsortSWD partners publish job offers internationally and support language acquisition for all employees, enhancing diversity and inclusion. KonsortSWD's working language is English, whenever appropriate.

6.2 Disclosure

KonsortSWD has used AI tools for grammar, style, spelling, creation of summaries, and translation that do not affect the scientific content.

Appendix

A1 Bibliography and list of references

All sources and data repositories, information infrastructures and software cited in the text are provided below. Contributions by members of KonsortSWD are highlighted in **bold**.

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